

THE INFLUENCE OF MICROFINANCE INITIATIVES ON CAPABILITIES
OF VIETNAMESE PARTICIPANTS - A QUALITATIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Research purpose: In developed countries such as the USA, the UK and Europe, microfinance is becoming a global phenomenon, as well as in developing countries. Against this development, however, there has been little in the way of research to try to understand the multidimensional impacts of the programs, particularly in Vietnam. This research attempts to explore how microfinance initiatives influence Vietnamese participants' capabilities. The conclusion of this thesis will provide answers to two sub-questions: investigating the impacts of microfinance programs as well as examining how microfinance programs promote these impacts.

Research methodology/design: This research adopts the social and financial exclusion framework to understand the effects of microfinance schemes. Meanwhile, social exclusion is gradually being used in many nations such as the UK, Australia and Europe, to facilitate the influences of microfinance. The concept of social exclusion provides a multifaceted approach to understand the drawbacks for households with low incomes; one of the primary purposes of microfinance initiatives in Vietnam was the distribution of financial products and services to those unable to use traditional financial products—financial exclusion is critical. The research strategy of this study relies on three major areas: what an individual desires, what capabilities a person has to achieve it, including freedom and the choice to do the things that he or she values, and the agency. A triangulation of data collection was adopted, including semi-structured interviews and participant observation, as this research focused on individual experiences and narratives.

Research findings: Research findings revealed the effects of microfinance, including the influence on participants from a financial aspect, the impact on the social dimensions of the participants and the production of improved capabilities. Furthermore, interviewees referred to the economic effects by highlighting four key issues: increased levels of savings, increased financial capacity, increased financial security and higher levels of economic participation. Such results were accomplished by integrating the financial aspects of the programs, as well as by providing support networks.

The social aspect of the microfinance schemes was mainly affected by involvement in savings and loans. Such services offered incentives for social interaction with participants. The social impacts felt by participants was more significant support, greater confidence, mutual feelings and a sense of belonging. All of these impacts are strongly interlinked in relation to social networks that can be shaped as people meet, hence, enhancing the social capital. What was noticed was that a mixture of financial and social factors provided participants with a more substantial capability.

Research implications: The critical impact of this work is that if initiatives are actually to enhance the capacities of low-income people and families, then more financial services and opportunities for people need to be provided, allowing the interaction with each other. This is a mixture of the two programs that increase people's capacity.

Keywords: microfinance, developing countries, participant capabilities

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Research Background and Motivation

Every day, more than 23,000 people around the world suffer from extreme poverty, making a total of 8 million people per year. Eight Millennium Development Goals were set by the United Nations (UN) at the end of 2005 (Le Blanc, 2015). The ultimate goal was to significantly reduce the number of people living on less than one US dollar a day and to reduce the number of people who are starving to zero. As a result, recent studies have shown that the number of people who actually live on less than \$1 dollar a day is decreasing.

Poverty is indeed a complex issue that involves a multi-faceted solution. Studies from multiple developing countries found that there was a lack of clarity about poverty and they raised the questions of how many people are living below the poverty line and the question of how poverty is measured. Saunders (2005) published a comprehensive study in a seminal article describing the “poverty wars” in developing countries. The book not only outlines the income-based/asset-based disparities in poverty but also addresses the development of more multidimensional poverty interventions, such as the context for social exclusion and the potential solutions (Mitchell & Macció, 2018).

Microfinance has evolved as a global phenomenon since the development of Muhammad Yunus’ Grameen Bank Project, an instrument helping in the war against poverty since 1976. Globally, this was seen as a significant and positive way in which the poor could be mobilised (Yunus, 1982). It is widely said that Yunus has initially tried to identify the best models, forms of services and savings groups in several developing countries such as Bangladesh, India and Sri Lanka (Yunus et al., 2010).

There is now a number of experiments being undertaken on creative microfinance programs which are unique to each country or region and that are customised to citizens’ requirements. In several emerging countries such as India and Sri Lanka, the general concepts of the Grameen model have been widely embraced and are even common across the areas where it has already been implemented, for example the African countries including Kenya, Libya and Ghana (Yunus et al., 2010). Other research projects have also studied the Grameen microfinance model to see whether it can work in Australia (Hulm, 2009). Microfinance initiatives in India and China are based on loans for the poor and arose as a solution to the shortage of traditional rural-sector banks (Yunus, 2007)

A wide range of literature is accessible on emerging microfinance activities in the developing world and there have been many reviews of these initiatives (Kaboski & Townsend, 2011). Although success stories are more convenient, more and more research studies investigate those shortcomings (Choudhury & Dusuki, 2008) and lessons are learned for potential future efforts (Park & Ren, 2001). The literature contains assessments of existing programs (Yunus, 2007), market research of possible interventions (Rao et al., 2009) and current program

outlines (Ameer, 2013). There are also descriptions of the relationships between microfinance and the regulatory environment (Park & Ren, 2001). While there was an extensive publication on microfinance programs evaluations worldwide, particularly in developing countries, the impact of these programs on participants in Vietnam has hardly been assessed or understood.

This work was motivated by the fact that there is a need for further investigation from the perspective of participants of microfinance and their impressions of the services need to be better understood, as well as how those programs have affected their lives. The goal of this study was to maintain integrity by allowing the perspectives of the participants to be expressed in their own language through the framework of social exclusion and financial exclusion.

Social exclusion can be understood as “the lack of denial of resources, rights, goods and services, and the inability to participate in the normal relationships and activities available to the majority of people in society” (Levitas et al., 2007, p. 9). Meanwhile, financial exclusion is expressed as “the lack of access by certain consumers to appropriate low costs, fair and safe financial products, and services from mainstream providers” (Chant Link & Associates 2004, p. 61). The integrated framework of social and financial exclusion included multidimensional perspectives and had several indicators, allowing participants to be free to express their ideas.

The rational of capability is entirely compatible with social exclusion because both are multidimensional. The capability approach was built by concentrating on the capabilities of individuals to do and achieve. Human capability is characterized by the preference of reflecting on the spiritual importance of the potential of people to pursue the kind of existence they admire. This separates it from more developed approaches to ethical judgment, which rely primarily on subjective well-being or the provision of means for good living (Brickell et al., 2020). The capacity of a person to live a healthy life is described in terms of a collection of valuable 'beings and acts' such as being in good health or maintaining a caring partnership with someone to whom they have real access. The capability approach had three primary notions: functioning, capabilities and the dimension of the agency. “Functioning” is defined as “the various things a person may value doing or being” (Sen, 1999, p. 175). Meanwhile the “capabilities” implies the various functioning that an individual can achieve or, put differently, a person’s ability to achieve a function. Finally, the agency perspective means “someone who acts and brings about change” (Sen, 1999, p. 19). The capacity method was used to guide this study; it reflects not only on outcomes but also on people’s ability to accomplish what they desire in their lives. The theory of Capability is introduced by the philosopher - Amartya Sen in 1979. It has been commonly used in the field of human resources as well as economic development such as in many research sponsored by the United Nations Development Programme, as a wider, deeper alternative to narrowly economic criteria such as Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (Bateman 2019)..

Previous studies show that microfinance with an approach to poverty reduction that relies on reducing poverty by subsidised loan schemes cannot sustainably enter the poor household. The use of a pure approach to financial systems, which stresses financial resilience may also contribute to restricted microfinance growth, such as the alienation of the underprivileged. It

is therefore proposed that a mixed micro-finance approach could be a great option and that the Vietnamese governments and participating microfinance institutions should change their view to achieving sustainable microfinancing (Bateman, 2014). According to this strategy, microfinance institutions will be forced to follow financial systems approaches to, for example, become business microfinance institutions, while government and donor supports serve to build a sound financial and informational infrastructure and foster social intermediation for the poorer households (Bateman, 2011).

Current studies suggest that Vietnam could be more suitable for the mixed approach at this time. The biggest issue is the compromise between financial and social priorities because, obviously, it is not easy to see where the compromise will be (Putzeys, 2002). However, it should be understood that the new microfinance systems are not ideal for stable microfinance and that subsidised microfinance permanently decreased the financial viability of microfinance initiatives (Kono, 2006). Therefore, further research based on the view of participants of microfinance should be taken to explore the development of this initiative in the context of Vietnam (Rossel et al., 2015).

In the past eight years, microfinance has grown considerably across Vietnam and has received significant government funding and support from the banking sector. Nevertheless, the knowledge gap in the field still exists, particularly in terms of understanding how microfinance initiatives impact participants' lives. In fact, microfinance continues to be feasible in Vietnam, which is critical, and relates to tackling social and financial issues. As a result, further impact studies must be undertaken, in particular with a view to addressing the needs, desires and goals or values of the participants. In addition, further impact-based studies are needed which place microfinance participants at the forefront of the research.

This work is a comprehensive qualitative examination of the impact of Vietnamese microfinance initiatives and an overview of their participants. It does not aim to evaluate the programmes nor determine whether the projects had accomplished their goals or expectations. Instead, the aim of this study was to position the participants at the forefront of the research and to understand the impact of microfinance initiatives, from the perspectives of the participants, and how programs create any change. In other words, this research attempted to understand what had happened to participants as a consequence of the microfinance initiatives and what aspects of the programs enabled the improvements. This study aims to shed light on microfinance in the context of a developing country - Vietnam. The introduction of microfinance initiatives has helped people in developing countries to have more selection in their lives. This option was the trigger for supporting participants in a variety of fields, however, there is a scarcity of research focus on microfinance schemes from the views of participants (Welsh, 2019). Thus, this research contributes to the existing literature on microfinance by exploring the influences of microfinance in poverty alleviation from the perspective of participants of these initiatives.

1.2 Research Question

The main question for this study is: How do microfinance initiatives affect the participants' capabilities?

Based on the main research questions, two more sub-questions are addressed:

1. What is the influence(s)¹ of microfinance programmes on the participants?
2. How are microfinance initiatives encouraging these impacts?

1.3 Research Method

In order to preserve the intellectual credibility of the competence strategy, participants were centred on explaining what was essential to them in terms of their lives and goals. This was achieved using a qualitative research approach; data was collected by using the semi-structured interview method and participant observation.

A selection of several forms of microfinance systems were chosen for study in this research. The first program was business development for businesswomen. The second was a program which provided the no-interest loan for poor people, and savings and loans circles were the third microfinance program. Participants were interviewed using a semi-structured interview approach. Other data sources were collected through participant observation to understand the contextualised perspectives of participants' lives. For this study, a qualitative approach was necessary because the impacts of the microfinance projects from the participants' viewpoints were essential to understand.

1.4. Organisation of this Research

This work comprises of nine chapters. The literature review is set out in **Chapters 2**, with the theoretical and conceptual frameworks that underlie the analysis being explored in the chapter. This chapter further describes the other more narrowly employed structures for this analysis, namely the accumulation of income, social capital and wellbeing. The chapter ends with a reflection on the connection between the main research frameworks and the rationale of this thesis.

Chapter 3 points out the context of the microfinance field in Vietnam, including the forms of possible microfinance services such as micro-loans and micro-enterprises. The distinctive essence of microfinance in Vietnam and the descriptions of prior impact studies and evaluations in Vietnam are also addressed. The approach used to carry out this research is also described in **Chapter 3**. It includes details of the research approaches, research methodology, information on the case studies and the techniques used to collect the data, such as semi-structured interviews and participant observation.

¹ For this thesis, 'influence' refers to the difference made in a person's life as a result of the microfinance programmes.

Chapter 4 provides a detailed description of microfinance in Vietnam as well as the three microfinance programs which formed the basis of the study, including the goals and details of each project. The first is the No-interest Loans Scheme (NLS), the second is the Ambitious Women Program (AWP) and the third is the Savings and Loans Circles (SLC).

The evaluation of the research findings is provided in **Chapters 5, 6 and 7**. **Chapter 5** explores the financial impact of microfinance schemes on participants' lives and ends with descriptions of the aspects of these microfinance initiatives. **Chapter 6** provides information about the effect of microfinance projects on the social aspects of the lives of the people involved, while **Chapter 7** describes how the microfinance schemes, including the elements of the systems that culminated in improvements in efficiency, have affected the capacity of the participants.

Chapter 8 completes this study and outlines the main research topics as well as the significant results, and provides ideas for future research avenues and the implications of this research.

CHAPTER 2. MICROFINANCE

2.1. Introduction

Low-income people are often referred to as individuals or families with no properties and average wages under the minimum extent for fundamental needs. Being denied the use of standard financial services threatens to prevent them from accessing ways of improving their employment, protecting their life and responding to emergencies. Consequently, financial services and the delivery of fundamental social programs are important in playing an active role in the financial system through taxation, negotiating capacity and the growth of social equality (Luo, 2010). The provision of financial services can help poor people to permanently transform their lives and remove them from poverty by utilising these resources to develop small businesses for long term income and to become autonomous in the long term (Ledgerwood & White, 2006).

Over the years, numerous studies have been carried out with specific observations of the effect of microfinance on alleviating poverty, examining whether or not microfinance is really helping poor people escape to a better life. Most studies support the positive effects of microfinance on raising poor people's incomes or growing their security (Swain & Floro, 2012). There were a number of studies on wellness, health and vocational training that were largely definitive and constructive (McGorry et al., 2014). Such research suggests that microfinance is clearly not a tool that can turn the vulnerable into the non-poor overnight. The argument is that microfinance is essentially a long-term mechanism that aims financially to help poor people so that they can leverage their talents, expertise, resources and financial capital to break out of inequality and improve their situation for a stronger, better future (Zhang, 2017). Thus, the research indicates that in certain cases microfinance has a productive and positive effect on the vulnerable. The contribution of microfinance to reducing poverty in developing countries, however, is exceedingly difficult to separate and quantify, since deprivation represents a major social issue that pervades every aspect of culture and society (Mader, 2014). Furthermore, potential synergies exist around microfinance and other non-financial schemes as the benefits of these services are interlinked. Microfinance initiatives are willing to lend wealth to the poor people so that it can at least help them to live, or provide them the opportunity to boost their living standards (Banerjee et al., 2015).

The providing of loans to the poor without collateral or unpredictable cash flows is generally seen by the mainstream commercial banks as a risky business. Hence, banking for the poor was largely undertaken by policy makers and contributors via non-commercial initiatives, with weak participation by the private industry, especially by local private banks (Weiss & Montgomery, 2005). Microfinance institutions can only proceed to extend their operations if they can pay all their costs and produce a net income by providing financial services to the poor. Microfinance institutions must be economically feasible and effective in the long run as survival of microfinance institutions without stable financial results is not achievable. Commercial microfinance has, however, evolved in recent years and is perceived as the face of microfinance or a modern poverty mitigation phenomenon (Kent & Dacin, 2013). This

suggests that microfinance entities progressively depend on commercial funding to fund their future expansion, through either debt or alternative investments. An in-depth knowledge of microfinance institutions which allows for the selection of their corporate structure for improving performance in microfinance is naturally becoming ever more relevant.

In order to expose the value of microfinance support and other historically unexplored topics, the connection between funding and success through social and financial perspectives, this chapter is intended to include a thorough overview of the main microfinance roles in poverty reduction.

2.2. Poverty and Poverty Reduction

2.2.1 Poverty Reduction

The notion is that suffering is a social issue. The meaning and objection of the perspective of the people or agency creating the concept offers other meanings of poverty. Thus, the term ‘poverty’ is not described in a suitable or universally accepted way, but it is frequently referred to and widely used to address efficiency strategies for raising the quality of life of people worldwide (Gerbery & Filčák, 2014).

The Development World Report also identified it as a living condition characterised by undernutrition, a lack of education and illnesses that were associated with the condition of poverty, which, under any sensible concept of life decency, would include the complete absence of food and poorly educated access to basic healthcare (Hermes et al., 2011). This meaning does not concentrate on the paucity of revenue, although revenue is a critical factor in achieving these fundamental essentials. In 1997 the United Nations Development Program offered the wider definition of human deprivation in relation to wage poverty with different sets of metrics used to measure it. This description defined concerns such as access to healthcare, schooling, fresh water, lifespan, infant mortality rates and levels of literacy. Poverty is also identified by the European Union as people or groups whose resources are minimal and below the lowest acceptable standards (Gutierrez-Nieto et al., 2007). This is amongst the most standard terms, as deprivation affects not only the income of individuals but also the complete isolation of citizens from normal living habits, practices and actions.

The notion of poverty which is generally accepted is to be starving and lacking shelter as people live on so little earnings and have no assets. It is defined as the state of: being ill without the right to see a doctor or receive medical treatment; not being able to learn because they cannot walk to class; not getting a job; and sometimes living in fear of the future and the loss of rights and recognition (Armendáriz & Szafarz, 2011). More precisely, an individual is only deemed to be impoverished if their weekly income for basic needs is less than the minimum standard. This minimum level is referred to as the “poverty line”, which varies from time to time. Each state has *lines* appropriate to its stage of development, values and social and cultural standards.

Poverty is often separated into two categories: severe poverty and poverty. Total deprivation occurs when basic human requirements, such as food, fresh water, health treatment, clothes, schooling, knowledge and shelter, are not met. On the other hand, relative poverty generally refers to incomes that are insufficient to achieve the living standard (Cantillon & Vandenbroucke, 2014). The major classes of banking and financial services have three categories which are dependent on profits (revenue) and assets: bankable, close-bankable and non-bankable. When the disadvantaged live in poverty, they are typically almost bankable and non-bankable (Arnold, 2002). Microfinance continues to concentrate on certain individuals who are similar to bankable and non-bankable, while agricultural finance appears to concentrate on banking in rural areas.

Bankable individuals are approved for money lending processes by banks as the word “bankable” clearly means they are appropriate or suitable for a bank loan. They are affluent or preferably not disadvantaged citizens because they have sufficient promises on their current wages, potential cash flows and a strong likelihood of banks receiving financing successfully. Non-bankable people are those with relatively little revenue, no real track record or assets to support a bank loan. “Non-bankable” is used in traditional demographics in conjunction with the term “absolute poverty”. They are main topics of traditional non-profit microfinance. Close to the bankable people are those whose income is higher than those who are not bankable and who have collateral but who do not have any demands on their debts as a local business because financial institutions would often prefer to see proof of payments to lend to those who are not bankable (Rogoff, 2007). This concept is often used to identify the fairly somewhat disadvantaged citizens who are the key businesses.

Reis & Moore (2005) split citizens into two main groups based on poor standards: the poor and non-poor. According to the report, the economically successful vulnerable people or citizens who are only just above poverty are the perfect candidates to seek loans from microfinance organisations to help them live above the line, a more in-depth discussion about this is set out in the next chapter. This implies that not all the poor citizens have the same lending capability and there is no successful template. The poor have so little revenue and invest more on food than the wealthy. Any raise in living costs would appear to render them poorer because the income does not rise in comparison, particularly for poor households because they have to spend more on food and so save less. Poverty is, therefore, the terminology adopted to describe the status of not having access to adequate everyday needs. Poverty was recognised as inevitable because markets were only developed just before the industrial revolution; the population expanded too quickly, rendering resources being sparse (Arvin & Barillas, 2002).

There are usually a wide variety of poverty alleviation ideas based either on enhancing the supply of basic necessities, such as increasing the basic needs of the poor, or increasing personal revenues that are needed to meet those needs. Some basic needs, such as better health and education, can also contribute to increasing revenues. The platform for the future, on the other hand, developed the Five Capitals model and said that economic power played a key role in enabling the ownership and exchange of other resources. This applied to a fund of funds referred to as deposits of loans principally given to creditors, such as companies or persons, by borrowers (shareholders) to purchase machinery or intangible assets for

commercial purposes. The borrowers are individuals, governments or government organisations that provide funding or capital for borrowing by others (Kessy & Tostensen, 2008). The lender provides the borrower with a loan, a sum of money known as the principal, and later recovers the principal and interest. There are several people in an economy who have money to be lent and people who also need to take out a loan. There are several families in any economy that are net debtors (in financial excess) and always lenders whose revenues are inadequate for their present planned expenditure and have to take out a loan from others (Spicker et al., 2007).

People usually need a loan if they do not have sufficient funds to spend. The poor frequently expend much of their lower incomes on daily food to cover their essential needs as stated above; thus, they often face malnutrition and have insufficient savings to manage any crisis or urgent cash needs. Therefore, loans can change lives in that it allows them to purchase food for daily requirements in the short term or take on small enterprises in the long term. However, these same poor people with small incomes and no collateral are unable to access the essential banking facilities (repayments) from conventional banking services and other mainstream banking providers (Donou-Adonsou & Sylwester, 2016). In addition, if they have modest sums of money, the sums to be used as leverage with the banks are too low. Therefore, they borrow money from monetary lenders who always lend with extremely high rates of interest if their family and friends do not have the money to lend them (Eversole et al., 2013).

The poor spend their money buying rice and food every day or acquiring equipment and property for long-term manufacturing. They may also create a small income corporation following a time of market cycle in terms of predictable profits and repayment liabilities. This means that a credit card can be obtained and they can pay it off by a collection of instalments. This method is referred to as saving (Hulme, 2004). From this perspective, the loan is known as a half-way stage since the vulnerable use the money borrowed for everyday needs and they conserve their savings to raise profits and properties for repayment. In addition, they will accumulate funds by investing vast sums of small savings before they reach the greater sum they desire. This technique is regarded as keeping money (Lustig & Stern, 2000). Certainly, microfinance organisations would provide the vulnerable with savings and financing, as both investing and reimbursing are related practices, despite inefficient usage of investment loans rather than spending (Crandall & Weber, 2004).

Providing the vulnerable with deposits and small micro-loans at subsidised or fair interest rates also offers them the opportunity to become self-sufficient. It is not, however, an gracious or computer that can instantly turn the impoverished into the poor. It is essentially a long-term process that overwhelmingly supports the poor financially to incorporate their abilities, understanding, knowledge and financial resources into a better and brighter future.

2.2.2 Microfinance Scheme

Microfinance was widely discussed as a new phrase of growth in the 1970s, but became increasingly popular after the UN announced the International Year of Microcredit in 2005. It

drew policy, company and researchers' interest (Henry et al., 2003). Microfinance is simply a term that refers to financial services of a micro or limited scale, such as small loans and other financial facilities, given to the vulnerable who, because they have low incomes and no collateral, are exempt from mainstream financial institutions. The poor have basic needs like many others, including basic health services, public education, hygiene and sewage, and will require financial services such as repayments, savings, insurance and financial transactions as well as the provision of basic social services to sustain their fragile lives. Financial support offers them the opportunity to take an active role in the economy by means of income, bargaining power and social influence in their societies (Leatherman & Dunford, 2010). We have the potential to become independent in the long run with the usage of these funds to build new companies and receive investment returns.

Microfinance is also referred to as the appropriate financial products and services planned specifically to meet the financial needs of the poor as well as to generate revenue. It also has an affiliation with non-financial services such as education, health and nutrition. Obviously, microfinance is a long-term mechanism that allows the vulnerable to save and raise limited profits in order to reduce the effects of economic insecurity. It can also help to fight acute deprivation triggered by crises (Bakhtiari, 2006). Microfinance is, therefore, deemed an important method to reduce poverty in rural areas where most of the world's poorest people live. It should ideally be amongst the key economic development goals for poverty reduction in most developing countries. Microfinance continues to evolve and industry leaders remain dedicated to creating a fully integrated financial service. This is the basis for building the best microfinance providers who are willing to provide the vulnerable with relevant and useful treatment depending on their benefits and drawbacks (Karmakar, 2008).

2.2.3 Micro-Credit and Microfinance

The words microfinance and microcredit are often used synonymously in the literature. However, it is applied here to the delivery of distinct and different rates of financial resources for poverty mitigation for the vulnerable. Micro-credit implies literally all forms of small loans or small sums of money to a person issued directly or indirectly by financial institutions or by non-collateral organisations. Microcredit avoided economic crashes and solved the development lending problems by encouraging better repayments, charging rates and concentrating on the underprivileged. The microfinance bundle, alluded to above, such as a larger variety of services including grants, deposits, health coverage, and other financial institutions, were targeted at the vulnerable. It covered microfinance and other financial products such as deposits, insurance, cash transfers and utilities (Hunt & Kasynathan, 2001). In recent years, microfinance and microcredit have been used primarily to describe small loans whereas microcredit is merely an element of microfinance which offers the vulnerable the ability to access traditional and secure financial services. It is well-known that the poor require a wide variety of financial resources, not just microcredit, in order to satisfy their different needs (Khavul, 2010).

The disparity among microfinance and microcredit obviously shows that microfinance organisations ought to regulate themselves to provide the poor with full financial services. In

addition, restructuring contributes to an enhanced management and ownership system which becomes the best path for microfinance organisations to commercialise or operate on a corporate basis (Tietze & Villareal, 2003). This allows microfinance organisations to expand their presence by growing the number of clients they serve through consumer loyalty and the repayment of loans thereby stabilising financial capital to establish a sustainable enterprise.

2.3. Donors of Microfinance

Microfinance companies are typically split into three categories depending on their financial features: regulated, semi-formal and unregulated providers. They are also popular for the Asian Development Bank and formal commercial banks such as credit cooperatives and governed financial institutions, many of which have appeared in research studies into microfinance. In this scheme, the administration plays a major role in offering financial assistance to the poor, mainly the provision of loans, through non-profit public-owned financial institutions (Hermes & Lensink, 2007). They were blamed for not being capable of reaching the intended minority communities due to limited public funding and a lack of private involvement (Balkenhol, 2007). Semi-formal suppliers are institutions that provide microfinance across different decentralised financing systems. This is a comparatively small system that covers about 8% of the total rural financial system (Flynn, 2007), which comprises government departments and programs, large associations and specialist microfinancing.

Casual vendors are informal borrowers, such as family members, friends and lenders. This scheme was once the main source of funding for the underprivileged. The interest rate for borrowing from family or friends is normally zero, or low, while money lenders charge five to ten times more than just the official service provider's market interest rate. The underprivileged people always have little resources until their crop is ready (Schäfer & Fukasawa, 2011). Without formal arrangements, money lenders loan money to them as short-term loans and receive repayments on a regular or weekly basis as decided upon with the borrowers. Without leverage, money changers depend on local underground to recover debts if they are not paid on time. The growth of small commercial banks, financial cooperatives and microfinancing organisations have, over the last few years, restructured rural finance systems and the vulnerable have had a better chance of accessing multiple sources of funds (Hudon & Sandberg, 2013).

The poor have no funds to access loans from nearby financial institutions. Microfinance services specifically and implicitly target the vulnerable, being the non-bankable or near to bankable people, and is seen as the key factor in determining precisely whether it is microfinance companies or other financial suppliers or institutions. In the literature, microfinance providers are identified by the formal financial take detailed in rural areas, such as sustainable livelihood suppliers. Microfinance and rural financing have some variations as rural finance applies to rural trading activities with microfinancing being a component of rural funding.

Martinelli & Mersland (2010) expanded typical definitions to four general groups, including formal financial entities, NGOs, member organisations and unregulated finance suppliers, by categorising microfinance suppliers. This paper splits the semi-formal vendors into NGOs and membered organisations to highlight the essential positions of microfinance NGOs (Hiatt & Woodworth, 2006). Microfinance providers are split into two networks dependent on funding sources: internal (local) and foreign (international). This is the context to identifying the right vendors and to collaborate internally and externally. External agencies with insufficient funding for microfinance also have a vital role to play but external resources play a significant role in increasing poverty mitigation by supplying local communities with foreign funds (Churchill & Frankiewicz, 2006). Microfinance suppliers can be split into three customer- classified groups. The consumer's rise from recipient to user reflects the improvement in how MFIs satisfy the requirements of the disadvantaged.

Beneficiary implies that perhaps the poor receive microfinance along with, amongst other advantages, economic assistance, hygiene and sewage. These programs give the poor an awareness of the risks and some payment and protection skills (Mersland & Strøm, 2010). Customers indicate that the impoverished are fully aware, particularly financially, of what they need but do not have access to a standard financial system capable of meeting their needs. They are represented by MFIs who are specialised in providing small financial and technological services for the poor (Montgomery & Weiss, 2011). The poor appear to have greater awareness and different priorities under the term 'clients', they may be a business who is involved in renting equipment or insurance insuring their companies; they are seen as customers and are easy to approach by advertising banks and finance companies.

2.3.1 Microfinance Institutions

Microfinance institutions are generally described as the various kinds of projects which provide microfinance services, from small, non-profit organisations to large-scale businesses, such as microfinance banks, credit unions, finance companies and NGOs. This concept encompasses a broad variety of institutions focused on their legal framework, function and technique for lending. Microfinance institutions, regional banks and credit unions have competitive market operating systems within them. In recent decades, the number of microfinance entities has grown rapidly and, centred around the sponsored initiatives of government and private organisations, was the establishment of microfinance institutions (Ahmed, 2002). They supported farmers with subsidised loans to increase production and profits in rural areas. Women in small industries were also given microcredit to allow the vulnerable to acquire assets and income for output (Ledgerwood & White, 2006).

Microfinance institutions prove that the vulnerable can be viewed as bankable individuals through a new approach to conventional banks such as community loans. They have offered structured entities some valuable lessons in relation to limited banking services. Many of the latest participants, such as business banks, have broad established branch networks, wide delivery channels and the opportunity to spend significantly in infrastructure, taking the best banking services closer to the vulnerable (Hartarska & Nadolnyak, 2007).

2.3.2 Development of Microfinance Institutions

Over the years, microfinance has expanded with more and more kinds of borrowers participating, with the production and sponsorship of new forms of goods and services. Internationally, there is a growing awareness that benefit projects and the involvement of the private industry can provide further incentives to meet the social goals of equitable exposure to a variety of demands (Wolfensohn, 2000). Therefore, business microfinance is considered to be the next microfinance phase. In tandem with conventional microfinance, it would be the perfect option because the poor need capital to purchase everyday food and supplies in order to live and to save in the long term to become ego-sufficient (Morduch, 2000). The success of microfinance would be focused on the efficient output of microfinance organisations, expanded private-sector involvement and financial market growth. In addition to funding foreign organisations, potential sources of funds would primarily be domestic savings and the task of financial agencies having critically essential deposits, transforming those savings into successful loans (Lopatta et al., 2017).

2.4. Influences of Microfinance

Microfinance has proved to be a viable, productive and effective method for the rising level of disadvantaged people and the deprivation in meeting the Millennium Objectives. Indeed, it has been thoroughly studied over the past fifteen years and the subsequent studies indicate that MFIs need to shift from highly supported activities to marketing in order to be successful and sustainable (Warnecke, 2014). Since donors' financing is inadequate to satisfy the continual need for new and current clients for well-designed financial goods, exposure to commercial funds continues to improve their output by microfinance institutions. This demonstrates explicitly that MFIs should maintain longevity in order to pursue a tailored strategy. However, some critics claim that financial security and social purpose are mutually exclusive. This element would also include a thorough overview of some of the key problems posed by microfinance in trying to shed light on the significance of financial security for microfinance institutions (Boateng & Agyei, 2013). It is proposed that microfinance funding plays a significant role in rendering microfinance organisations economically competitive and worthy of delivering long-term financial services to the vulnerable (Kanunga, 2012).

2.4.1 Microfinance and Poverty Reduction

In the last few years there have been numerous research studies and findings on the effect of microfinance in reducing poverty with these surveys exploring how microfinance actually helps the poor. The majority of studies have proven the positive effects on the rise or decrease of the wages of the disadvantaged. Any research on wellness, diet and employment have been overwhelmingly convincing and optimistic (Roy, 2010).

It is generally accepted that deprivation is a social issue and highly intertwined, covering all aspects of culture and values. Consequently, poverty reduction is a long-term process involving multiple financial and non-financial services for the numerous poor families. Missing

funds and reduced initial wages are essential measures and signs of deprivation (Muhammad, 2010). This is why the borrowing of small sums by the disadvantaged, particularly the poorest, has a potentially beneficial influence on poverty alleviation, as it will help them sustain malnutrition and give them an incentive to undertake small enterprises and boost their living conditions for potential cash flows. Clearly, in social terms, providing microfinancing to the people benefits them and has a significant impact on the reduction of poverty (Bateman, 2011).

Many longitudinal experiments have been performed in various countries to analyse the impact of microfinance using the double-difference method and panel results using the defined effect model. The results show that the borrower's personal income is different in different regions even without microfinance schemes. Rankin (2002) studied the correlation around exposure to finance and poor health and the results indicated that microfinance is likely to lower weaknesses and being able to connect directly to finance options which tends to assist poor people with smooth consumption in the face of health declines. Real spending, or a decrease in the deprivation of the vulnerable, has had major beneficial consequences. Jose & Chacko (2017) suggested that it was curious that scholars were always questioning whether or not microfinancing would alleviate deprivation.

Nothing has been proven, given the growth and acceptance of microfinance, that microfinance has a significant effect on reducing poverty. Estapé-Dubreuil & Torreguitart- Mirada, (2013) analysed the microfinance impacts and their findings highlighted that the pure quantifiable evidence of the impact of microfinance remains sparse and incomplete. It is generally recognised that there is no well-known research that can show significant microfinance impacts. Given the latest background of poor economies, where microfinancing may leave certain poor citizens worse off, such as credit cards and mortgages, the effect of microfinance remains unlikely.

According to Bateman & Chang (2012), the impact of microfinance on the consumer was unimportant and pessimistic and it had no effect on new entrepreneurship development or the education and empowerment of women. Ghosh (2012) indicated that no effect had also been observed by a number of major microfinance programs. Olu (2009) took a different approach and recorded very little concrete evidence that showed the special role of poverty reduction microfinance in a measurable way.

Therefore, the majority of evidence tends to suggest that in some cases microfinance has a favourable and important effect on the vulnerable. Many reports have taken various approaches and concluded that it is exceedingly difficult to distinguish and quantify the impacts of microfinance on reducing poverty because poverty is a significant social challenge, and it penetrates every aspect of culture and community (Balkenhol, 2007). Furthermore, as the gains obtained from these schemes are interrelated, there are significant theoretical connections amongst microfinance and the delivery of certain non-financial initiatives. In addition, these findings indicated that microfinance could not transform the vulnerable into non-poor citizens overnight (Hermes et al., 2018). The argument would be that microfinance is a long-term mechanism that aims to financially help vulnerable citizens in order to leverage

their expertise, education, resources and financing to free them from hardship and transform their lives towards a stronger, happier future (Kapoor & Sinha, 2013).

2.4.2. The Benefits of Microfinance

Some debates have taken place about the impoverished or the poorest living in poverty who see advantages from microfinance. During this time, microfinance institutions try to utilise commercial funds to enhance their productivity and accomplish targeted outcomes as donor funding is not sufficient to meet the emphasis for well-constructed financial instruments from potential and existing clients. There has, therefore, been some discussion on the opportunities available to support the poorest of the poor (Janda et al., 2014). Most microfinance institutions typically serve the elderly, who are not the worst category, that are either almost or just above the poverty threshold. It is often claimed that microfinance has made a positive difference to the welfare of the poor overall, but it has not helped the wealthiest (Van Rooyen et al., 2012).

Shui-tu & Yun (2007) asserted that the impoverished are not marketable and thus cannot access financial services from structured financial institutions, such as commercial banks, because, as already noted, they have no collateral. The experience of the Grameen Bank showed that financially sustainable microfinance can support poor people in achieving better benefits by empowering them to save how much they can, borrow just what they can afford and take responsibility for the planning and reimbursement of microfinance institutions (Ngo & Wahhaj (2012). Therefore, economical approaches for the vulnerable make a slight improvement for the extremely poor.

Microfinance for the needy, such as the youngest, can be successful yet well-designed banking systems will not have a significant effect on the disadvantaged because they do not directly touch them. The poorest are missed or excluded because they do not think the systems are for them (Ferguson, 2003). Mavrenko (2011) showed that about half of Bangladesh's agricultural population are the richest. Microfinance projects have entered only half of the population in Bangladesh with nearly half of the disadvantaged not investing in non-financial social programs. The weakest continue to be exempt from microfinance, whether that is because they are unwilling to be responsible for daily continuous returns or because the husbands cannot encourage their wives to utilise it.

Khandelwal (2007) argued that a market plan still allows a large amount of failures and the thought that income will offset losses is irrational. They believe that institutions of microfinance will offer the right business facilities to both the right consumers in order to prevent defaults with pressures that trigger MFIs to render so many loans of poor quality by not lending to the right lenders. Over lending and simultaneous borrowing will render a poor person struggling to repay their loans, as in the crisis of microfinance. Microfinance organisations thus continue to consider it challenging to refinance themselves or collect funds for financing operations. Investors continue to worry about the efficiency of their lending to microfinance institutions.

2.4.3. Microfinance and Sustainable Development

Ultimately, microfinance provides poor possibilities for resolving poverty by dealing with small businesses and becoming self-sufficient. Economic microfinance usually does not touch the vulnerable citizens who are actively funded through non-profit services by the state and sponsors (Imai et al., 2012). Microfinance relies strongly on a society where people work together, connect with other people and establish partnerships with community, whether it focuses primarily on the weakest or not. The mix of microfinancing between corporate and non-profit initiatives, therefore, is suitable for economic growth rather than concentrating on a single proportion of the population, such as the vulnerable or the relatively disadvantaged. Microfinance obviously has two primary roles: a social purpose and financial sustainability. Whilst MFIs should boost financial activity in order to pursue a targeted approach, some critics claim that there is a connection between financial viability and social purpose (Taylor, 2011).

The social quest refers to the growth aim of governmental and NGO microfinance teams. This goal can be achieved through the amount of target lenders from subsidised or non-profit organisations based on utilising microcredit, which is mostly offered to the weakest, especially at subsidised levels. There are still several concerns as to how subsidising interest rates was warranted. This idea is always noted in the initial stages of microfinance development (Korth et al., 2020). The social function literature is concise and standard with the conceptual and theoretical research on the effect of microfinance being the focus of the peer reviewed papers. It is also believed that the supported microfinance schemes will not have adequate public financing and microfinance organisations cannot continue to be sustainable.

Financial conservation stresses the value of economic stability. It relates to the capability to cover all administration expenses, credit losses, financing costs and operating income. It has been stressed repeatedly that microfinance institutions must be economically viable and sustainable in the long term as without good financial performance the viability of microfinance institutions is inaccessible. Furthermore, some studies have found that financial sustainability is strongly linked to achieving the cultural goals of microfinance institutions. The poor tend to consume from the financially viable microfinance institutions and it appears that microfinance enterprises and the poor can make profits. For these reasons, microfinance institutions are ideally focused on sustainable development by reaching the economically productive poor with small potential profit firms rather than concentrating on the number of borrowers (Schaffner, 2013). Clearly, in certain cases, the social role seems to drive microfinance organisations to over-lend by not providing the right citizens with microfinance.

There are still many microfinance institutions that are dependent on government non-profit programs or donation subsidies because microfinance is an expensive payment and information-based business. The importance of sustainability, however, led to a major controversy between financial sustainability and social purpose. Both methods accept that, although in separate respects, the vulnerable will be represented. Ideally, sustainable

development is the concept for the microfinance future (Afrane, 2002). The social advocates contend that the poorest people will not be able to meet the higher interest rates and that financial security in microfinance undermines the goal of servicing large groups. The scientific research does not show that the disadvantaged cannot manage higher interest rates, nor does the financial health of the company and the degree of poorness of clients have a significant association. Even so, the financial strategy focuses mainly on individuals who are close-banking than on non-banking persons. Apparently, the contrast of both strategies is often understood by scientists who claim that microfinance schemes operate both for benefit and non-profit (Lønborg & Rasmussen, 2014).

Rising in interest rates contribute to higher profits, however, this may not need to be the case as higher prices may contribute to lower income for information asymmetry and adverse moral risks. A more precise assessment should be appropriate for the expense and gain of the subsidies to be measured. Unfortunately, this issue concerns only a few research projects and they indicate that the social gains exceed the loss.

Some research has concentrated on financial sustainability and the influence of sustainable development on activism, in particular the number of lenders and the socio-economic stage. Bhatt & Tang (2001) concentrated on Asia and Latin America, whereas Bateman & Chang (2012) concentrated on Africa, supplying blended evidence of the depth of their coverage. The current studies do not clarify discrepancies systematically or directly investigate whether there is a connection between the depths of outreach and the fight for economic sustainability. De & Ratan's (2009) findings brought a dimension to microfinance banks with the literature based on a comprehensive analysis of more than 100 microfinancing institutions. The research revealed an objective correlation between extreme expansion and competitiveness by analysing how further productivity is correlated with a lower extent of growth because, if this occurs, in order to reach a higher financial efficiency, you need the appropriate ratio in the total poor to wealthy citizens. This study also looked at whether an increase in credit interest rates impacted the lending activities because of adverse selection and moral risks. According to Barman et al. (2009), there are ample scientific indications that the vulnerable have adequate profits from their firms to afford the interest cost at current prices. These findings are ideally a context for commercial microfinance development by increasing private sector participation.

In brief, the literature indicates that for microfinance organisations, no particular financial stabilisation or outreach (social mission) is better or more relevant. Instead, it is necessary to have the right mix because they are typically similar and this mix essentially means that microfinance organisations will generate revenues that are reinvested in the sector and hence run longer. Microfinance's critical goal is not to achieve profit on equity but to help the vulnerable relieve suffering through bankruptcy.

2.4.4. Lending Approaches

Microfinance is essentially given by collective or individual loans to the needy. Many MFIs are historically focused on community loans to render the weak bankable by the knowledge

asymmetry of credit operations after becoming non-bankable or close-bankable. On the other hand, some MFIs favour individual loans as there is more experience and the management of the loans with the vulnerable as individuals is simpler. This seems to indicate that MFIs prefer to allow community lending in the early stages of growth rather than individual lending. The correct financing approaches, therefore, contribute to better results and each case depends on the particular circumstances of a growing nation and the particular business.

2.4.4.1 Providing Loans to Groups

It is doubtful that the poor, who have no currency, no leverage and no guaranteed income, will have exposure to sources of financing. A variety of new, relatively effective MFIs have sought to boost small borrowers' balance sheets by lending to associations and not individuals (Awaworyi, 2014). The poor are grouped into small groups and each member assumes a shared duty for the lender. Several empirical research studies have shown that self-selected communities perform better than identified microfinance institutions, as underinvestment issues can be resolved and repayment levels increased, for example village banking is known as a community loan. There is cross-subscription between several schemes implying that the projects do not comprise of a specific creditor but are distinct.

Johnson (1998) offered a fresh perspective into when and how community lending operates to increase return levels. Borrowers' groups are formed to ensure the redemption of loans when representatives of the community have shared liability. Non-repayment ensures that this liability must be compensated by all creditors or potential access to loans will be refused. This is why community loans have the opportunity to track and control loan repayment participants. In addition, lenders are often near and connected to each other (considered social capital) and they are also well educated about the actions of each other.

Until now, there have also been some observational reports of knowledge asymmetries being minimised, at least in part because of the difficulty of collecting accurate statistics on the operation of such systems and their behaviour. The effect of community lending on repayment levels by the use of multiple forms of proxy for monitoring, tracking and compliance is in many of the current studies.

2.4.4.2 Providing Loans to Individuals

Personal loans reflect a conventional and growing approach under which individuals borrow directly on the grounds of their own business credit value, such as their credibility with peers and community and revenue streams. Individual lending in microfinance is correlated with higher loans per person than community lending. The MFIs offer loans to the poor on the basis of collateral or specific guarantors that are identified to lenders as acquaintances or relatives. The guarantors are designed to compensate the investor in the event that the creditor cannot make the payments. According to Nair (2001), microfinance institutions tend to provide private loans rather than community loans, as refinancing costs are high and there is rivalry amongst microfinance institutions with weaknesses where the group's loan size is

smaller. Screening and supervision by mutual lending colleagues, however, eliminates social harm and adverse collection issues. Individual lending is projected to expand if microfinance entities start to obtain greater exposure to the capital markets.

2.4.4.3. Interest Rates

Amongst the most critical problems of microfinancing is the interest rates on the loans given to the vulnerable. A few years earlier, because microfinance agencies and foreign organisations concentrated on allowing those to apply for loans who were from poor households through subsidised schemes, interest rates were lower than cost recovery thresholds. The weak were expected to be known as low credit risk people who could not spend capital in such a manner that they would reimburse the loans and interest.

Obviously, if they make profits or have good cash flows from their savings, they can always refund the credited capital. Being in debt is not a good thing because the poor have to repay borrowed money and cannot afford to lose access to it and if there are financial risks, they would be in far deeper danger (Pronyk et al., 2005). Investment funding is not necessarily a terrible thing as investors do not often have enough money to invest in new investment plans or even lending for immediate finance purposes because they are helpful to the needy so they will pay back the loans and, regardless as to the probability being small or high, there is still a possibility of failure. If the poor have little creative ideas or experience to establish their own company it may be a risky decision to use borrowed capital for investment. Investment also requires time to develop itself and make a return slowly. The weak cannot, therefore, afford to gain instant income and must repay their loan and interest on time. In fact, the cost of return from the businesses will be greater than that of the interest rate on the debts to gain the income.

Small loans for the poor are usually an expensive endeavour because of the high prices of the purchases. Microfinance organisations may need significant support to offer loans and lending rates in order to stay viable. The subsidised interest-rate microfinance scheme is typically run or funded by the municipal government and poverty mitigation donors. In fact, the subsidised interest rates support only a limited percentage of the poor for a short time. These projects have lower interest levels than traditional microfinance because the vulnerable realise they can borrow as long as there are government proceeds to fund such systems (Maru & Chemjor, 2013). There is also little opportunity for microfinance organisations to become competitive and demonstrate structural dependence due to restricted development and a lack consistency in pushing the vulnerable into reimbursement. The vulnerable appear to accept such loans as one-off contributions that will be refunded. Nevertheless, the poor are eager for decent infrastructure and continuous and efficient access to financing to pay high interest rates (Sanyal, 2009). Obviously, the subsidised prices are able to efficiently negate the rivalry which is crucial for microfinance institutions' growth and performance.

While many of the poor can earn returns on their savings, clearly not all of them can use the borrowed capital in such a profitable way and cannot thus manage commercial loans (Kumar,

2012). In order to eliminate the disadvantages for participants, many microfinance organisations aim to mix their sources of funding, particularly investment funds, with low donor costs, to minimise their interest rates. It is evident that a market interest rate is feasible and microfinance may be a competitive business by growing private sector involvement (Wanambisi & Bwisa, 2013).

2.5. Reduce Gender Inequality

Many researchers who have studied the alleviation of the poor addressed prosperity as a significant aspect in business loss credibility. It refers in general to the change in the ability of the person to make strategic life choices. The poor are not motivated because they have little work and they choose to embrace employment or establish smaller firms to live. This condition of life may also be related to deprivation (Zhang & Posso, 2017). When citizens are powerless, they sometimes find themselves in misery. The empowerment, however, is to increase poor people's abilities and skills in bargaining, shaping, managing and keeping responsible structures that influence their lives. Poor citizens require a range of skills and resources to boost wellbeing, health and self-confidence. The advancement of females has become an important subject of the debate in terms of democracy and economy and is termed gender advancement.

Motivating people involves fighting for equality due to their various significant positions in their households, societies or cultures. Effective schooling allows most people to achieve greater influence over their everyday lives and raise their quality of living. Women invest in birth control which leads to high population increases in developing countries (Zulfiqar, 2017). This also aimed to improve economic growth on the basis of their commitment to the family's existence. The empowerment of women is also one of the significant microfinance priorities.

In general, microfinance has reached vulnerable people by offering incentives for exposure to financial resources. Many research studies have demonstrated how exposure to financial resources has enhanced the women's position in the community and society. Females are becoming more confident and assertive, they have become more prominent and are best able to secure the public sphere in areas where female autonomy is strictly regulated (Boehe & Cruz, 2013). Women have strengths and play a greater role in decision-making with decreasing levels of poverty against women in some welfare programs. The fundamental theory is that microfinance helps women by offering loans and resources to gain independent identity and contribute financially to their families and communities.

Financial lending to women around the developing world allows them to play an important role in poorer families. Women are to blame for the house-keeping, land upkeep, children and are especially necessary for everyday consumption and the family's current accounts, while men usually operate to raise cash (Basargekar, 2009). Many practitioners claim that a deliberate emphasis on the empowerment of women as a core concept of microfinance will lead them to further practices which could have a lasting effect on the efficacy of the delivery of financial services to the vulnerable. There are three primary reasons not to dwell on

women deliberately. First, the correct microfinance partner in the poor family should be given funds because microfinance is not ideal for everybody (Simanowitz, 2007). Furthermore, loans to women are not only applicable to individuals but also to communities or families. If a woman decides to take a loan, microfinance institutions will still say that she will speak to her husband about it. Women often sacrifice their money on their family and for a better future. Finally, microfinance organisations prefer to offer micro-financing to families that engage in existing economic development or business plans, rather than being deliberately based on ethnicity (Mengoli et al., 2017).

2.6. Criticisms of microfinance

There is a lot of scepticisms of the uses of microfinance schemes. As such, scholars have also challenged whether microfinance would able to mitigate poverty, facilitate women empowerment as well as the ethical crisis of microfinance initiatives.

2.6.1. Criticisms on the role of microfinance in poverty alleviation

In order to argue that microfinance is a loss as it is not economically viable, the essence of the microfinance sector must be considered. While several microfinance programs rely on benefit, the overwhelming majority of them have been produced for social services, including poverty reduction and empowerment for the disadvantaged people. With this in mind, it should be remembered that absolutely no service targeted at the vulnerable is financially via Low-income housing schemes, hospitals for the disabled, public colleges, health and technical education, agriculture services, and indeed any service aimed at enhancing the lives of the poor relies on funding from either the government or other donors (Bateman, 2010). Thus, the benefits of microfinance needs to be appreciated. In addition, however, findings from current studies indicated that microfinance could not transform the vulnerable into non- poor citizens overnight (Hermes et al., 2018). The argument would be that microfinance is a long-term mechanism that aims to financially help vulnerable citizens in order to leverage their expertise, education, resources and financing to free them from hardship and transform their lives towards a stronger, happier future (Kapoor & Sinha, 2013).

It's too early to consider microfinance as a successful initiative. Microfinance is a startup incubator whose success has quickly set it in motion, maybe too quickly (Bateman, 2011). Since microfinance is a very recent idea, there are still few managers trained to operate a microfinance service and there is still a lot to be learnt on how to attain sustainable development. In a couple more years, when leaders are able to obtain more expertise and preparation, many MFIs should be able to support themselves financially (Bateman & Chang 2012). There is a great deal of proof that self-sufficiency is achievable, but it is still uncommon yet.

The other criticism against the use of microfinance is that it is unable to reach all poor people. It is said that microfinance cannot reach young women, the disabled, the poor, the physically or mentally disadvantaged. Microfinance projects are often responsible for removing remote

areas lacking resources or connections to markets, areas with a scattered community or populations that rely on a single economic operation (Bateman, 2012). The most pitiful indictment against microfinance is that it needs the disadvantaged to be entrepreneurial. It is painfully evident, also in our own world, that most citizens are not entrepreneurial. It would be unrealistic to believe that the weak are different. Microfinance supporters prefer to encourage the notion that all disadvantaged citizens are dynamic, talented businessmen and women-only waiting for an opportunity to shine if they just have access to credit (Bateman et al., 2018). Critics contend that microfinance is exclusive and that most disadvantaged people are badly trained, oppressed by culture, and unlikely to have the entrepreneurial drive required to start up a company. Critics emphasize the need for a more universal solution to poverty alleviation (Brickell et al., 2020).

2.6.2. Criticisms on the role of women empowerment

The other critique of microfinance is that it able to harm or reduce the development of women. Women have been removed from civic or income-generating practices for much of their history; only lately have they began to talk about gender equity and the right to fair economic conditions for men (Bateman, 2019). Some men fear that the liberation of women is a direct challenge to conventional patriarchal dominance. In certain societies, if a man's wife functions, and particularly if it produces more revenue than it does, it degrades a man's sense of masculinity (Bateman, 2014). This can lead to a power battle as a man tries to reclaim authority of the home, which in certain situations escalates domestic abuse against women.

There is a second reason for why microfinance may be detrimental to women. Microfinance is hailed as a way of fostering women's economic prospects and empowerment; moreover, when women take a microcredit loan to start a company, it is mostly men who regulate how the loan has been used (Bateman, 2011). In most Third World countries, men have better earnings practices, connections to larger economies, and a higher social standing than women. Some claim that as men regulate women's loans, they further enforce male control over women's lives (Nega & Schneider, 2014). Another difficulty that women encounter with microfinance is that they have a dual jobs of operating a company and taking care of children. Typically, women have taken care of the kids and household work while men work for family income. More and more women are joining the public workforce, but they are also required to take responsibility for all household duties (Bateman et al., 2019). This imposes a massive double pressure on women.

While microfinance may lead to a higher workload for women, most women find that the advantages of participating in micro-credit programs greatly outweigh the costs. Women feel motivated by involvement in the job force, a role in economic decision, access to education opportunities, and a sense of freedom and greater autonomy over their lives. For others, the additional workload is a reasonable sacrifice to compensate for (Rossel et al., 2015). However, for those who feel frustrated, it would be challenging to overcome the problem of the double responsibility of employment and household duties before husband learn to share house duties with their wives. In the meantime, women should set up their own day-care services and help each other (Bateman, 2020).

2.6.3. Criticisms on the ethical crisis of microfinance

The first explanation why microfinance services have not reached the "true" poor people is attributed to inequality on the part of loan officers. As in other lending programs, the bigger the loan, the better the benefit to be gained by the lenders. As a result, loan officers sometimes discriminate against very poor borrowers and instead support the poor people who can handle loans as well as offer higher interest. The second explanation why microfinance cannot enter the lowest of the disadvantaged people is the pariah position of the extremely poor (Welsh, 2019). Much as there are wide divisions between the wealthy and the disadvantaged in rich nations, poorer societies which have social segregation between the poor and the needy. The disadvantaged, often referred to as the extremely poor or the lowest of the poor, can be separated from the majority of society (Chhorn, 2020). Perhaps it is injustice against the "advantaged" people that pushes the destitute further from community and, as a consequence, away from microfinance services, but it is also the destitute that distinguishes themselves. Quite disadvantaged citizens, who neglect even essential needs, refuse interaction with the rest of society out of guilt. They may have lice or parasites, they may lack proper clothes, or they may just feel too ashamed to reveal their severe poverty in public (Nair & Njolomole, 2020). Simply stated, microfinance is not necessarily an attractive solution for the very disadvantaged. A impoverished family who works every day to thrive will not have the energy to build up an innovative, business company (Omomowo, 2020). The lowest of the poor can hardly fulfil essential needs far less operate the company as a whole and lack the requisite qualifications, managerial skills and social networks. The trouble is that if preparation had to be provided by microfinance services, the institution's potential to become financially solvent would be crippled (Correa & Girón, 2019).

The omission of the poorest from microfinance is not an implication that the poorest cannot benefit from microfinance services, but rather an indication of the inability of microfinance initiatives to design programmes to address the needs of vulnerable households (Green, 2019). Microfinance appeared to eliminate certain programs that could not be used by one-size-fits-all services offered. Services that have been established appear to address the desires of a specific sector of the client market and have contributed to the exclusion of others that are unwilling to access or compensate for such services. The usage of the weekly repayment plan, a trademark of the microfinance sector, has been highly criticized for this. It is argued that the wage periods of the vulnerable range from company to business. Some disadvantaged households receive money every week, others on a biweekly basis, and others monthly. Demanding that all clients conform to a strict weekly payment schedule renders microfinance an unattractive choice for many poor (Tijani et al., 2020). Microfinance that are unyielding and do not deliver a variety of services risk losing consumers and performance.

Microfinance should be seen as an efficient way of alleviating suffering for the poorest people. The approach for delivering micro-financial resources to the very vulnerable is to design projects that address the expectations of poor people (Bernards, 2019). Factors that allow development organizations to reach out to the vulnerable are creating information

exchange with the very young, building on the expectations of the poor rather than on their challenges, understanding the importance of cultural intervention and educating the poor. Microfinance services need to be agile in tailoring their systems to suit the specific desires of the community. Services that are more suited to clients' needs contribute to better success and sustainability of clients, which, in turn, would lead to higher performance and sustainability of the microfinance services (Morshed et al., 2020). The first step in reaching out to the poorer people is to provide services that help disadvantaged families fulfill their essential needs, such as food, housing and clothes. Microfinance programs can also include general schooling and business management skills for disadvantaged households. Training and training in financial accountability would contribute to greater sovereignty and prosperity for the vulnerable (Buera et al., 2021). When the poorest families are secure that their fundamental health, housing and nutrition requirements have been fulfilled and that they obtain adequate schooling and training, they able to take a loan.

2.7. Different Perspectives in Microfinancing

The size of the activities in business microfinancing relates to the amount of financial goods and services offered by MFIs to the poor. Monetary goods and services should certainly be tailored to meet the needs of the poor, meaning the best financial technologies are provided to the best individuals. Consequently, MFIs may gain income at a real interest rate or at a fair cost at which MFIs will pay their operating expenses and stay sustainable. Without adequate investment money, poor asset yields and a poor borrowing pace, businesses in this field of income cannot usually survive. Return on equity continues to enable shareholders to invest in microfinance, thereby enabling it to continue longer to satisfy the growing demand of new and current customers (Blanco et al., 2013). This section is intended to offer a detailed analysis of the effects of the microfinance scale of operations from the point of view of the borrower and the investor, to explain the relation between financing, scope and economic efficiency.

2.7.1 Microfinance Participants' Perspectives

It is broadly acknowledged that the disadvantaged have different financial requirements, which can be divided into three major goals, as mentioned earlier: spending on family needs, small enterprises and emergencies. The disadvantaged tend to borrow funds to secure financing because they do not have adequate money with very comparatively low incomes. The value of the loan depends on what the loaned money is going to be used for (Dillard et al., 2010). It is advised that microfinance institutions have adequate lenders with creative minds and expertise to create good organisational ideas. There are potential moral hazards because the disadvantaged may want larger loans than they are offered or can afford. Large loans will quickly lead to over-indebtedness by some lenders who do not use the borrowed money wisely in small companies and fail to repay the lending to the creditors. In addition, borrowers are expected to leverage inappropriately from other lenders when their financial demands are recognised and fulfilled, which can contribute to over-indebtedness. Therefore, MFIs need a deep knowledge of the financial requirements of the poor in order to provide the necessary goods to meet their expectations (Mersland et al., 2013).

The poor often keep borrowing from a range of ethnic and informal lenders for different reasons, resulting in multiple loans, creating a large challenge in trying to monitor loans from a number of sources. This drives the weak into substantial debt which is a risk if they cannot repay their loans. If microfinance institutions have sufficient goods to satisfy their financial needs, they will not always be able to resist borrowing elsewhere (Augustine, 2012). It is clear, therefore, that financial awareness and the implications of undue debt must be clarified and regularly improved.

Over lending and frequent leveraging are the early key indicators of unsustainable debt, under which disadvantaged citizens are unwilling to pay back their debts. The open market and the heavy rivalry between microfinance institutions and other financial companies are likely to trigger this. Credit offices are introduced as a helpful tool in conjunction to monitoring lenders from other organisations that exchange credit details with the offices. However, credit offices give just a limited response since the degree of indebtedness cannot be calculated and the weak are over-indebted. This implies that MFIs would reduce the amount offered to the poor to avoid unsustainable debt.

Excessive indebtedness applied generally to the failure to pay off all obligations fully and in good time. The poor are deemed to be over-indebted under this description if they have inadequate revenues to fund all the expenditures for the time specified in the loan agreements. This description was claimed to be only the one fixed period and required a fluid perspective. On the other hand, the complex multi-period concept noted that over-indebtedness existed even when net cash flows for the weak became consistently negative, such as being over-indebted over multiple periods.

The first documented microfinance recession in Bolivia in 2000 was as a result of numerous consumer loans. Chamlee-Wright (2005) also argued that the fast expansion of microfinance institutions led to the crisis in Morocco and Pakistan in conjunction with mortgage credit and lending policies. The situation in Zambia depicts explanations for the lowering of mortgage broker requirements (Robinson, 2001).

Based on cross-country analyses and microfinance crises, Dillard et al. (2010) recently concluded that unsustainable indebtedness typically emerged for various reasons, such as multiple borrowing, the development goals of microfinance institutions, unsustainable structures and controls of microfinance institutions, the deterioration of lending disciplines of microfinance institutions and inadequate policies. Moreover, the global financial crisis of protest and non-repayment protests with political motivation aggravated the situation but was not the root cause of crises in Nicaragua, Pakistan, Brussels and Bosnia. It appears that numerous loans and the low quality of the loans given to the vulnerable by the rapid development of institutions of microfinancing were the major causes of the notable micro-finance crises (Robinson, 2001).

A fragmented sector was responsible for the recent microfinance crisis in the South Indian state of Andhra Pradesh, reflected in the competitiveness amongst microfinance institutions and the emergence of multiple borrowing. In order to achieve their significant growth goals, the vulnerable who lent themselves to other financial institutions received loans. While several microfinance organisations have failed and continue to experience confusion, the main people affected are the lenders. There is a real risk that lenders, notably in Andhra Pradesh, may face difficulties in securing loans in the coming years. The situation of Andhra Pradesh also indicates that not only there but globally the crisis has affected microfinance.

The weaker people obtain cheap loans because they do not use borrowing capital wisely but still seek to reimburse the borrowers with loans and interest. Over-indebtedness, not just for the vulnerable but also the microfinance organisations, is particularly risky and may create multiple social issues. Usually, there are some potential over-debt options. As said by Radhakrishnan (2015), two major viewpoints are focused on microfinancing in this region. The poor appear to take bigger loans or borrow from multiple lenders for their financial needs and eventually become over-indebted and unwilling to repay the money borrowed. To overcome this issue, the weak must intend to be funded and be willing to pay back their loans. This seems to mean that microfinance organisations will be taking a gamble to give the vulnerable the opportunities to overcome their financial difficulties. Microfinance institutions, as well as other financial providers, are claimed to accept the high risk by giving more credit to the vulnerable as a consequence of rivalry amongst microfinance institutions and other providers. Therefore, the vulnerability of microfinance collateral is deemed the world's greatest concern for microfinance organisations. According to Hulme (2000), this has evolved across the board from the micro-borrower to the microfinance institution, as well as the borrowers of microfinance institutions. The link has been split more and more at various stages.

2.7.2 Microfinance Providers' Perspectives

Commercial banks may impact the poor directly or indirectly by downscaling and upscaling. The term "downscale" is used to decrease size or distance. Downscaling in microfinance applies to the size of the products and the services funded "directly" by commercial banks for the needy. It means reducing its scale into business niches: the disadvantaged and microfinance organisations.

Downscaling primarily reflects the participation of the local exchange banks in marketing on the premise that microfinance is an application framework that is successful to combat poverty but cannot target the lowest of the impoverished and be used in areas of severe poverty. The convergence between consumers of microfinance institutions and local business banks is therefore probable. Downscaling is the way to commercialise local commercial banks' microfinancing and turn NGOs into commercial investment through microfinance institutions.

The words "upscale" or "scale-up" results in a drop from high to low volumes. In financial services, this problem concerns the rise in small to medium-sized financial services for the

poor. Typically, there is a large gap between small and medium-sized companies and there really is two different aspects, thus different financial products and services can be used. “Extension” involves targeting different groups of customers who obviously have different kinds of competition for financial services, workers who recognise small-scale loans as well as those familiar with large-scale loans vary in expertise (Arvelo et al., 2008). Upscaling is used to comment about the bottom-up method in which local financial institutions indirectly fund the vulnerable by supplying financial services to microfinance organisations in higher volumes. Microfinance organisations assign credit to persons or associations after coping with higher-level credits due to the absence of accurate knowledge, promises and the complexities of contract feedback.

The topic under consideration is whether it is easier to improve or downgrade to enable the private industry to contribute and raise the poverty reduction pace. Microfinancing for the poor is given explicitly by community or individual loans or indirectly by intermediary organisations through structured financial institutions. Microfinance organisations are, by intermediary institutions, deemed the strongest choice to introduce microfinancing by working with banks in order to discourage a lack of credible knowledge and a shortage of collateral. So, upscaling and downscaling was collectively used as an approach to boost microfinance on the basis of the particular requirements of growing nations and organisations.

Secondly, microfinance organisations are only established in the most advanced nations to serve this specific section. Their staff are qualified to work with the vulnerable, who are impoverished and have no financial documents or records. Their goods are, nevertheless, only intended to reduce inequality (Beisland et al., 2019). Secondly, it is difficult to change the operational and financial systems of microfinance organisations to extend their sector. Small commercial banks often require a variety of financial goods, such as bigger banks, whereas microfinance organisations usually supply disadvantaged citizens with a small selection of products and services. These goods are also made by greater financial entities. However, the issue is that they believe that lending to small companies is dangerous and requires high running costs. Both facets are also probable.

2.8. microfinance in Vietnam

2.8.1 Influences of Microfinance in Vietnam

Microfinance schemes in Vietnam are public-owned, semi-public-owned as well as private-sector involvement. They provide loans to the vulnerable at low rates from municipal governments and foreign donors. This microfinance facilities provided by foreign lenders are limited NGOs or subsidized schemes that are not lawfully approved to offer microfinance and to raise savings from the public. The savings typically do not provide adequate funds for the lending operations of microfinance providers. As a consequence, they have difficulty in obtaining further venture funds to extend their strong development due to funding restrictions. Debts and deposits seem to be suitable funds for microfinance services in Vietnam, based on the knowledge of microfinance services around the world. However,

market-price debts will raise prices and therefore adversely impact the productivity ratio. In the case of offering microfinance loans, local financial institutions implicitly offer microfinance services to the vulnerable, who appear to favour microfinance services due to various existing advantages.

Microfinance services have shown a tremendous increase in efficiency over the last few years. The primary goal of microfinance is to meet poor people's unfulfilled financial demand for poverty reduction on a much larger scale. A lot of progress has therefore been decided to make in the last few decades, but a number of outstanding issues need to be solved. In Vietnam, microfinance services face some of the main challenges. First, in its early stages, microfinance was driven mainly by national government and NGOs. Over the last years, new donors have set up various funds to finance microfinance services. However, the lack of regulatory frameworks for microfinance has become one of the main factors which discourages large amounts of international microfinance funds from flowing into Vietnam. Second, microfinance programs appear to lack the means to expand outreach, since none of them is efficient and is not authorized to mobilize savings. Besides, there was a decline in corporate spending and a sharp turnaround of foreign capital movements after the 2008 global financial crisis. This dilemma involves microfinance programs to provide access to long-term debts and to build attractive products to generate savings and reduce capital costs. Moreover, microfinance providers will need to implement innovative technology to lower processing costs in the order of becoming productive and to increase consumer loyalty and to become sustainable. Third, the existence of funds and soft loans from municipal agencies and foreign organizations continues to dissuade microfinance services from seeking further entrepreneurial debts and mobilizing savings, which will help them decrease capital expenses and improve outreach. Fourthly, microfinance programs need to become sustainable in order to remain effective and extend their outreach. However, few microfinance programs have the managerial ability to effectively run a commercial financial intermediary as they started as social mission NGOs through the distribution of loans to the needy. Microfinance providers also need to boost management capability in order to grow operational microfinance.

2.8.2. Lending approaches of microfinance in Vietnam

The common lending methods in Vietnam, as in many other countries, are personal and community lending. Roughly 80% of the loans are paid on a community loan basis, but the collateral system simply acts primarily as a way to reduce processing expenses, not a shared responsibility scheme (Laurenson & Nghiem, 2005). Most of the loans are issued on collateral/guarantee by structured entities for persons or company loans. Land use certificates, houses and fixed assets are the assets listed and used as collateral, of which rural borrowers use land use certificates most frequently. Movable properties, such as televisions, bicycles and poultry are not secured. In fact, the appeal process requires the local community committee to approve the inventory of properties and their overall worth (Fanconi & Scheurle, 2017).

In the structured market, the annual interest rate is relatively small on average with the average loan volume for regulated and semi-formal lenders and unregulated lenders being

typically small. It is important to note that the Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development tends to give the list of assets of the potential borrower half the actual loan sum requested by the main criteria for loans (Lebovics et al., 2016). The Land Use Certificate is the most widely accepted form of asset/collateral (Daley-Harris, 2002). Where a family has not obtained Land Use Permits, municipal government assurance that the property is uncontroversial can be seen as a credit assurance (Harper & Arora, 2005).

As a government regulation, structured financial organisations provide loans for development purposes only (Johnson, 1996). In 1998, loans for growth capital constituted approximately 65% of all loans obtained from all sources. While applying for a loan, lenders may request a business plan. In fact, although the government does not allow guarantees on loans of up to \$700, households are usually required to include their Land Use Certificates as security in order for the loan to be protected (Ashta, 2016). Consequently, project proposals and land management licenses are essential requirements for the standardised borrowers' processing of candidates (Singh, 2004; Le, 2017).

The lending systems of structured microfinance organisations are influenced by many variables. First, while the interest rate has increasingly risen, low basic interest rates and government determination to provide low-cost loans for poor households have prevented regulated institutions from being expanded to more rural households as a result of the cost of transactions which causes financial repression (Van Hung, 2004; Balkenhol, 2007). Secondly, Land Use Permits have been issued progressively and, in several provinces, have not yet been established. This decreases the likelihood of access to structured credit for rural families. In addition, an efficient use of Land Use Certificates, as collateral, requires a market that does not exist for the transfer of Land Use Certificates (Bateman, 2011).

2.8.2.1. Individual Loan

The acceptance of the loan and, in particular, the amount of the loan, depends upon the collateral given. The non-security loan cap has been raised to US \$700 but the borrowers are usually required to mention properties as security and to verify the cumulative worth of the properties identified by the Local People Committee (Noltze, 2008). Certificates of land use tend to be the most important loan protection (Dufhues et al., 2002). In certain instances, such as the Vietnam Bank for the Needy, poor rural households are expected to apply a Local People's Committee certification to make sure they are poor households and are qualified for loans (Ashta, 2015).

The administrative method for the payment of loans is a time-consuming operation. The primary factor is the absence of a local branch network. In the case, for example, of the Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development, with an internal branch network, the branch network is distributed only at the district level and credit officers will fly around to process loan applications, in most cases primarily in rural villages (Ghate, 2008). In order to agree on the loan, the credit officer must review the bid of the lender in the context of the so-called "company proposal". The credit officer often estimates a cumulative loan balance

that is typically equivalent to 60% of the overall valuation of the assets listed. Nonetheless, the division director makes the ultimate call (Sorell & Cabrera, 2015).

2.8.2.2. Group Loan

Theories have demonstrated that shared partnership community loans are the best recognised financing platform for microfinance companies worldwide. It has shown that this leveraging technology can help to minimise asymmetric knowledge issues by choosing colleagues, tracking and control, the loss of collateral vulnerabilities and related risks. This system allows prospective lenders to shape borrowing classes. The borrowing community's key and significant feature is shared liability, implying that all party leaders are expected to repay their deferred partners to obtain additional credit (Matthäus-Maier & Pischke, 2008).

In Vietnam, about 80% of rural poor private debt is calculated by borrowing classes. However, most financial institutions (with the exception of foreign NGOs) render community loans without clearly defined joint responsibility. Credit associations are mostly formed by voluntary organisations. Each loan group has to be certified by the Local People's Committee that they are poor households in order to apply for loans. The cycle of investing then proceeds as in the personal loan model (Geleta, 2016). Credit officers distribute loans solely from each member of the group and collect refunds.

Currently, the shared liability capital is overlooked. The party member is accountable for the whole party but is not liable. Its duties are clearly to provide credit officers with details regarding community members, to obtain mortgage applications from team members and (iii) to encourage participants to repay their loans. However, in many situations, community members cannot handle their departments adequately due to the absence of appropriate processes and the inadequate awareness of organisational skills. In the case of a failure, other party leaders may not have to pay anything, although in terms of social repercussions, for example fames, they can place some burden on the lost partners (Goldberg & Palladini, 2010). The loan officers are liable for coping with defaulting lenders and the community leader may convince them to pay it back.

Thus, while group loans are common, they are merely a method to minimise transaction fees instead of a method for reducing default risks. Others can also regard this loan technology as personal loans by classes. Nevertheless, this system varies considerably from standard person lending as it lends to approved classes. If groups are formed by SOs and certified by the Local People Committee, the financial body can take advantage of the information and provide individual loans to a group of borrowers. The cooperation or collaboration with the Social Groups and the Local People's Committee eliminates asymmetric knowledge issues which exist in the traditional loans (Tuan, 2005).

2.9. Human Capabilities

Economic isolation has been suggested as a consequence of poverty or a lack of expertise. Sen (2005) introduced the philosophy of capabilities. The basic concept of the skill method is to improve the power of individuals to make decisions on their freedoms in that they have to do the activities they want to do or have cause to enjoy.

The philosophy of human development, and the approach to capacity within the human development framework, has been considered a return to the origins of economic discipline. The essence of economic discipline arose as a consequence of wider human concerns; nevertheless, the philosophy has now shifted to narrower and more quantitative metrics of success such as the emphasis on income and property. The principle of human development is related to some of the world's greatest thinkers, including Aristotle (385–322 BC) and more modern thinkers. Miettinen (2013) argued that the basic aim of human growth is to improve people's choices.

The capability strategy uses a community approach to conversations on deprivation and growth. It is based on the idea that development's primary objective is to give people more freedom and options, not just money. Boettke & Subrick (2003) claimed that suffering should be seen not just because of low incomes, but as a lack of basic capacities. A lack of income is indeed a good starting point for researching deprivation but not a strong destination. The underlying problem resides in the value of bringing citizens out of deprivation, and that is based on the idea of changing people's lives. The capability solution reflects on the organisation and the independent citizens have to do what they want with their lives. Walker (2008) claimed that creation required eliminating various forms of restrictions which left citizens with very few options and little ability to practice their rational power. The approach to capability is about what an individual needs to do and its success, as it looks at the potential to produce those goals. Most of the other systems, including financial and social isolation and social resources, are focused on implementing goals or principles in action. Based on those discussions, this study adopted the definition of Fukuda-Parr (2003) and Sen (2005), which defined human capabilities as functioning, agency and freedom, and examines whether microfinance influenced these aspects of its participants.

The categories or indices of social inclusion, which are use, development, political participation and social contact, may also be seen as indicators of the functioning of an individual, that is, of what a person values or desires in his or her life. As Sen (1999) indicates, social exclusion can emerge as a consequence of lack of ability. Similarly, due to a lack of ability, an individual could not be able to accomplish the fulfilment of his or her functions (Sinha et al., 2019). However, while intake, development and social contact can be elements of functioning, the political commitment of an individual is directly linked to the capacity of a person to work and is thus directly related to the ability of a person to function.

The political dimension of social inclusion is indirectly related to the idea of a capacity strategy, and this is where the notion of preference and capacity becomes relevant in the discourse on social exclusion (Alawattage et al., 2019). The discourse on social exclusion also avoids the position of preference and ignores the fact that individuals may want not to be included. Social capital is strongly linked to social inclusion and, in particular, to the social

engagement aspect. Social capital applies to the effects of what occurs as individuals communicate socially (Anglin, et al., 2020).

Many various forms of measures have been established in relation to social isolation and there are other indicators linked to well-being and ability (García-Pérez et al., 2020). The goal of this study was not to use them as a metric of a person's general sense of well-being or the degree to which they were socially included, or even to create a new collection of measures. These structures were used to inform the study and to instruct the interview questions as a general reference (Dahal & Fiala, 2020). As mentioned above, the focus of this analysis was clearly to place the participants at the core of the research design, to consider their expectations and priorities (their functioning) as well as their needs, and to see if and how the microfinance schemes could promote greater potential for the participants.

Figure 2.1. Conceptual framework

2.10. Conclusion

In order to meet the millennium goals, microfinance has proved to be a relevant, efficient and influential platform for the vulnerable and for reducing poverty. In the current literature, the detailed study of microfinancing posed several essential questions. Firstly, microfinance obviously cannot transform the vulnerable into the non-poor overnight. The argument is that microfinance is basically a long-term method, which aims to financially empower disadvantaged people in order to leverage their talents, knowledge, resources and financial capital to move freely from deprivation and improve their lives. Secondly, donor finance continues to be inadequate to satisfy the growing demand from both new and existing clients for well-designed financial goods. A connection to private funds is also likely to enable MFIs to move from highly regulated activities to try to gain productivity for sustainability. Thirdly, a number of studies have focused on studying the impact of microfinance or trade-offs between social purposes and financial stability rather than on the likelihood of it being viable in the long term to provide financial services to the vulnerable. Fourthly, microfinancing

played a significant part in microfinance institutions' economic stability and survival. Fifth, financing methodologies, savings, gender empowerment and the effects of microfinance are likely to be focused on microfinancing institutions' legal status, income status and regulatory status. Lastly, these studies also emphasised the link between participant capability and the influences of social and financial perspectives to the participant of microfinance initiatives. This thesis, therefore, seeks to fill these gaps in the literature by exploring microfinancing from a social perspective and examining the impact of these structures on the participant's capabilities. The next section presents research method and main research methodology for this thesis

CHAPTER 3. RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This work refers to the demand for more informed microfinance study in Vietnam, putting the experiences of the program participants at the core of the research design. As Chapter 1 explained, there is a rising argument about the effects of microfinance initiatives. In the objectives of this research, it refers to the analysis of the cumulative outcomes in members of the programme. There is also growing literature that explores the various ways to quantify the effects. A database has also been created to detail the multiple ways to assess impact and emphasis on social enterprise initiatives. The methodology employed in this research is closely linked to what Hulme (2000) calls the humanities methodology, using qualitative approaches to gather data.

The research methodology and the methods used in this study are explained in this chapter. It starts by defining the philosophical context for this study and includes the epistemological background used to direct the analysis, namely the constructivist epistemology. This is accompanied by a clarification of the application of the phenomenological theoretical view and whether a qualitative method is employed. This chapter outlines the research sample and data collection technique, as well as a description of the three essential data collection techniques used for this study: semi-structured interviews, an evaluation of the subjects and the management of a research report. Analytical methods are defined and descriptions of the difficulties and weaknesses in the research are presented in the chapter.

3.2. Philosophical Stance

The philosophical context through which analysis is carried out must be recognised as it determines the nature and limits of science. A researcher's epistemological approach establishes the framework for the study design. Bryman (1984) noted that the object of epistemology is to have a metaphysical framework for deciding what sort of understanding is feasible, including what the researcher ascertains to be information (Ghauri et al., 2020). This research's epistemological method was the constructivist approach. Awareness and truth are based on human actions, constructed into and out of the relationship between human beings and their environment, and in a predominantly human sense (Adams et al., 2007). The purpose of this research was to explain the interaction between the participants and the microfinance programmes. Based on the assumption that meaning is formed by interaction, Khan (2014), in this case the implication produced by the interaction between participants and their perceptions of the microfinance project, the positive epistemological was deemed suitable for this analysis (Ghauri et al., 2020). The emphasis was on the intangible people and how the effects the microfinance projects had on their lives was significant.

It varied considerably from the objective-oriented epistemology, which believes that the sense of fact and information rests in the objects and is non-interpreted (Myers, 2019). If an

objectivist method had been utilised for this inquiry, methodological approaches should have been used for data collection, such as polls, with the emphasis focusing on effective measures rather than the nature of the relationships between individuals. Specific theoretical viewpoints guide the work within constructivist epistemology (Bryman, 1984). Theoretical insights generally apply to the theories a researcher introduces into a research project. The phenomenological method was the critical theoretical viewpoint guiding this research. This involved the elimination of preconceived ideas about what is being examined and an analysis of the definitions of the interviewees (Marschan-Piekkari & Welch, 2011). However, phenomenology is the fundamental and most crucial presumption that affects the participants' living reality (Houy et al., 2010). Another fundamental principle is that individuals can be known on the basis of their universes (Buckley & Chapman, 1996). Throughout this study, the primary emphasis was on the perspectives of the participants of the microfinance projects throughout the broader life.

The project's analysis architecture was qualitative, with qualitative approaches having been used since it was believed that definitions were generated from experiences in the universe in phenomenological methodology (Smart et al., 2019). Qualitative researchers continue to address questions that emphasise the development and importance of social interaction (Goulding, 2002). Qualitative approaches were more suitable for this work as it focused on the participants and their perspectives and their perspective on the impacts of the microfinance initiatives. This was not an evaluation of the programs. A conceptual study approach was the only way to cope with analysis problems.

The qualitative method, therefore, provides the ability to fully appreciate the roles and capacities provided to participants by the services. This ensured that participants might explore the effect of the curriculum on them without implementing a preconceived set of answers (Lee, 2009). This was intentional as it was meant to quantify what was relevant for the participants. To do so, the research required consistency and semi-structured interviews. It was essential to see if the services fitted in with the lives of the participants and, as later illustrated in this chapter, participant evaluation offered this opportunity. The goal was to consider what was relevant for the participants of the microfinance projects and what facets of the initiatives, from their viewpoint, had the most significant influence.

Conceptual reasoning and theoretical development are interconnected with the methodology of the relational analysis system—the grounded theory approach (Khan, 2014). The qualitative methodology is being adopted to identify possible origins and causes that have been poorly studied and investigated (Remenyi et al., 1998). The use of a qualitative study was further expanded by Guba & Lincoln (1983) in that it is a philosophical approach which believes that truth is interconnected, intertwining and linking the researcher to the research matter. Furthermore, qualitative analysis focused on three main paradigms and the core ones of a qualitative study are positivism, interpretivism and critical paradigm (Myers, 2019). Neuman (1991, p. 57) provided additional insights of paradigms as:

'A paradigm is a framework or a set of assumptions that explain how the world is perceived where the paradigm of a science includes its basic assumptions, the important questions to be answered or puzzles to be solved, the research

techniques to be used, and examples of what scientific research looks like'
(Neuman, 1991, p. 57).

As a well-known qualitative researcher who used paradigms in a particular context to generate the understanding of inquiry, Kuhn (1970) promoted the use of paradigms as:

'A set of values and techniques which is shared by members of a scientific community, which act as a guide or map, dictating the kinds of problems scientists should address and the types of explanations that are acceptable to them' (Kuhn, 1970, p. 175).

In fact, all paradigms are focused on multiple viewpoints, with such viewpoints covering epistemology, ontology and philosophy (Day & Bobeva, 2005). The epistemological approach addresses the manner in which information is gained. This is largely based on the interaction between the investigator and participant whether the investigator interprets his/her research findings (Salaria, 2012). Ontology is fascinated with the essence of truth. Truth is viewed as contextual and relies on how it is interpreted by researchers and informants (Marschan-Piekkari & Welch, 2011). Methodology is associated with the mechanism and process by which the investigator interprets and generates an understanding of a particular phenomenon (Maylor et al., 2016).

Neuman (1991) distinguished metaphysical paradigms of perception and positivism. He claimed that the positivist perspective of the reality is empirical, where action and causes and effects could be assessed and human actions interpreted. Regarding this issue, he interpreted the role of a positivist researcher as:

'For a positivist researcher, the purpose of research is to understand how the world works so that the events can be controlled or predicted' (Neuman, 1991, p. 58).

An interpretive interpretation of the world is contextual, where people shape their own perception of the universe in various ways by their experiences with others. Each person perceives the reality differently and sees it in various ways. Their decisions and attitudes are often inconsistent (Zikmund et al., 2013). These sociological paradigms have their own advantages and limitations as defined by Saunders & Lewis (2012); the positivism is regarded empirical whereas interpretivism is perceived quite contextual. Due to the reality that all research strategies have their own benefits, the most significant thing about evaluating testing techniques is that they are focused on scientific criteria and study goals (David & David, 2016).

Collectively, this form of study, which aims at analytical thought and theoretical construction, is oriented on an interpretive methodology, because the investigator needs to see the social context and phenomenon from the viewpoint of the participant and generate an understanding of the experience based on the context of the respondent (Jeston & Nelis, 2014). It is also clarified by Denzin & Lincoln (2003, p. 296) about the possibility that the interpretive method relies on both the participant's experience and the investigator's perception of the truth, such that the investigator can "*find meaning in an action, or to say*

one understands what a particular action means, requiring that one interprets in a particular way what the actions are doing”.

3.3 Qualitative Research Design

The emerging development of qualitative research has emerged as a consequence of the discontent amongst certain researchers with the empirical analysis amongst psychiatry, such as behaviouralists.

‘We can never achieve a complete ‘scientific’ understanding of the human world. The best we can do is to arrive at a truth that makes a difference that opens up new possibilities for understanding’ (McLeod, 2001, p. 4).

While psychologists analyse human behaviours, the conventional method to science is not viewed as an acceptable way to carry out work as it struggles to understand the entirety of human nature and the meaning of what it is to be human. The study of participants’ perceptions is regarded as a conceptual method (Chohan, 2019).

The conceptual paradigm is a qualitative technique and used more in qualitative analysis with this style of research emphasising on the ‘grounded theory approach’ because it is rational thought and concrete construction rather than theoretical or hypotheses testing (Gray, 2019), which is typically performed in the quantitative analysis methodology. Qualitative work is an interpretive, naturalistic practice (Collis & Hussey, 2013). In the words of Creswell (1998, p. 15):

‘Qualitative research is an inquiry process of understanding based on distinct methodological traditions on inquiry that explore a social or human problem. The researcher builds a complex, holistic picture, analyses words, reports details of informants and conducts the study in a natural setting’.

The goal of qualitative study is to grasp the social context of people, organisations and societies as closely as possible as the participants experience or practice it. Therefore, individuals and communities are observed in their normal environments (Rouse, 1997). Qualitative work is exploratory and aims to understand ‘how’ and ‘why’ a given event or activity functions as it will in a specific sense (Ji & Hussey, 2009). Qualitative work is focused on perceptions and impressions of people’s experiences of various occurrences and provides a glimpse of people’s views in a natural environment (Collis & Hussey, 2009). For a ‘grounded hypothesis’ methodology in which studies aim to illustrate and analyse employee impressions of a problem and the misuse of control in an organisation, observational evidence is obtained by direct interactions, focus groups and telephone interviews, (Hunt, 1977). In fact, in order to improve the framework and address scientific issues, investigators need to collect data and evaluate it and replicate it over and over before fresh evidence or evidence exhaustion is prevented (Hussey & Hussey, 1997). The grounded theoretical method is an acceptable way to examine human actions on a critical issue as well as in a specific cultural background

(Konopinski, 2013). Throughout the graph, the investigators sought to differentiate the rooted quantitative method from the majority of the conceptual strategies (Atahau et al., 2020).

In order to address the research questions, a selection of three forms of microfinance systems was selected for the analysis. The three initiatives were based in the urban areas of Ho Chi Minh city and Hanoi city. This ensured comparability between the sample as social contexts and living environments in one area or country may differ from another. The microfinance programs, such as the No-interest Loans Scheme, the Ambitious Women Program, and the Savings and Loans Circles, were selected with the AWP being one of the most prominent programs that provided support for women—allowing them to become entrepreneurs and develop their own business or deliver both savings and loans facilities.

Participant observation was often performed with representatives of the savings and loan circles in order to achieve a contextualized view of the lives of the participants. A qualitative approach was necessary for the credibility of the study, since it was crucial to consider the effects of the microfinance projects from the viewpoint of the participants. In order to preserve the theoretical credibility of the capacity strategy, the emphasis was on encouraging participants to communicate what was essential to them in terms of their lives and goals. This was achieved using observational analysis techniques, including semi-structured interviews of participants and observation of participants. A scientific report has since been maintained to guarantee the integrity of the research phase. All interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed and then examined for evolving cultural themes.

Figure 3.1 Features of different qualitative approaches

Features	Narrative	Phenomenon	Grounded theoretical approach	Ethnography	Case study
Focal points	Explore practices of person or profession	Generate understanding through experience of participants	Develop new theoretical background from collected data in the field	Interpret and describe knowledge from culture amongst participants	Develop an in-depth narrative and explanation of issues through a single or a variety of cases
Problems that were frequently considered in the study	Interpret story behind phenomenon or experience and understanding of profession	Illustrate the essence of a reality or anomaly	Develop appropriate theory based on perceptions of researcher and experience of participants	Discussing the understanding of common practices in social culture	Provide an in-depth interpretation of a situation or scenario
Background	Illustrating on classics, including philosophy, literature, culture, sociology and psychology	Trying to draw on science, sociology, and culture	Root from social sciences	Starting to draw on history and sociology	Attempting to draw on psychology, economics, social sciences and medication
Research sample	Research of one or more people	Exploring a variety of people who have similar knowledge	Analysis of a mechanism, event, or activity affecting multiple individuals	To research a community that shares similar cultures	The analysis of a case, a plan, an action, more than one person

Features	Narrative	Phenomenon	Grounded theoretical approach	Ethnography	Case study
Data collection procedure	Use interviews and records	The usage of interviews with people in particular, while records, impressions and art can also be regarded	Use interviews as data collection approach with a specific number of participants	Used impressions and interviews in particular, but also gathering other documents during prolonged field time	The usage of various data sources, such as interviews, reports, records and objects
Data analysis techniques	Analyse events, "restore" tales, creating patterns, sometimes use chronology	Analysis of data for important phrases, i.e. groups, procedural and conceptual definitions, definition of the "essence"	Analysis collected data by explaining and interpreting coding, axial coding, selective coding	Analysis of data via a summary of the culture-sharing community; community themes	Analyse data by a summary of the event and the dynamics of the event as well as cross-case dynamics
Interpret findings	Develop a story about a person's life narratives	Describe the "essence" of the practice.	The generation of a theory described in a model or framework	Describe how the culture-sharing community functions	Build a thorough study of one or several cases

3.4 Grounded Theory

The methodological analysis methodology ‘grounded theory’ was founded by two sociologists, Barney Glaser & Anselm Strauss (Collis & Hussey, 2003). In these terms, they described ‘grounded theory’ as “*The theory that was derived from data, systematically gathered and analysed through the research process*” (Strauss & Corbin, 1990, p. 12). Grounded theory is mostly around data gathering and study. The goal of this method is to build a concept centred on data (Kombo & Tromp, 2006). In the words of Colli & Hussey, (2003), grounded theory is concerned more with an inductive method instead of a deductive method to science. In a similar vein, Punch (1998, p. 163) provided a brief definition of the grounded theory approach in his work as:

‘Grounded theory is not a theory at all. It is a method, an approach, a strategy. In my opinion, grounded theory is best defined as a research strategy whose purpose is to generate theory from data. ‘Grounded’ means that the theory will be generated on the basis of data; the theory will therefore be grounded in data. ‘Theory’ means that the objective of collecting and analysing the research data is to generate theory. The essential in grounded theory is that theory will be developed inductively from data’.

Although Hussey (2003) added that rooted methodology relied on inductive data processing approaches, it started with basic ideas and describes and understands details. The journey of theoretical growth in a grounded theoretical method starts and ends with results. This explanation of grounded theory is best interpreted by Strauss & Corbin (1998, p. 12) as:

‘Data collection, analysis, and eventual theory stand in close relationship to one another ... the researcher begins with an area of study and allows the theory to emerge from the data ... grounded theories, because they are drawn from data, are likely to offer insight, enhance understanding, and provide a meaningful guide to action’.

Since the ground-breaking growth of the concept by Glaser & Strauss in 1967, it has been in the process of being modified by its instigators and other social science scholars for several decades. The idea is also split into two ‘forms’ by its originators, the Glaser edition (Glaser, 1978, 1992) and the variant edition (Strauss, 1987; Schwartz, 2011). Glaser tended to concentrate on the early idea and kept faithful with it, the one he found with Strauss. These authors perceived grounded theory as “*... a method of discovery, treated categories as emergent from the data, relied on direct and, often, narrow empiricism, and analysed a basic social process*”. Around the same period, Strauss (1987) pushed the approach towards proof rather than relying on the earlier variant of grounded theory. Following considerable opposition, the iteration of grounded theory became more popular than the older variant of grounded theory (Strauss, 1987; Strauss & Corbin, 1990, 1998). The work acted as a valuable method for performing grounded theoretical approaches and has educated graduate students around the world (Charmaz, 2014). Charmaz (2006, pp. 5–6) further referred in his

work (Glaser, 1978; Glaser & Strauss, 1967; Strauss, 1987) to describing the elements of grounded theoretical analysis in such terms as:

'Simultaneous involvement in data collection and analysis. Constructing analytic codes and categories from data, not from preconceived logically deduced hypotheses. Using the constant comparative method, which involves making comparisons during each stage of the analysis. Advancing theory development during each step of data collection and analysis. Memo-writing to elaborate categories, specify their properties, define relationships between categories, and identify gaps. Sampling aimed toward theory construction, not for population representativeness. Conducting the literature review after developing an independent analysis.'

Charmaz (2003, p. 250) also outlined the development of grounded theory since its creation in the annotated text below:

'What grounded theory is and should be is contested. Glaser and Strauss and Corbin have moved the method in somewhat conflicting directions (Glaser, 1992; Strauss, 1987; Strauss & Corbin, 1990, 1994, 1998). Glaser's (1978, 1992) position often comes close to traditional positivism, with its assumptions of an objective, external reality, a neutral observer who discovers data, reductionist inquiry of manageable research problems, and objectivist rendering of data. Strauss and Corbin's (1990, 1998) stance assumed an objective external reality, aims towards unbiased data collection, proposes a set of technical procedures, and espouses verification. Their position moves to post-positivism because they also propose giving voice to their respondents, representing them as accurately as possible, discovering and acknowledging how respondents' views of reality conflict with their own, and recognising art as well as science in the analytic product and process.'

Strauss (1987) and Strauss & Corbin (1998) have moved the course of the grounded theoretical approach from a positivist model to a more constructivist model. This is further described in the following article by (Annells, 1996, p. 279):

'A theory is not the formulation of some discovered aspect of a pre-existing reality 'out there'. To think otherwise is to take a positivist position ... theories are interpretations made from given perspectives as adopted or researched by researchers. To say that a given theory is an interpretation – and therefore fallible – is not at all to deny that judgments can be made about the soundness or probable usefulness of it.'

However, Charmaz (2003, pp. 272–273) described it in more depth and sought to discern between both the valid and the actual from the rooted theoretical viewpoint:

'A constructivist grounded theory distinguishes between the real and the true. The constructivist approach does not seek truth—single, universal, and lasting. Still, it remains realist because it addresses human realities and assumes the existence of real worlds...the constructivist approach assumes what we take as real, as objective knowledge and truth, is based upon our perspective ... thus the grounded theorist constructs an image of reality, not the reality that is, objective, true, and external.'

Ultimately, grounded theory is a formal approach of the social sciences requiring the creation of concepts through empirical evidence collection and examination (Roger & Collis, 2009). This theoretical technique employs an inductive inference of comparison to the deductive paradigm of the experimental method. A research study utilising grounded theory is to launch with a query, or perhaps with the compilation of qualitative data. When analysts study the data gathered, recurring thoughts, principles or components become visible and are labelled with codes that have been derived from the data. When further details are gathered and certainly-reviewed, codes may be clustered into definitions and then into groups. Such categories would become the base of a new theory (Collis & Hussey, 2003). Thus, rooted theory is very distinct from the conventional empirical paradigm where the investigator uses an established scientific construct and then, instead, gathers evidence to demonstrate whether the hypothesis will or will not relate to the phenomena under analysis (Ghauri et al., 2020).

3.5. Research sample, participant recruitment, and case background

3.5.1 Research sample and participant recruitment

This part offers a summary of the three microfinance projects that involved respondents in this study, providing a brief description of the programmes and, in the following chapters, a more comprehensive explanation of the plans will be discussed. This section also justifies the sampling techniques that facilitated the data collection of this study.

In order to explain how microfinance programs lead to greater potential and effect for participants, it is first important to understand how the initiatives work and what their goals and philosophies are. The three initiatives were based in the urban areas of Ho Chi Minh city and Hanoi city. This ensured comparability between the sample as social contexts and living environments in one area or country may differ from another. The microfinance programs, such as the No-interest Loans Scheme, the Ambitious Women Program, and the Savings and Loans Circles, were selected with the AWP being one of the most prominent programs that provided support for women—allowing them to become entrepreneurs and develop their own business or deliver both savings and loans facilities. Theoretical sampling was used to recruit participants from these microfinance initiatives. In order to gather evidence from places, individuals and activities, theoretical sampling was adopted as a survey technique to optimise the likelihood of forming hypotheses in terms of properties and measurements, locating differences and classifying associations between ideas (Goulding, 2002). It is distinct

from conventional data sampling methods, as it is carried out as a response to the data already gathered, as opposed to sampling strategies developed at the outset of a project.

Regarding the sample collection, the first step was to identify the current microfinance programs in Vietnam by referring to active microfinance programs, available at: <https://microfinance.vn/>. After identifying a list of programs, the researcher went through the list of participants provided by the Vietnam Microfinance Working Group. An email was then sent with detailed information of the research to participants of the microfinance initiatives; they then emailed back to express their participation interest. In other words, the participants in this study were voluntary.

Regarding sample size, the expectation was to interview thirty to fifty participants from all of the microfinance initiatives in Vietnam, following the theoretical sampling approach and each interview was estimated to be between one hour and thirty minutes. Each interview was recorded or notes taken with the permission of the participants. Theoretical sampling is a data collection method for gathering data from locations, persons and events that optimises possibilities to build theoretical attributes and metrics, to explore changes and to identify relationships between principles. It is distinct from conventional data sampling methods, because it is done as a solution to data already obtained and not as sampling techniques developed at the start of the process.

3.5.2. Case background

To consider how microfinance initiatives lead to enhanced user capacities and influences, the author will describe the background of these microfinance initiatives and highlight how the systems functions and what their goals and philosophies are. This section, hence provides a summary of the three separate microfinance schemes that have been mentioned in this thesis, including Non-interest Loan Schemes (NLS), the Ambitious Women Program (AWP) and the Savings and Loan Circle (SLC). Every part of this section starts with details on the microfinance programs background and also includes a summary of its aims and principles, as well as details about how these services are organized and engaged with the users. This is accompanied by a brief description of the members' backgrounds for each microfinance system.

3.5.2.1. Non-Interest Loan Scheme (NLS)

The Non-Interest Loans Scheme (NLS) is a microfinance service offered by the Vietnam Microfinance Working Group, the Vietnamese government agencies and Vietnam commercial banks. The system provides no-interest loans to low-income persons, primarily for the purchasing of household items. Nearly twenty years ago, after the year 2000, the first low interest loan was given by the International Monetary Fund (IMF).

The conception of the NLS system came into existence from the collaboration of the Vietnamese Government and the International Monetary Fund (IMF), with further loans given

to citizens with low earnings. Initially, loans from the IMF's fund were provided for the government of Vietnam. Since 2010, the government of Vietnam has been borrowing directly from IMF in order to fund microfinance in Vietnam. After a longitudinal survey of the region which showed a desire for these programs, the first offices were opened in Ha Noi, Vietnam. A few years later, the NLS Network of South and North Vietnam were set up, supported by the Asian NLS Network. These efforts allowed community groups and organisations to be able to participate and borrow low-interest free loans by assessing micro-financial services under Vietnamese government control.

The main aim of the NLS is to guarantee that participants obtain equality and support through the microfinance scheme offered by the NLS. The key goal of the NLS system is to offer equal and reasonable credit to those with little or no earnings. This varies significantly from the other two initiatives reviewed, as they both rely on the environment. The NLS system is largely focused on raising financial inclusion by supplying individuals with low-income exposure to secure and accessible loans, whereas the two other initiatives are, as can be seen below, both targeted at promoting social equality.

The NLS loans mainly provide participants the opportunities to buy domestic goods, such as refrigerators, dishwashers, furniture, television sets and arrange for home maintenance as well as pay for services like healthcare and education. They may be seen in certain situations for other uses like wellbeing and learning. Loans shall not be given, however, for debt repayment or household expenses and expenditures.

The NLS system works in such a manner as to reinvest payments received by borrowers in the pool of funds used for more loans. Customers are told that this is how the lending operates and that the NLS service agent points out to clients that the funds they are contributing will support those in need of a loan. This is called 'circular support' for the society. However, NLS system consumers do not reach each other, unlike the SLC and the AWP. This microfinance scheme only interacts with participants with proper references from connections with this program.

To qualify for a NLS loan, an individual must fulfil certain qualifying requirements. The nominee shall be in permanent housing where the NLS system is given, which is determined by its postal address, and must be at that address for at least six months. The place is normally near to an NLS location. Such conditions include individuals having an insurance card or pension plan and being able to pay back the loan.

Customers are able to borrow a low interest loan from \$300 to \$1000. Loans can be obtained for some household items and must be paid in full within 24 months. The payment amount is based on the ability of a person to pay the debt regardless of their income and expenditures.

The application procedure for an NLS loan is easy and clear. Potential applicants first contact the NLS office via phone or email and ask for help from the NLS services. The NLS staff also discuss the entry requirements and the manner of the loan is discussed. If you still want to

apply, the consumer should provide an application package, including an introduction note and a summary list of documentation to be sent by the applicants.

The consumer arranges to meet an NLS staff member and is required to provide bank accounts and different expenses information together with an estimate for the service they wish to purchase. A quotation is provided, amongst other factors, to help the NLS staff to decide on the amount of money that the consumer desires to borrow and whether they can identify a cheaper offer for the object they want to buy.

The customer and the NLS collaborate on the proposal and even conduct a planning exercise together, so that the staff will be confident that the consumer will not experience financial problems as a consequence of the loan. The appeal is then submitted and sent to a credit team. Usually, the board only accepts positive applications. In fact, staff will assess the applicants if the consumers fulfil the requirements, including their willingness to cover the loan without any additional strain on interest payments.

After it began, the NLS extended the service and continued to offer low to no income interest loans to individuals and there are now actually over twenty offices in Vietnam. Past studies have also shown continuity in the proportions of loan recipients, with estimates from 2010 reflecting the reality that nearly 60% of loans were provided for the procurement of white products—70% were female and the rest were male. The SAs described that most of NLS members were female.

All respondents in the NLS microfinance initiative of this study earned federal support as it was a condition for securing a loan. Table 3 offers a list of the NLS respondents' demographic data.

Interviewee code	Age	Sex	Marital status	Education	Income (per year)	Interview time (mins)
N1	47	Male	Single	Primary school	\$1,500	60
N2	50	Female	Single	Primary school	\$1,200	50
N3	48	Female	Married	Primary school	\$1,300	45
N4	55	Male	Married	Secondary high school	\$1,100	50
N5	57	Female	Married	Secondary high school	\$1,500	60
N6	45	Female	Married	Secondary high school	\$1,400	65

N7	58	Female	Married	Primary school	\$1,200	60
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Table 3.1. Participants of Non-interest Loan Scheme (NLS)

3.5.2.2. Ambitious Women Program (AWP)

As part of a cooperation initiative, since 2010, between the Vietnam Women’s Union, the Vietnam Minister of Finance and Vietnam’s Microfinance Working Group the Ambitious Women Program (AWP) has been in existence. The AWP offers women’s programs, in particular, in holistic therapy, sexual health, lifestyle and guidance, and education and support for female entrepreneurs. Their activities support women residing throughout the nation.

Before the AWP was initiated, a public consultation had been carried out to determine how microfinance support could be used and implemented in Vietnam and particularly the South-West and North-Eastern Vietnamese low-income regions. This program provided credit preparation and, as was being consulted by the Vietnamese government, it could possibly provide longer-term benefits other than just loans.

A pilot study was implemented between 2005 and 2010 to follow the consulted project. A significant finding from the pilot was that women needed financial education and management training. The AWP has, therefore, been updated to provide financial education and management training modules. The pilot plan continued over several years and concluded in 2010.

Following the results of the pilot project, the AWP was targeted at empowering disadvantaged people, in particular women from different cultures and languages in Vietnam. The AWP has always focused on the idea that people would be the most motivated because the curriculum is cohort-based and gives participants an opportunity to connect. One of the key factors for the AWP targeting ethnic minority women was that the pilot project found that, relative to people in other places in Vietnam, people from different ethnical cultures did not have or were sponsored in terms of business and financial management training.

Three separate facilities were given by the AWP. It included funding for micro-entities, which included a training curriculum for entrepreneurs and the possibility of taking out a small- interest loan at the completion of the business training. Women firstly needed to execute and apply a business proposal in order to be considered for a loan. Financial literacy instruction was also offered as part of the project, providing people the ability to join the Northern AWP, a community that helps entrepreneurs and shares their market skills. For this study, only people who were a sponsored micro-enterprise were questioned. Any of these participants have enrolled in the Northern AWP. None of the people studied were engaged in the financial literacy program. A few women who have taken the training in financial education have also begun the Vietnam women enterprise network.

Interviewee code	Age	Sex	Marital status	Education	Income (per year)	Interview time (mins)
A1	52	Female	Married	University	\$3,000	60
A2	50	Female	Married	University	\$2,500	55
A3	49	Female	Married	University	\$2,800	65
A4	55	Female	Married	High school	\$3,000	60
A5	56	Female	Married	High school	\$3,200	60
A6	54	Female	Married	High school	\$2,800	50
A7	57	Female	Married	High school	\$2,500	55
A8	48	Female	Married	High school	\$2,800	40
A9	49	Female	Single	Secondary High school	\$2,200	55
A10	53	Female	Single	Secondary High school	\$2,500	60
A11	50	Female	Married	Secondary High school	\$2,500	50
A12	42	Female	Married	High school	\$3,000	50
A13	45	Female	Single	High school	\$2,600	60
A14	47	Female	Single	High school	\$2,600	60
A15	45	Female	Married	High school	\$2,500	65

Table 3.2. Participants of Ambitious Women Program (AWP)

3.5.2.3. Savings and Loan Circle (SLC)

The Microfinance Working Group Vietnam is located in the two largest cities in Vietnam—Ho Chi Minh city and Hanoi city—and has a development history over the last few decades. The development of this microfinance independent organisation is traditionally regarded as mutual assistance delivered facilities. Mutual support programs traditionally tended to offer social services such as life care and unemployment compensation. They were constantly led by people they knew and who donated to a fund of money to support their lives, their families and relatives. The Vietnam Microfinance Working Group has begun a project with the idea of providing mutual assistance to extend the SLC network.

Secondly, the Vietnam Microfinance Working Group created this SLC and decided to spread the concept in the north of Vietnam as it represented their mutual help roots. They employed many community participants who introduced the SLC concept to numerous community organisations in the north. The training plan has also been developed by the Vietnam Microfinance Working Group. The plan was a tool to help microfinance members create a network of savings and loans. It included details on the intent and function of the circles, and recommendations and methods for sustainable savings or credits.

The SLC has been advocated by the Microfinance Working Group Vietnam as such centres support the ideals of establishing and nurturing partnerships, collaborative decision-making and community sovereignty. The SLC was developed by the two communities where employees visited numerous community groups and supported the SLC concept.

There are around twenty SLCs operating and the agreement amongst those interested in developing and running an SLC is that the majority of the circles were initiated after the training program was already in action. Two of the new circles began operations in early 2020.

There were also other SLCs that vanished. Participants verified during the assessment that there were a few SLCs that were no longer active. In addition, according to the Vietnam Microfinance Working group, the other group split because all the participants of these circles now had jobs and did not have time to meet or take part in activities of the SLC. The principal purpose of the SCL was not well established. Nevertheless, it seems that momentum in the initiative had arisen from consultations with community members as it followed the three core concepts of the Vietnam Microfinance Working Group, including: (i) self-help: implying that individuals have social service obligations and a sense of empowerment; (ii) cooperation: common benefits are shared with individuals in the community; and (iii) togetherness: individuals take care of each other, including others who may be in a tougher position than themselves.

Such values are built into the framework of the SLC. Although each circle has its own style of functioning, with each circle there are certain general ground principles and guidelines for how they operate.

There will be an individual in control of helping to build a new network, the word 'Promoter' used by the Vietnam Microfinance Working Party. The Promoter's initial task is to supply the new group with knowledge and make sure everybody engages fairly in decision-making. The key function for the Promoter is to establish the climate for the SLC, guaranteeing that it is an atmosphere in which participants interact with each other with dignity and tolerance.

The participants in the circle should have a link with each other and the leaders should have a shared purpose. This is because trust and partnership between participants are the main pillars on which the circles work. Confidence is a crucial element in the development of circles.

The SLC features encourage participants to get to know one another and learn to respect their resources to other community leaders. In the early stages, citizens will believe in the systems that they set in place and not in each other when they come together with their savings. This is because before they turn over their money, they create the guidelines that they choose to obey in the circle. You need trust in the program that you have put in place to turn over your capital. The length of time between entering a community and taking out a loan is normally necessary in order for the group to accept the new individual and the new member to be able to believe in the group.

Since each circle can differ in relation to other needs and operations, it is vital to create specific regulations and requirements, to recognise that they may respond to the adjustments in the circle's members' needs. Some of the popular characteristics of these circles will be that they interact regularly for a few months before they accumulate their joint savings in order to get to know one another and increase confidence. After a while, the circle must open a bank account, typically with several account signatories, to ensure that transparency is always possible. Circles will determine what kind of bank account they want to create. Once the account is accessible, the circle determines who will play various roles, including traders, account managers and secretaries. Such positions are advised to be exchanged periodically.

After these concerns have been identified, the participants of the circle begin regularly to contribute to savings in meetings. Several circles define both the lowest and highest savings, some merely mention minimum savings. After a certain amount of time, which is collectively decided, members cannot borrow money from the pooled savings. Members usually have to make contributions and engage consistently in meetings for a certain period of time so that they can raise capital.

The circle determines how long people have to be participants before they can borrow and, therefore, how much borrowing they can have at their fingertips. Decisions may require the loan intent (if they wish to determine this) as well as the cost and length of the repayment. If the bank account has enough funds, more than one participant may borrow at a given time. For situations where a dispute occurs and more than one participant needs to have a loan and the account has inadequate funds, a determination is framed in terms of ultimate need. The circle determines who is most in need of the loan or whose situation is most urgent; nevertheless, this problem has not yet occurred.

Over time, these rules can change to accommodate the changing needs of circle participants. If an individual wants to leave the community for some reason, they will make the contributions they have given to the network through their participation. This is intended to promote savings. While the SLC reflects the closest reproduction of microfinance trends abroad, especially in the developing world, the operations differ fundamentally. Although overseas models focus on peer pressure to guarantee repayments, as neither of them will access a loan in a circle before one is repaid, reciprocity and confidence are the foundations for the savings and lending cycles. Such principles are further explored in the next chapters in which the SLC is formed and controlled by its representatives. They are self-funded, which assists in making such organisations viable as long-term external support is not required. The only part of the circles in which extra funds would be needed is in teaching people to promote the initiation of the established circle and to provide any seed capital for the procurement of items, such as a receipt sheet, journals and head-books for record-keeping, generally between \$100 and \$300 per circle.

Participants require little or no training to join and engage in creating one of these groups. Group staff with previous practice also observe that the circles operate well where positions such as accounting, minute tracking, and report keeping have been shared, and all participants have a voice in the choices taken by this community. The procedures of how things are achieved in the circle are critical as to what is ultimately agreed, such as making sure that both have fair influence. Details of participants in the SLCs have been provided in the table below:

Interviewee code	Age	Sex	Marital status	Education	Income (per year)	Interview time (mins)
S1	53	Female	Single	Secondary High school	\$2,500	55
S2	51	Male	Single	High school	\$2,100	55
S3	55	Male	Married	High school	\$2,600	50
S4	48	Male	Married	Secondary High school	\$2,800	60
S5	47	Male	Married	Secondary High school	\$2,000	65
S6	55	Female	Married	High school	\$2,300	50
S7	50	Male	Single	Secondary High school	\$2,500	60

Interviewee code	Age	Sex	Marital status	Education	Income (per year)	Interview time (mins)
S8	51	Female	Single	Secondary High school	\$2,600	60

Table 3.3. Participants of Savings and Loan Circle (SLC)

3.6. Qualitative Data Collection

It is very interesting to pursue work in the field of conceptual growth with an explanation of constructions and further operationalisation. By way of analytical literature, defining the definition of structures and the application of their nomological network to such structures in order to establish a conceptual structure was an essential move ahead of the selection of a qualitative data collection process. Exploratory work is typically undertaken to investigate constructions and areas where insufficient knowledge and study is accessible on the topic (Morgan, 2013) and qualitative work is the simplest way to approach the study (Moore, 2006). Stephens (2009) described four approaches for the analysis of qualitative data that researchers may follow which comprise of fieldwork, evaluation, interviews—including team interviews and focus groups interviews—and the study of records and obtained documents.

As a result, for qualitative analysis data gathering, particularly in the sense of a grounded theoretical method, the type of semi-structured in-depth interviews and focus groups can be used to acquire data (Jensen & Laurie, 2016). Thus, the aim of data gathering and review is to define and analyse the context and factors correlated with the phenomena of the employee perception report. Interview data would be decoded and evaluated by encoding and continuously contrasting, taking into consideration the constructivist-based approach to theory. Analysed interview results, along with the documentation, would be used to incorporate and improve analytical analysis and the creation of concept (Dawson, 2019).

Regarding the qualitative data collection, individuals should be contacted during or after working hours and details about the purpose and justification of the study should be included. The protection and security of the data and findings will be assured to the responders. As stated earlier, when undertaking a ‘grounded hypothesis’ method and for the first round, investigators should assign standardised questionnaires to provide workers with the understanding of the phenomena of concern in the company. If there is an entity, the interviewer will perform a face-to-face, in-depth, open-ended and semi-structured discussion and panel discussions with the focus groups. Through certain forms of interviews, the interviewer has a greater opportunity of obtaining the participant’s in-depth thoughts and observations. The method of semi-structured interactions helps and encourages the interviewer to formulate a theme guide or related question for each subject in one environment (Brennan, 1998). Therefore, the face-to-face interaction enables the observer to carefully examine the subject for some non-verbal contact, which often helps both the investigator and the respondent (subject) to explain the confusion and the appropriate

points. Investigators do not tend to specify a particular timeline for interviews, but rather that such questions and periods are simply a reference and an approximation for interview periods; the length and period of the interview relies on the reaction to the subject, which may expand the interview (Cassell, 1994). Interview meetings should be audio or video-taped with the consent of the subject to evaluate the correct description of the conversation, and can be replayed for diagnostic purposes and anonymity may be maintained throughout the process. Attendees will be informed of their ability to withdraw from the analysis or to cancel the interview at any point prior to the start of the meeting (Abdulai & Owusu-Ansah, 2014; Bell et al., 2018).

3.6.1. Semi Structured Interview

Semi-structured face-to-face interviews were used to compile much of the data in all three microfinance programs. The interviewing procedure can be defined as a qualitative approach requiring transparent, relatively unstructured interrogation in which the interviewer looks for a piece of detailed knowledge within the thoughts, attitudes and opinions of the interviewee (Buckley & Chapman, 1996). A series of interviews for each curriculum was planned in order to maintain continuity between discussions and obtain answers to the critical study issue. The interviews explored a number of topics, such as the general knowledge of the participants, general information on the programme, the effects of the program, the financial status of the participants, the facets of the services that made improvements for them feasible and concerns regarding how people viewed their future.

In the interview plan, the section on the ‘impacts’ was the most controversial and an effort was made to include the most extensive possible spectrum of influences. Nearly all of the topics were the same in the interview order, with just variations in the issues that were program-specific. For instance, interviews with participants from the Ambitious Women Program had several concerns about business education and discussions with others who were taking part in the No-interest Loans Scheme having other questions regarding no-interest loans. The interview timetable was mostly used as a reference with a question order and terminology being versatile. Because of the transparent aspect of the interviewing process, participants frequently explored the interview questions without them actually being asked. The remainder of the audio excerpts were then analysed to ensure that no mistakes existed. This method allowed the interviews to be more clearly understood as the meaning and tones of the voices.

Prior to accessing each microfinance program, a number of pilot interviews were performed to determine how the topics were advancing correctly throughout the interview process and to validate the overall interview period. The pilot interviews were documented or registered, allowing analysis and appraisal of the interview method, while offering a means of coping with problems and developing the interview methodology during the interviews with participants. Interviews were performed in locations suitable for the interviewees.

3.6.2. Participant Observation

Participant observation is adopted as a complementary data collection approach for a semi-structured interview. Participant observations, also referred to as fieldwork and ethnography, are used most generally in anthropology; however, they are more frequently employed in other fields as data collection techniques (Adams et al., 2007). Over about a month, participant observations were conducted for participants of microfinance initiatives. In order to achieve a deeper understanding of the participants' society, conditions and lives, the participant observation approach was employed to develop a connection with participants and their community (Myers, 2019). Khan (2014) described the assessment of participants as a qualitative way of obtaining data concerning a healthy interaction with people when performing regular research. The insight involved talking to others to know more about what was occurring and to understand why events happened (Ghauri et al., 2020). This helped the investigator to gain an understanding of the context of the participants' lives and thus blend into the phenomenological sense.

The participant observation method is a method which allows for a better understanding of the complexities and meanings of people's lives (Goulding, 2002). This enables an "outsider" access to the "insider" perspective and helps the investigator to see the existence and perceptions of the participants over a lengthy period of time. This not only offers meaning but also helps the researcher more readily to recognise what is relevant in the life of a participant and to have the background in which to explain that it is appropriate. This work has provided a more in-depth insight into the relationships between the participants in the savings and loan cycles. The researchers were also able to discuss and examine their interactions and routines. A one-month observation period with the participant offered an ability to learn and see why various issues had become relevant in the life of the participants and whether the microfinance initiative had improved their lives.

Over the process of the observation period, various concepts appeared from observations and concerns were taken up in order to obtain further perspectives. For instance, the social aspect of the microfinance initiative is always assumed to be essential to participants. Based on the participant evaluation phase, the task of learning whether and why this social interaction has been helpful to participants was conducted. The participant observation discourse also addressed the importance of informants (Bryman, 1984). Informants include members with a community view and often they have knowledge that is not visible in discussions or interactions with others but know details which may be necessary. The participants were generally polite and happy, and the gatherings of their respective groups were allowed to be witnessed.

The observation of participants was designed to allow for the optimum amount of circle meetings during this study. During each discussion, the research and the analysis methodology were presented and detail was given on the survey. The contact between participants was witnessed through much of the conference. Connections and interactions were created with the members at the conclusion of the sessions, contributing to more participation. Wright (2003) stated that, before joining the area, a researcher must better grasp the investigation questions, the personal opinions of the individuals being examined and any difficulties. To better coordinate field operations, very comprehensive field records were made. Just before the field was reached, notes were provided about all interactions with

members, opinions and worries about the fieldwork phase and discussions with people about the fieldwork method.

3.7 Data Analysis

Content analysis is another large type of qualitative study. Text review evidence can take virtually any shape, including all forms of written records (magazines, legal hearings, student appraisal of teachers) and audio/visual resources. The purpose of the qualitative content review is to analyse both the manifest content of the item – what is currently documented or represented – and the latent content. Latent content refers to implicit signals or interpretations embedded in an object, such as unspoken expectations that provide significance to content in the social environment.

The qualitative method is driven by an inductive reasoning in which the future interpretation of a concept is inferred from the evidence. Hypotheses are then formulated after the compilation and initial review of the data, from which stage additional data are also obtained to test the hypotheses in the iterative method. Hypotheses in qualitative analysis also refer to the function of contextual variables that affect the phenomena of concern, and aim to discern whether and how people of differing backgrounds perceive the phenomenon differently. The aim of the qualitative research is not to obtain generally generalizable findings, but rather to include comprehensive or "thick" explanations of particular circumstances or experiences.

The data was analysed mainly through the organisation of interviews and field observations into themes and categories. Data from all of the interviews were coded and analysed, first on the topics of the interview system, accompanied by the answers of the participants. The study was supported by NVivo12, a qualitative data analysis computer software package. This software acts as a data analysing system which helps qualitative researchers to organise data into various categories and subcategories. It enables researchers to change categories and generate different groups with the same source of data.

The gathered data on these subjects was then re-examined and split down into smaller components. This required an estimation of the real results and what features of the programs were necessary for these results. Many of the definitions that resulted from this study were very weak since it was apparent that the results were not prone to any prejudice. The smaller divisions were then reorganised according to subjects and in certain situations merged with other types, in which terms were considerably overlapped. This led to the creation of the three central topics of the research: financial aspects, social perspective and capabilities.

Thereafter a matrix was drawn up to analyse the interaction of different impacts and components, determine which elements were most essential and obtain insight into the most common effects reported by the participants. It will accurately categorise the impacts through data sources.

3.8. Challenges During the Data Collection Stage

During the entire study, there were a number of challenges. Connections to people involved in the different microfinance schemes has sometimes been challenging, with difficulties in being able to have a conversation. This research experienced several obstacles. Because of the recent crisis triggered by the Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), several organisations had to close and people from other countries had to be isolated before reaching another region.

Such difficulties required the reprogramming of several interviews and more time was spent gathering data than anticipated. It was noted that the Vietnamese were not acquainted with the approach chosen for a profound qualitative analysis. Most respondents assumed that they would complete a questionnaire, just as they did for academic research. At the beginning of every discussion, about twenty minutes was spent demonstrating to the people who were interviewed that this was academic work and it was identified that people were cautious about being questioned, particularly if the interviews were recorded. This is attributable to the history and culture of Vietnam. It was explained to them that the interviews were private and confidential for research reasons only, and the name/company of the interviewee would never be disclosed. During every interview, a difference was noted in what was said and seen before the interviews and what some interviewees said during the meeting. The researcher noticed that, like the Vietnamese, it was because of the cultural and historical history of Vietnam and Asia that the researcher was questioned, so they were asked if they would avoid documenting interviews and the answer was yes. Nonetheless, ultimately a diverse range of programs was incorporated in this research.

3.9 Ethical Issues

Ethical concerns are relevant with both quantitative and qualitative studies, although ethical issues are more essential in qualitative research because qualitative analysis methods are sometimes invasive into the lives of the subjects (Jankowicz, 2005). This is why Neuman (2011, p. 143) held the human researcher accountable for the ethics of study. He stated that:

'Ethics begins and ends with you, the researcher. It is the moral and professional obligation of the individual researcher to be ethical even when research participants are unaware of or unconcerned about ethics' Neuman (2011, p. 143)

In the entire study cycle, the investigator was the one who recognised the possible gains and costs of the current research project. When gathering some kind of knowledge or details from the informants, the investigator would report some gains and disadvantages that could impact the participants (Smallbone & Quinton, 2004). Such broader ethical concerns in research that can lead to certain restrictions are: never inflict undue or unintentional damage to subjects; offer explicit informed consent when appropriate; and never needlessly humiliate, abuse or reveal derogatory details regarding particular persons gathered for scientific goals. Those are basic requirements that are open to definition, for example what does 'unnecessary' imply in a particular situation? (Dawson, 2013).
Involvement of every type

of study must be cooperative and the investigator must notify the respondents about all dimensions of the study. In this respect, it is important to remember that the investigator has received a written consent document signed by the subjects to remind them of their obligations and to include brief details on the research sample (Scheyvens, 2014).

In order to prevent the participation of the association to data gathering via a legal acceptance point of view, researchers should stop hiring respondents to their organisations. Alternatively, individuals may be reached using a snowball sampling method via the personal connections and networks of the investigator (Richards, 2014). In order to achieve the true nature of the report, the investigator will obtain the trust, consent and permission of the respondent before engaging in a discussion with the respondent. Before engaging in data collection with participants via interviews, explicit written consent should be collected from them and they must be told that they can exit at any point during the discussion. Besides, in order to prevent some form of recognition of persons, managers or institutions, work should be focused on previous observations and impressions of the phenomena by workers. Attendees may be encouraged to express their knowledge of the process, though not by actual human managers or institutions. If the respondents, intentionally or unintentionally, recognise any specific superiors or organisations, the investigator will instantly warn them that the investigator does not desire them to reveal that knowledge (Boynton, 2005). Therefore, when transcribing audiotapes, each specific employer or company identity will be substituted with pseudonyms or removed entirely. At the completion of the interview, the interviewer will guarantee the informants of the security of the interview details. Given the highly volatile nature of the situation for workers and the possibility that the investigator will address topics that might cause attendees to recall any traumatic memories, the investigator should specify the help or other communication resources that people may use in their field should they believe they need to do so during discussion. Upon data processing, all records of all types, such as written documents or audiotapes, should be preserved in a secure folder in the investigator's office and all digital information, for example NVivo files must be retained in password-secured machines (Fulton et al., 2013; Easterby-Smithe et al., 2015).

3.10 Conclusion

In this chapter of the thesis, the author outlined the methodology to the qualitative analysis approach—a grounded theoretical technique that aimed to develop a theory for participants of microfinance initiatives in Vietnam. The grounded theory approach was also adopted as it played a significant role in creating and constructing the theoretical background in a Vietnamese context. The background and creation, and the two streams of thinking, being Glaser's interpretation and Strauss and Corbin's interpretation, were both discussed. The author also focused and highlighted the later interpretation because it had been more common and more pro-constructivist instead of a positivist method. Other essential sections of qualitative study methodology have also been used and expanded in this thesis, such as theoretical sampling, target audience, investigator function, data collection protocols, data analysis strategies and related research ethics.

This chapter aimed to discuss the research design and methodology of this thesis. The constructivist philosophy and the methods of the study were described, and the numerous approaches for gathering data were clarified in detail and supported. This contained in-depth, semi-structured interviews and insights from participants. It was followed by the justification of the data analytical techniques and this part ended with an overview of the research challenges and difficulties. In the next section, the background of microfinance in Vietnam is provided

CHAPTER 4. MICROFINANCE IN VIETNAM

4.1. Introduction

The author has clarified in prior chapters why the traditional financial industry is typically hesitant to provide services such as savings and loans to underprivileged and small-income households. The author also discussed that government encouragement and actions on the financial markets, as well as appropriate policy development, could also be an alternative for supporting the poor. The approach to reducing poverty, aimed at low credit for the underprivileged, showed its weaknesses and shortcomings in approaching the poor. The alternative to financial systems, aimed at developing an economically financial intermediation for the vulnerable, could also not be a remedy at this point due to problems of financial autonomy and the absence of extremely poor people (Armendáriz & Morduch, 2010). A mixed approach might therefore be more suitable.

The Vietnam government has been interested in financing underprivileged citizens for decades. The 1990 economic reform turned the country into a business-oriented economy with considerable economic growth efforts (Roodman, 2012). Rural areas in Vietnam, however, appear to be influenced slightly, whereas the majority of the population comes from rural areas, which leads to a huge income and living differences between rural and urban areas. The national development plan underlined the significance of agriculture and rural development in this sense (Robinson, 2001). One of the major parts of this approach was ensuring access to financial and banking services for all of the poor people across the country.

Consequently, the Government of Vietnam tends to follow the strategy of reducing poverty in financial services for the poor. Governments and donors offer cheap loans to the poor through a network of government-owned banks, microfinance initiatives and non-profit organisations with the premise that credit increases poverty alleviation in rural areas (Guérin et al., 2013). Although the impact of loans on household poverty alleviation, which will be addressed in the next chapters, are optimistic but low, it is impractical for the regulated financial sector to touch the vulnerable. The primary reason is that the approach to eliminating poverty would not permit financial bodies to be financially autonomous (Karmakar, 2008). Other reasons may include a lack of government and donor assistance in improving financial infrastructure and information intermediation that does not allow financial institutions to reach poorer people at a lower cost, a lack of intermediaries that do not help financial institutions reach poorer people more effectively and efficiently, and, finally, and most importantly, a lack of understanding of how potential microfinance initiatives may influence participant capabilities (Morduch & Armendariz, 2005).

This chapter is intended to examine the existing microfinance situation in Vietnam in order to render potential proposals for a plan for sustainable microfinance. To this end, the author analysed the output of the microfinance initiatives with special interest regarding the position of the governments, as illustrated by policy system structures and the strengths and

limitations of financial institutions (Roy, 2010). The author usually believes that the financial systems of traditional financial organisations in Vietnam are not economically auto-sufficient. The author therefore proposes a solution to poverty reduction by subsidised credit and then implementing a hybrid strategy. The government and investors should engage more in society and knowledge intermediation, while financial firms should benefit from positive experiments of serving the vulnerable and pricing their programs so that they act as effective microfinance projects around the world. To consider how microfinance initiatives lead to enhanced user capacities and influences, the author will describe the background of these microfinance initiatives and highlight how the systems function and what their goals and philosophies are. The chapter provides a summary of the three separate microfinance schemes that are discussed in this thesis, including the Non-interest Loan Scheme (NLS), the Ambitious Women Program (AWP) and the Savings and Loan Circle (SLC). Every part of this chapter starts with details on the microfinance programs background and also includes a summary of its aims and principles, as well as details about how these services are organised and how they engage with the users. This is accompanied by a brief description of the members' backgrounds for each microfinance system.

The remainder of the chapter is as follows. After the introduction section, a literature review of the economic reform and microfinance background of Vietnam is conducted. The author also introduces the microfinance approaches such as unregulated, semi-formal and regulated. In addition, related technologies and resources for facilitating the development of microfinance in Vietnam are also presented. Finally, a brief review of three microfinance initiatives taking part in this thesis are also highlighted at the conclusion.

4.2. Economic Reform in Vietnam

Financial reform began in the late 1980s, particularly with Doi Moi in 1986. The Vietnamese government aimed to drive the country towards a market-oriented economy. Significant changes have been made in the concepts and the sense of economic development. As a result, the economic growth rate rose from an average of 5% in the 1980s to 8% in the 1990s. However, there are major disparities in city and rural growth. The latest national per capita growth is estimated at USD \$400, while the amount is estimated at USD \$90 in rural regions, accounting for 70% of the population. Rural growth was, thus, established as one of the main objectives of the strategic development plan of the Vietnamese Government (Sinha et al., 2009).

The first regional development effort started in 1998 with the introduction of a federal poverty reduction strategy to provide underprivileged and low-income households with a better life. One of the key elements of the government's poverty reduction method was to ensure access to loans and business and financial and banking services for poor rural people (Berger et al., 2006). The government stated that enhancing connection to microfinance was one of the critical meaningful ways to help low-income people in rural as well as city areas (Hossain et al., 2020).

Nevertheless, there was limited coverage of the structured banking industry in rural areas. A new report showed that only 25% of rural financial needs were fulfilled by the organised banking system (Gulli, 1998). The bulk of rural loans comes from unregulated lenders with several times higher interest rates than those paid by official banks. While certain rural financial needs were fulfilled by the unregulated economy, primarily moneylenders and revolving savings and financial associations, the high interest rates levied on low-income households were usurper and did not provide relief in the field of deposit mobilisation (Fernando, 2004). Therefore, it was necessary for households with low incomes to boost their living standards and increase financial intermediation, in particular to improve the availability of banking services in rural areas (Hulme & Arun, 2009).

Even now, the government has not released clear microfinance policies. The comprehensive plan for poverty elimination and reducing poverty (HEPR) is the key policy which focuses on the importance of microfinance and poverty reduction. The plan seeks to increase the total poverty level to 8% by 2010. Subsidised loans are considered one of the most important aspects in this strategy. To allow this strategy, the Vietnam Bank for the Poor was founded in 1997 with the key task of providing soft loans to poor families and supporting poverty alleviation programmes (Mersland & Strøm, 2014). The government also enhanced its position as government agent in the establishment of the Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development.

The financial industry was converted from a Soviet-style binary financial structure into a two-tier framework, in which the four major state-owned banks operated and performed significant positions in the banking sector, together with a central bank. The restructuring of the financial system often provided incentives for non-state banks and finance providers to compete in the credit industry (De Aghion et al., 2007). There is a variety of banks and financial institutions in rural areas, including the Agriculture and Rural Development Bank Vietnam, the Bad Bank Vietnam, Local Shareholding Banks, Peasant Loan Funds, Financial Cooperatives and certain other kinds of microfinancing. The Vietnam Bank has the highest branch network and has been the biggest force in this sector. The Vietnam Bank for the Poor was founded in 1995 and operates on the basis of the government's initiative to provide subsidised loans to poor households through a network of the Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Growth (Rhyne, 2001).

Interest rate regulation is one of the most significant fields of the restructuring of the banking system which impacts rural credit. The Banks and Financial Institutions Legislation defines and controls interest rates in deposits. The policy has increasingly liberalised interest rates since 1996. The base rate plus margins substituted the ceiling value. Nonetheless, banks and lending companies working on the rural sector found the prices too small to be financially viable (Neverson, 2013). When attempting to cover expenses and to make an income, the banks have little to no versatility. The restriction on the gap between credit rates and deposit levels of 0.2% and 0.6% a month for short-term lending and medium- and long-term lending, respectively, has also prevented rural financial institutions from issuing small loans to agricultural, marginal and disadvantaged families because of the high cost of small-scale transactions (Robinson, 2002).

A new analysis by multiple researchers shows that 55% may be categorised as lower or low-income households if we regard 12 million rural families. However, this distinction is derived from the requirements of the nation. If the World Bank's definitions are used, most agricultural households could be marginal and low-income residences. Statistics also revealed that agricultural households' living standards are marginally lower than non-borrowing families. This suggests that rural Vietnam's poorest households really need cash (Köhn, 2013).

The most obvious feature of Vietnamese rural lenders is the lack of adequate leverage, partially because of the former state ownership system. Just a limited percentage of residences have the capital that structured financial companies need. Such entities recognise as security only legitimate properties—the key asset being the government Land Use Certificate. However, by June 2001, no province of Vietnam had yet completed granting certificates of land usage to households (Webster & Fidler, 1996). In fact, any household may only provide one Land Use Permit granting approval for a single loan at a time. Resources that are used as leverage are generally of poor interest and are typically undervalued relative to the government's land price (Rehman et al., 2020).

The low level of rural lenders' education renders it challenging to grasp and complete the necessary paperwork and documentation, such as business plans and loan usage statements. Most rural lenders live well removed from the financial point of operation and travelling to the bank's branches is time consuming. Moreover, banking and finance advertising is both ineffective and too late. Rural debtors are still unwilling to complete loan applications and often rely on credit officers to support them. Credit officers are contacted on certain proposals for the planning of business strategies and loan use or merely to request payment forms (Ashta, 2010). However, loan agents are reduced in their amount and, for the Vietnam Bank of Agriculture and Rural Development, an officer has to negotiate frequently with several communities with thousands of lenders without a schedule of service.

The applicants expend a significant deal of time and resources on initial procedures, which often may not result in a request form being sent (Ledgerwood et al., 2013). Moreover, families tend to utilise funds for a range of reasons but only those applications are funded by structured financial firms. For certain low-income families who are essentially experiencing supported exclusion, the costs incurred such as certification charges, photos, application type, travel and employment losses borne by the banks are negligible (Bateman, 2011).

Therefore, the challenge of reaching poor rural households is relevant as, in general, poor households have difficulty entering the regulated financial system for a variety of purposes, but they still profit from exposure to financial services. Studies by Ali (2003), for example, show that the workload for rural families, which mostly depends on farming, such as rice and animal husbandry, decreases as they obtain exposure to financial resources and thus raise their household income (Sundaresan, 2009; Counts, 2008).

4.3. The Establishment of Microfinance in Vietnam

The Vietnamese rural financial industry is split into three main sectors: regulated, semi-formal and unregulated. In formal enterprises, the Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Growth, the Vietnam Bank for the Needy and the Local Shareholding Banks & Citizens Loan Funds are the major providers of microfinance services (Walt, 2012). The semiformal market is dominated by regional initiatives, social association (SO) micro-finance projects, and savings and loan schemes funded by non-governmental organisations and donors. In general, Vietnam's regulated and semi-formal financial sectors provide loans to rural households for limited rural growth and/or poverty reduction at cheaper rates (Puhazhendhi, 2013). Therefore, these industries effectively use their own requirements for the collection and evaluation of lenders qualified for loans. Yet, both the regulated and semi-formal systems either struggled to satisfy the immense need for financial services or refused to serve the vulnerable. The poor will, in these circumstances, depend on unregulated credit streams, primarily involving credit from revolving lending unions, money lenders, relatives, associates and merchants (Lamberte, 2006).

Until 1990, structured financial institutions, such as state-owned banks and loan cooperatives, only offered finance for state and efficient enterprises. International NGOs have not been willing to work in the country and social organisations have not received banking services. Therefore, individual farms and families did not receive structured credit (Swain, 2012). The Doi Moi program, which was initiated in 1986 accompanied by changes to the banking system and land use, changed the nature of the growth of rural financial services. The number of rural families with exposure to loans has dramatically improved (Fikkert & Mask, 2015).

The position of structured finance in the rural financial sector has been growing. In 2000 only 50% of total rural households and 42% of total rural LIHs had exposure to formal and/or semi-formal finance, however by 2005 the numbers were 70% and 61%. Most rural households and low-income households had links to the regulated financial system, of which the Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Growth and the Vietnam Bank for the Needy are the main sources (Schwittay, 2014). In 2005, a very small business customer, being 2% of rural households and 3% of low-income households, constituted a semi-formal source of financial services. However, a significant proportion of households still had no access to regulated or semi-formal loans (Arun & Hulme, 2009).

There are several explanations for having to borrow from the unregulated sector, which are critical for smooth consumption. A study conducted at the National Economics University Microfinance Resource Centre in 2010 found another explanation in that approximately 99% of the households examined took loans from the unregulated sector at higher interest rates owing to a limited exposure to the regulated market. Since rural households in Vietnam historically do not enjoy indebtedness to individuals, unregulated loans can be seen either as hardship loans or as a second option (Bateman, 2010). Nonetheless, families may be investing at very low interest rates from relatives or friends, but usually these are not binding and are thus temporary (Premchander et al., 2009).

4.3.1 Regulated Financial Schemes

The four regulated establishments, being the Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development, the Vietnam Bank for the Poor and the People's Credit Funds and Rural Shareholding Bank, offered regulated financial and banking services for rural families and LIHs. Most loans from these organisations are provided on a subsidy basis for specific purposes, such as regional development or reducing poverty. In other words, the Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development is the tool for the government to take its approach to poverty reduction: the state-owned bank and the largest financial entity in Vietnam that offers financial services in rural areas through a nationwide network (Nair & Tankha, 2013). The structured financial sector has the largest share (Tijani, et al. 2020). The Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development's market clientele includes a mix of rural households and LIHs. This accounted for 70% of remote families and 69% of LIHs with access to structured financial services in 2000. Such estimates were respectively 68% and 70% in 2002. These statistics indicate that the Vietnam Bank is the main participant in the cycle of outreach and the government's rural growth and poverty reduction policy (Ashta & Bush, 2009).

Vietnam Bank for the Poor

In fact, the structural "fusion" of the Vietnam Bank for the Poor was founded in all provinces in the Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development branch network. Vietnam's Weak Bank had no ambitions to develop its own network until 2010 (Huis et al., 2019). It has been turned into a 'private fund' and focused primarily on the Vietnam Fund for the Poor (Dichter & Harper, 2007). One of the bank's tasks was to distribute credit with government support to disadvantaged households. The bank was also expected to collaborate with loan and deposit programs run by NGOs and social microfinance initiatives. With major government support, VBP increased its market share in rural households with access to the regulated sector to 35% in 2010. It is worth noting that most Vietnam Banks are poor rural families with small customers (Ledgerwood & White, 2006). This suggests that the Vietnam Bank is the key player in the upcoming plan to progress the poorer families for the affluent or policy system.

The People's Credit Fund

The People's Credit Fund is a small collaborative and social economic organisation which is community owned, operated and managed by shareholders from the municipality in which it is located. People's social capital funds play an important role of intermediation; increasing access to financial resources for remote lenders and savers, stressing conservation and capital management (Huis et al., 2019). A People's Credit Fund provides a safe and easy space for the communes to save their money, offers a source of credit to families who are no longer eligible to join the Vietnam Bank for the Poor, creates loans for local businesses and jobs, helps displace community lenders who charge their loans at very high rates, and can quickly lend

household income funds (Puhazhendhi & Satyasai, 2000). However, the network of the People's Credit Fund plays a small role in remote capital markets.

Rural Shareholding Bank

The Rural Shareholding Bank was the result of the reorganisation or combination of the Rural Credit Cooperatives in which the government is 12% interest, sometimes referred to as Credit Cooperatives (Huis et al., 2019). The key benefit of these institutions is that their financing is easy with credit officers who depend on their experience and strong relations with many families or associates. Credit officials also assist borrowers in obtaining the required paperwork. The efficiency and low cost of this method comes from the dual positions of the majority of the workers as professional employees and shareholders. However, the Rural Shareholding Bank's market share is very small (Schmidt et al., 2016).

4.3.2 Providers of Semi-Formal Financial Services

Semi-formal microfinance initiatives are primarily given by three categories, including national programs, social financial services and foreign NGO loans and investment schemes.

The National Program

In essence, regional services are supported by the government budgets and have different goals. In addition, several national programs include a credit component in their activities that is used to endorse the pre-set goals. Examples of core initiatives such as job creation, greening bare hill, and the Regional Exclusion and Poverty Reduction Initiative can be identified (Kalpana, 2016). Financial services such as credit are usually supported instead of driven by poor rural family demand (Ohanyan, 2008).

Microfinance Scheme Offered by Social Organisations

The charitable organisation's primary interest is the economic prosperity of its participants. This purpose is not only fulfilled by credit but also serves as a stimulus for other activities. The two specific approaches of social organisations to funding activities include: (i) holding and handling members' deposits and grants from contributors such as foreign NGOs; and (ii) supporting the Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Growth, Vietnam Banco for the Disadvantaged or supplying financing vehicles (Zeller & Meyer, 2002; Nghiem, 2005). Credit services are provided by social enterprises, such as the Vietnam Farmer's Union which is very much valued as it can be specifically channelled to potential grassroots beneficiaries (Khoi & Gan, 2017). It also has more direct and closer contact with clients than a regulated credit institution because it is community-based (Bhatnagar, 2008). For this reason, several foreign NGOs, like the Vietnam Bank for the Needy, have opted for collaboration with social organisations in their growth programmes (Christabell, 2009; Zhao & Han, 2020).

International NGOs

Many foreign NGOs in Vietnam have incorporated their microfinance systems combined with other operations for different purposes (Nghiem & Laurenceson, 2006). Microfinance programs combined with other projects will leverage area advantages that can piggy-back microfinance on certain business structures, such as irrigation collectives, or use supplements in household development and enhanced welfare systems (Quinones & Remenyi, 2014). Therefore, several NGOs consider microfinance as a means to an end and not to the source. Credit and investment schemes from NGOs, however, are typically limited and cover relatively few rural families (Johnson & Rogaly, 1997).

4.3.3 Unregulated Microfinance Services

Families, friends, colleagues, merchants, non-registered private borrowers and conventional rural loan classes are the origins of unregulated microfinance in Vietnam.

Moneylenders: The moneylender's loan on a variety of terms to each client, whether temporary or regularly. In rural regions, they are typically the strongest and have a wide pool of capital or commodities. It is estimated that two or three irreversible and five to ten temporary private moneylenders exist in every village. The hidden nature of the activity means that there is no data about the number of people who use moneylenders. A primary characteristic of moneylenders is the perception of a cooperative attitude to lending and bargaining at a premium cost of minimum fees of around 5% a month (Gallaway, 2007). The company is versatile but has a large cost of potential (Nghiem et al., 2012).

Ho: This term means family or friendship and comes from northern Vietnam. This is a typical community loan party run by locals. Each party consists of approximately ten to twenty-five leaders, who have the same occupations such as farmers groups, merchants' groups and war veteran groups (Nghiem & Laurenceson, 2005). Each group acts as a personal institution which has no connection with other groups or regulated organisations. Members nominate a party representative to receive deposits and to preserve documents. Leaders invest funds to finance the allocation of each party leader (Duong & Nghiem, 2014) and either cash, paddy or gold can be classed as savings (Mersland & Strøm, 2014). The sum of monthly cash savings relies on the company arrangement and the key distinction with this scheme is that the Ho is not an organisation in Vietnam but individual independent credit classes (King, 2008).

Phuong: This does not tend to involve owing loan interest. Every investment needs regular savings and is entitled to a loan free of interest once a credit period is completed. Minority communities in mountain areas, where interest-bearing lending is not a cooperative means of helping each other, prefer this strategy (Cornelis & Ruben, 2008). The classes are smaller than in the Ho and range from seven to ten. This system can be seen as a rotating group of savings and loans (Shakya & Rankin, 2008).

Hui: Hui's name comes from southern Vietnam. The Hui work in the north like a Ho. Many leaders sadly lent as much as possible by providing shockingly high interest rates (10-15% a

month) (Nguyen, 2007). The loans were used to invest for speculative purposes in land, trade or assets. These projects were extremely productive during the 1990–2000 boom. Nonetheless, it ended as certain participants only lent from one party to compensate the other in lieu of all loans being offset by potential returns. Many Hui crashed (VOHUI) because lenders lacked their repayment power. Hui is thus now known as a “cheating loan” in Vietnam (Nghiem et al., 2007).

Borrowing from Relatives: This form of lending is typically interest free with adjustable terms. The conditions of the loan rely on lenders’ partnerships and the existence of external streams of revenue (Bui, 2014). The vulnerable are not inclined to lend from families or acquaintances due to the current social repercussions. Myth suggests that bad acquaintances or weak family members will be supported by giving up resources instead of borrowing it from successful partnerships (Nguyen & Hollister, 2012).

Figure 4.1. Financial system in Vietnam (Source: author)

4.4. Other Perspectives of Vietnam Microfinance

4.4.1 Policy Context

Although the Vietnamese government has adopted the path of microfinance to reduce poverty, the main concern is that the state has not yet articulated any concrete microfinance policy or policy plan. Banking laws and the legal frameworks do not include many forms of microfinance institutions in the microfinance industry. Most structured microfinance institutions currently run under a common legal structure for all banks and credit institutions though acknowledging that the microfinance field requires legality needs to be strictly addressed (Khoi & Gan, 2017). Semi-formal microfinance bodies, particularly international NGOs and social institutions, which can use the protocols in microfinance, tend to be excluded from the real provision of financial services.

The lack of a clear microfinance policy and plan could result in a reduction in both demand and scope. Experiences from states in the region, such as Indonesia, Thailand and the Philippines, where financial markets were liberalised, microfinance was established and encouraged to some degree, which is a good lesson for consideration. In the mid-1980s, for example, the Philippine government took its first step towards financial liberalisation, opening the banking industry to more competition. The central bank discarded its conservative bank entry and strategy of branching and welcomed new players to join the industry (Abeysekera et al., 2014). More specifically, in 2001, the Philippines introduced the national policy on microfinance, including in the revised general banking legislation a separate microfinance strategy. As a consequence of this policy environment, the development of microfinance networks with the participation of all types of microfinance institutions has been facilitated. The government's commitment to provide priority and cheap loans in rural poor households has failed to realise the need for microfinance institutions to become more self-sufficient, particularly in the regulated sector, leading the microfinance industry (Bateman, 2011). The increased costs of lending to the vulnerable cannot be borne by the majority of official microfinance institutions and they therefore cannot attain financial viability (Chinomona, 2013). For example, the average gap between input and output levels for 2010 is 1% per month in the Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Growth, as estimated by experts in microfinance (Khoi & Gan, 2017). As a consequence, most official MFIs are unable to offer microfinance programs unless they are funded by foreign development organisations like the World Bank and the Asian Development Bank (Buera, et al., 2021).

The disparity in interest rate policies and their subsequent efficiency consequences can be seen in the case of Indonesia, where there is no interest rate limit, such as the Bank Rakyat Indonesia. From around 1985, the legalisation on interest rates has enabled Bank Rakyat Indonesia to establish its own prices on loans and savings. Bank Rakyat Indonesia utilises its loans at a flat rate of 2.5% per month, based on initial loan amount.

4.4.2 Loan Methods

As seen in the previous section, community lending is the largest growing loan technology in Vietnam. However, this technology differs from the popular model in that the key advantages of community loans in Vietnam include: (I) groups are typically formed by social institutions and certified by the Local People's Committee, ensuring community survival and legalisation; and (ii) because loan applications are approved by the Local People's Committee it helps minimise the persistent danger raised by the problem.

In contrasting community loans in the Agriculture and Rural Development Bank of Vietnam in comparison to the popular Grameen Bank identifying the drawbacks of a loan community is important. Due to group set-up requirements through social organisations and permission from the Local People's Committee, many debtors ignored microfinance services. This also improved the major issue of administrative procedures which essentially takes time and results in high borrowers' non-financial costs. The collateral provision does not seem to be applicable to microfinance lenders, however, the position of mutual responsibility, which can serve as collateral, is commonly overlooked and is the main explanatory factor of community lending performance. Indeed, the credit officers work with group members directly.

4.5. Microfinance Initiatives in Vietnam

This section outlines the legitimate of microfinance in Vietnam with the aim to review the current relevant regulatory as well as exploring the current development in the adaptation of microfinance initiatives in Vietnam.

4.5.1 Regulated Sector

State-owned organisations, for example the Vietnam Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development and the Vietnam Bank for the Needy, are the most structured microfinance entities in Vietnam. The key strengths of these organisations are that they have a strong regional network with good ties to the Local People's Committee and are a significant microfinance participant in Vietnam, a conduit for local knowledge and a skilled banking business, compared with other microfinance organizations (Ngo & Wahhaj, 2012). This explains why the biggest proportion of microfinance in Vietnam is structured microfinance and also has better performance. However, in the case of the Vietnam Bank of Agriculture and Rural Growth or the Vietnam Bank for the Needy, the network of structured microfinance institutions is only expanding to the district level and not to the level of the villages and communes that is best seen as representing the lower-income families (Nghiem & Laurenceson, 2006).

The value of the branch network extension is learned from the case of Rakyat Bank in Indonesia which defines the micro-banking division, known as the Rakyat Indonesia Banking Unit System, and provides a grassroots range of savings and credit items. With 400 units at the grassroots level, Bank Rakyat's extended banking system is one of its greatest strengths. Each Rakyat Unit acts as a separate profit centre with its own profit and loss balance sheets (Nghiem et al., 2012). This principle is fundamental to Rakyat Banking Indonesia's structure which helps it to introduce incentive programs dependent on its success and enables monitoring tools to be introduced (Bateman, 2012). The Micro Banking Division was also the most successful one and also funded the bank's other activities.

While Bank Rakyat Indonesia's expanded network performance is a crucial lesson to be learnt, a further limitation of the official microfinance agencies in Vietnam is that they rely heavily on their partnerships with others, such as Social Organisations and the Local People's Committee that raise borrowers' administrative expenses. While the importance of this aspect is also that it reduces lenders' screening expenses, it represents the influence of the central planning system. Obviously, the complex structure of the loan system raises non-financial risks which is prone to be people's destructive behaviour (Nghiem et al., 2012).

4.5.2 Semi-Formal and Unregulated Sectors

Although they have no national network and no skilled microfinance relative to the controlled community, semi- and unregulated microfinances have the benefit of concentrating on the vulnerable as target customers (Lin et al., 2014). In addition, semi-formal organisations, including foreign NGOs, typically hold perspectives from abroad and maintain best general practices from the microfinance industry (Huis et al., 2019). Most research has shown that NGOs adopt the best microfinance method, in particular in community lending and social intermediation.

However, the key drawback of these parties is that financial institutions are exempt from the legislative system, this is clearly the case, for example, in the informal market (Huis et al., 2019). Financial infrastructure cannot be given as the key operation for semi structured microfinance but rather in combination with other operations. This varies from other countries like the Philippines or Indonesia, which promotes competitiveness and eliminates barriers to financial markets (Lin et al., 2014). In other terms, Vietnam's semi-formal microfinance organisations are not able to function successfully as financial institutions.

The other drawback is the large costs involved. It's because they do not have their own networks for semi-formal microloans and several semi-formal microfinance organisations are focused on subsidised funding streams. For informal microfinanciers, lenders usually demand very large costs to address asymmetric knowledge problems.

4.5.3. Accessibility

The ability to expand relies on self-financial adequacy and auto-financial adequacy on the ability to charge stable interest rates covering all required expenses (Lin et al., 2014). Rural Vietnam has the following rules regulating the structured financial institutions offering LIH financial services: the Law on Cooperatives, the Law on the State Bank of Vietnam and the Law on Financial Institutions. The interest rate formula is the apparent constraint in the current context of the legal framework and regulation for institutional microfinance initiatives is to pay a sustainable rate (Quach & Mullineux, 2007).

Whilst the government, through the State Bank of Vietnam, has modified its interest rate strategy through moving from the loan rate limit to a base interest rate legislation, it remains committed to providing prior or cheap loans to poor rural families and under government direction through structured microfinance bodies (Nguyen, 2010). As a consequence, the existing microfinance organisations are seriously limited to competitiveness and self-sufficiency (Tu & Minh, 2017). Therefore, the ability to expand coverage and maintain financial security requires the ability to find new ways to deliver financial services at cheaper costs (Nghiem et al., 2010).

On the other hand, there are semi-formal structures. With the exception of the national loan schemes, semi-formal programs like those introduced by social organisations and NGOs are not regulated by bank regulation and are capable of setting interest rates covering operating costs. Vietnam Women's Unions and the Vietnam Farmer's Unions have been the most active of the various social groups and the government programs engaged in microfinance operations (Lin et al., 2014). The Vietnam Women's Unions have issued loans to households through its own savings and lending programs, as well as helping members obtain lending at the Vietnam Bank of Agriculture and Rural Development. The Union of Farmers in Vietnam is believed to have far less in terms of numbers and still has a significant loan extension (McCarty, 2001).

The principal constraint on growth and stabilisation of semi-formal microfinance entities is that they are not deemed to be financial organisations, in order to prevent actual involvement in securitised loans, such as deposit stabilisation. Furthermore, the released banking legislation made it mandatory that all conditions be complied with in order to carry out banking activities (McCarty, 2001). Consequently, they cannot extend their operations to a great degree and, in most instances, are supported by public funding or investor money (Le, 2017). This suggests that semi-formal systems are not viable and cannot significantly increase their ability to communicate if banking laws are not modified.

4.6. Future of Microfinance in Vietnam

4.6.1. Potential of Microfinance in Vietnam

The foregoing literature review indicates that the traditional financial sector has been the leader in Vietnam's microfinance markets and that microfinance in Vietnam in general is not quite scalable. Some large improvements are required to achieve sustainable microfinance, leading to poverty reduction and economic growth (Bulte et al., 2017). These adjustments will concentrate on policies, corporate plans, lending activities, and the efficiency of microfinance institutions. The greatest limitation that regulates both of these problems is microfinance awareness (Khoi & Gan, 2017). The key question will then be what is the best path to microfinance in Vietnam but how will this method be understood?

This study suggests that Vietnam could be more suitable for the mixed approach at this time. The biggest issue is the compromise between financial and social priorities because, obviously, it is not easy to see where the compromise will be (Putzeys, 2002). However, it should be understood that the new microfinance systems are not ideal for stable microfinance and that subsidised microfinance permanently decreased the financial viability of microfinance initiatives (Kono, 2006). Therefore, the suggestion is based on the view that improvements should be taken in order to phase out subsidies and that the government should, instead, provide more aid for the development of a sound microfinance financial system and investment in social and information intermediation (Le Tam, 2011).

Previous studies show that microfinance with an approach to poverty reduction that relies on reducing poverty by subsidised loan schemes cannot sustainably enter the poor household. The use of a pure approach to financial systems, which stresses financial resilience may also contribute to restricted microfinance growth, such as the alienation of the underprivileged. It is therefore proposed that a mixed micro-finance approach could be a great option and that the Vietnamese governments and participating microfinance institutions should change their view to achieving sustainable microfinancing (McCarty, 2001). According to this strategy, microfinance institutions will be forced to follow financial systems approaches to, for example, become business microfinance institutions, while government and donor supports serve to build a sound financial and informational infrastructure and foster social intermediation for the poorer households.

It is not agreed, however, that shifting microfinance expectations in general is a simple idea and it is a delicate process. The first is to improve the overall financial system and establish knowledge intermediation (Le, 2017). The Asian Development Bank has advised that microfinance institutions can only permanently develop and broaden their reach of activities and coverage if they operate within suitable financial systems, such as information systems and educational facilities (Nghiem et al., 2006). The regulatory and supervisory system, including the quality of self-regulation and the efficiency of microfinance institutions, should therefore be set up to promote sound development and improve the ability of microfinance institutions to access public funds and to succeed. Legal barriers must be eliminated that preclude banks from entering into business relations with informal or semi-formal organisations, like society-based agencies or self-help groups (Chen & Schreiner, 2009).

Secondly, the pledge to give poor families cheap credit should be withdrawn. The survey found that the disadvantaged are able to pay higher rates. The Rakyat Bank Indonesia is a really clear illustration of how microfinance organisations will profit by expanding their scope (Duy et al., 2012). Therefore, a reform in the policy on microfinance interest rates should be made. The new dedication to provide cheap loans to low households has prohibited traditional microfinance organisations from paying all expenses including capital market expenses, running costs, unemployment, loan defaults and fair income (Johnson, 1996; Oosterhoff et al., 2008). The government could loosen this pledge by enabling the traditional microfinance institutions to decide their own interest rates for loans to poor families, as regular trade financial institutions do (Wijesiri & Meoli, 2015).

Thirdly, a regulatory structure should be developed to understand the position of the various forms of microfinance institutions, in particular the non-formal microfinance institutions. The lack of a clear regulatory system hindered microfinance organisations from delivering their programs properly and effectively (Nghiem, 2009). Many long-term microfinance entities have a policy defining the financial practices they require. In fact, the legal position of the “borrowing party” is not laid out in the statute. Microfinance entities are also not permitted to lend to individuals as a legal body by communities (Hisaki, 2006). The government should immediately issue specific microfinance exclusive regulations, create a clear legislative system for the activity of microfinance institutions and, because the Land Use Certificate is one of the most widely used collaterals for microfinance, it should encourage the land use certificate mechanism vigorously such that further low-income households may use land-use certificates (Vietnam Microfinance Working Group, 2014).

Therefore, microfinance industries would be efficient as in ordinary economies. As shown in the section above, the Philippines promoted competition and created a fair field for financial institutions in the banking industry (Coleman, 2003). The government will also promote competitiveness to boost the level of distribution in the provision of rural financial services. More semi-formal savings and credit programs can become loan collectives by streamlining enrolment and lowering capital requirements (Adam, 2001; Khoi & Gan, 2017).

Fifth, sustainability is also critical for expanding the reach of the primary goal of reducing poverty. Policy funding for enterprise advancement to maintain sustainability requires: (i) ownership and regulation; (ii) a variety of goods and services; (iii) database infrastructure, accounting policies and practices; (iv) consistency and growth portfolio control; (v) transaction cost mitigation processes and procedures and financial technology; and (vi) facility for instruction. This is critical for Vietnam as the residual elements of the central planning system remain in the country (Tahir & Tahir, 2013; Nguyen et al., 2014).

In conclusion, microfinance programs cannot become successful without social intervention or intermediation as an instrument for reducing poverty and hunger

reduction or as a financial intermediary. It's often seen as a safer alternative to subsidised microfinance as it offers the poor "a path, not a line". The government will, however, consider ways and means to develop capacity in rural households in general and in low-income households in particular. Governmental organisations and extension programs in different government ministries are required which would allow them to strengthen their activities with greater financial help from the government (Ayayi, 2012). Experiences from other countries have received comprehensive and frequent training for both workers and lenders in microfinance institutions and SME organisations, for example, must be developed within the first period of time (Kono, 2006).

4.6.2. Microfinance and Related Businesses

Microfinance institutions must grow into commercial microfinance institutions in attempt to supply financial services for the poor on a permanent basis. Change in marketing requires growing MFI to implement the concepts of commercial finance in microfinance at first. Currently, the most formal microfinance institutions provide the poor with subsidised financial services that prevent them from self-sufficiency (Bassem, 2008). The first move would then be to offer financial resources in such a manner that all running expenses are protected. Lessons can be learnt from the progress of NGOs but that relies strongly on the international climate, in particular financial assets (McCarty, 2001; Bao, Quoc & Tsai, 2014; Huis et al., 2019).

The strength of the formal microfinance institutions is a wide national network of branches, but it covers only districts and should thus be further developed (Kono, 2006). To ensure sustainable access and development it is necessary to extend the branch networks at municipal and village level, to form a village and communal banking network, as was learnt from the Rakyat Bank Indonesia and the original success of the Vietnam Bank of Agriculture and Rural Development's mobile banking model. In addition, collaboration or cooperation with social agencies, as required in a community loan environment and in the mobile banking network, must be preserved and improved (Dufhues et al., 2003).

Because of the persistent high fixed transaction costs in microfinance, microfinancing specialisation strategies could be the solution to increase profitability. Microfinance organisations will also be conscious of the need for microfinance programs to be strengthened and innovated (Lensink & Pham, 2012). In addition, strategies should be used that emphasise community development as they are more adapted to the poor, particularly in rural areas. Social intermediation may also be carried out through government and donor funding through microfinance organisations, but should be differentiated from financial intermediation, in order for low-income households to take advantage of financial services (Nghiem et al., 2006).

4.6.3. Microfinance Technologies

It is known that there is currently no difference between personal loans and community loans in Vietnam. The crucial thing, however, is to find an effective and efficient way of extending access to the poor. In this context, collaboration with the Local People's Committee and the Social Organisations is an ideal way to leverage local information regarding prospective lenders, but the MFIs will ensure that the needless non-financial cost of this mechanism is removed (Christopher & Gilbert, 2017). Cooperation with NGOs may also be a successful option as they can take advantage of the large network of structured financial systems and the NGOs' familiarity with disadvantaged households (Shakya, 2006).

With respect to group loan technology, it was apparent that the group loan approach should be used to strengthen the position of joint responsibility in order to profit from efficiencies and the elimination of risk, in line with the world's best practices of group lending worldwide (Seibel, 1996). It ensures that microfinance institutions profit from the community lending in Vietnam in two ways: it takes advantage of the knowledge on potential lenders at lower cost, and guarantees peer search, peer surveillance and peer pressure (Phan et al., 2014).

Microfinance institutions should also learn through experience that the standard loan approach of prior limited deposits or compensatory balances can be useful (Wijesiri et al., 2015). This approach becomes particularly useful when an automated loan insurance coverage process is implemented. Studies in national lending to the needy, such as through NGO programs, indicates that the bad pay-out is higher at the end than in the maximum lump amount (Khoi & Gan, 2017). Pay rates are usually very high with a payment plan. It is to be remembered, however, that the opportunity to secure larger loans in the coming periods may contribute to a moral hazard issue if failing lenders borrow "hot money", pay it back and obtain larger loans that will compensate for a "hot money" loan to help others. This can cause a severe delinquency problem (Kono, 2006).

In tandem with the system of financing, creativity in mobilisation saving strategies guarantees the other aspect of competitive microfinance (Bui Thanh et al., 2018). Benefits for policymakers, including many incentives, has proven quite productive and should be taken into account in the savings in many developed countries. They should be designed to encourage deposits on demand and long-term deposits. Mobilising savings efforts must be favoured by publicly focusing on easy accessibility, simplification, the security of stored sums, easy withdrawal if necessary and lotto (Haq et al., 2008).

4.6.4. Resources

Unless there are enhanced capabilities of microfinance institutions, sustainable microfinance cannot be achieved (Khoi & Gan, 2017). The capacity's key advantage is the human capital, the expertise and the experience of microfinance lenders. Credit and management officials should be aware of microfinance, of best international business and microfinance practices in general, and of the microfinance borrowers' ability to

save, borrow and pay back properly (Lin et al., 2014). Factual evidence and real-life knowledge will be exchanged such that the loss of confidence in coping with the low-income households may be modified.

The MFIs will also have a focus in creating a knowledge infrastructure that not only allows microfinance organisations to function effectively at an organisational level but also gives stakeholders and external advisors a greater trust and understanding (Quach et al., 2005). More realistic and relevant guidelines can be provided and the sustainable growth of microfinance organisations can be improved with greater accountability. State grants and sponsors may assist with these tools.

4.7. Conclusion

The performance of microfinance in Vietnam has been fully reviewed in this chapter. It has been stressed that the Vietnamese Government should consider microfinance to be important for the approach of reducing poverty and increasing economic development. The performance evaluation shows that whilst microfinance has achieved considerable progress in reaching the vulnerable, it has not been sustainable. The lack of a legal structure which prevents formal microfinance organisations from participating financially and semi-formally in microfinance is the principal constraint of sustainable microfinance. Other constraints include loan technologies, which do not apply to best practices in the world of microfinance, and the limited institutional network that cannot reach the poor at the grassroots level.

It is recommended that a mixed strategy in delivering financial services to the vulnerable be addressed to achieve sustainable microfinance. The government and donors will abolish all direct subsidies to financial services but then promote the creation of a stable financial system and innovation in social and knowledge intermediation. In particular, supporting organisations such as the credit rating agencies, credit ratings and credit offices, which are currently unavailable, can be set up by the government and donors which will lead to better infrastructure, healthcare and school programs and tend to expand disadvantaged people's capacities to obtain access to utilise the financial resources.

Regarding the background of microfinance initiatives participating in this thesis, the way the numerous microfinance initiatives operated and worked was worth understanding. It was particularly important to consider the complexities of the programs, which led to the different effects on the attendees. The SLC and the AWP had a financial and a social element, whereas the NLS was mostly political. The NLS and AWP have been handled and operated by their respective organisations and members have made no commitment to system operations decisions. The SLC, on the other hand, offered a great deal of flexibility for program members. The next section – chapter 5 provides the findings regarding financial influences of microfinance initiatives

CHAPTER 5. FINANCIAL INFLUENCES

5.1. Introduction

This thesis aimed to assess the impact of microfinance initiatives on user capability. For this reason, it became important to consider the effects of microfinance programs on participants and also explain how such influences were facilitated by microfinance programs. It has been observed that microfinance projects have a broad variety of consequences which can be divided into three categories: financial impacts, social aspect impacts and capability impacts. This chapter explores the implications on the financial aspects, Chapter 7 discusses the influence on the social aspect, and Chapter 8 analyses the influence on the capabilities of participants. Every part is accompanied by an overview of the individual elements of the services that facilitate the effect on the lives of the participants.

The most significant goal of microfinance initiatives is to improve user financial stability (Churchill & Frankiewicz, 2006). Regarding the financial implications of microfinance programs, participants often spoke about the impacts of these initiatives on their families and financial situations. This also included an analysis of the effect of the services on the financial aspects of the lives of the individuals. This chapter explores the effect of the services on the social facets of human lives. The participants addressed five main aspects that influenced their finances, including: (i) saving behaviours, (ii) financial knowledge, (iii) financial stability, (iv) financial difficulties, and (v) enhanced business participation.

5.2. Saving Behaviour

The growth of saving behaviours is an effective way to acquire savings (Rhyne & Otero, 2006). A total of five respondents claimed explicitly that their savings engagement was enhanced by the microfinance system they were a part of. While the NLS offered a non-interest loan instead of a saving service, participants frequently viewed it as an option for investing and often related it to saving.

Two members in the AWP claimed the plan would save them and that it was the company experience that supported her. Interviewee A2 is a mother of three dependent children and she said she learnt to save through the workshops and seminars given throughout the project. She offered explanations of realistic suggestions that helped in saving her. Interviewee A2 said that she mentioned all the items she wanted and would not purchase needless products until she went shopping:

“What I suppose [is] in this family home you need anything ... you're [making] ... a guide for shopping can help and you're not lost. When you want

something else to buy or ... [when] I'm asked by my husband ... I'll get the list or I'm lost and would like to buy it ...”

She said she found that she could “*spare some cash*” when she started compiling her lists. But “*that was a major opening of the eye*”. She was a client who spoke specifically about how the company schooling benefited her. Another AWP client claimed that once the AWP employee created a savings account for her, the plan had allowed her to save more money. She stated that she continued placing tiny amounts of money back in the banking account to support the education of her children after the account was opened.

Other participants spoke about savings that mostly came from the SLC scheme. In addition, it should be noted that all SLC respondents had to save while only five participants spoke explicitly about saving. Those who were a part of the formed SLC, notably from the beginning, said that they had succeeded in saving a great deal of money since they joined this microfinance initiative, which had been almost five years ago.

Interviewee S8, a single mum, claimed that she had received great benefits from the SLC network. It helped her savings account but she also actually began two other investment accounts, including an “*emergency account*” which was directly linked with her own private savings account and an “*education savings account*” to deal with payments required by the educational services of her children.

“Because I have some money now, I am not as stressed or nervous. So, I think further about the future for me, our family and my children. I decide to do some investment, for instance, save money for emergency moments, or when I need to take care of relatives and save money for my child by investing in education for them, give them a bright future ... I did make several intelligent choices because I did not follow the credit route.”

She had sufficient investments and invested beyond the SLC networks, but S8 claimed her children had gained as well. She was spending for their lives and futures, and she kept saving for the items she would like to purchase. While her children qualified for a credit card, she opted not to get one but rather saved for the items that she needed to buy. She clarified that it made her save, attributing the party to the general sense of duty she thought: “*I think I know I have an obligation of spending these [savings] and I will raise money. If it were just me, I would definitely*”. She decided to spend it. “*I want some nice shirts. I assume I should only go out and purchase those.*” She was willing to express what kept her money in the investments as well as the loans circle:

“I just believe that anything is related between me, because while it's not that anyone in the community is going to say something less about me, because I don't make the pledge, I know that has a good sense of obligation towards me.”

An additional member of the existing savings and loans group, S2, said he had tried to save but could not. They spoke about some of the challenges they encountered when he borrowed before joining the web of savings and credit.

“Even if I played ... I think I had a comparatively better salary than what I'm doing now, but I never saved it ever. I never had enough money to raise a lot so still there were a number of hurdles ... [for example] inspiration. We are all sorts of unique challenges, I suppose. Motivation, I guess it got in the way of my desire for consumer products.”

These findings confirm previous results from a savings survey from minimal-income households in the United Kingdom, which showed that people generally favoured the safest actions, especially when their financial situations required effort, and listed this as one of the saving barriers. Interviewee S2 admitted that she lacked ambition and a lack of self-control—which is considered as her main challenge—and she speaks about what has affected his conduct.

“However, I start blaming that I only had little motivation, not myself as I agree that, indeed, the idea of society is that we can get this all, get it easy and had all these material things. This is the way you were judged, although, I would actually not really understand it, I know that this is an intrinsic decision that I felt. That I always pick myself up, however, I still so bad, while I don't believe I ought to, when I don't have a car that looks as good as everyone else's.”

The comments of S2 implied that a certain degree of ‘content’ acceptance has to be reached to believe that they are part of the mainstream culture. Significant discussions have taken place that the possession and its value is now seen as the status symbol, such as how a person feels that has a huge, flat-screen television. Although social equality interventions are more systemic and multi-layered instead of just economic engagement, this is not occurring in many situations. The social integration debate also refuses to provide fair representation in the population, including socioeconomic metrics, such as sources in work and demand. In addition, the social equality debate often emphasises ideas which are mainly included in people’s business, while integrating steps to analyse the degree to which an individual participates in society and political activities. The view of S2 relates to societal expectations, to ‘belong’ on the grounds of finance instead of just social perspectives.

What affects S2’s desire to save money is to be part of a social system which has its base not on products and services demand but rather on people’s daily saving practices. Whether these experiences may have impacted the performance of the NLS respondents is uncertain. Ironically enough, however, many NLS participants

indicated in a similar way that people sometimes think about preserving exposure to a non-interest loan.

The NLS members also claimed it was impossible to save. Participant N1, an NLS customer, aged 47, father of one child, said he could not save. He did not perceive himself to be somebody who should invest and claimed he would find it impossible to raise funds over a prolonged period of time. He said he viewed the line of credit as a diversified way of investing, since he would not have bought the new household element otherwise.

“The debts are ... different and if I can't afford it, I cannot manage to earn. You take \$30, that's not going to last me for long. I'm not going to find anything to buy. But if I need something for my home, I'll head to the store to get anything I don't have, and it's the safest option so I can't spare. I'm happy to pay back, but nobody's going to provide you credit in these days, because I'm retired.”

He may consider a loan as the way to save.

“That's far easier because I can't save and it's about investing and offering money, rather than placing \$30 every two weeks, which I spend on myself. By this approach I give them \$30, and I and they are happy together.”

This is reinforced in the study of Swanson (2008), which highlighted that one of the reasons that citizens did not invest was their view of themselves as spenders instead of savers. Although the NLS plan is primarily about the availability of non-interest loans, it was treated more as savings from the recipients' perspective. Although participants are already indebted to a lender and to a bond that requires to be repaid, free of interest, they nevertheless viewed that as a victory and compared it to investment. Sometimes, if anyone invested for anything, they saw this as a chance to buy products and services or as an additional financial protection, as we have seen. The NLS plan encourages borrowers to accept a fresh loan directly after a loan has been taken out, which they use as an option to buy something more, for their next deposit, in the very same manner as investments. In reality, both interviewees talked about what they would pick up if the current loan was paid off. Although NLS participants didn't invest, they looked at the loans as individuals who save money. It is worth noting that this cannot also be treated as an effect on savings for NLS respondents as it does not conserve behaviour.

Table 6.1 outlines the features of microfinance services that facilitates behavioural saving. This indicates that the main aspects of the AWP and what savings and credit loops have in common to encourage savings behaviour, is help. Certain characteristics which contribute to savings and loans would include a sense of identity, a sense of share of obligation and a habit of forced savings. Education was also essential for the AWP participants.

Micro-finance Initiatives	Characteristics
Ambitious Women Program (AWP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial Education • Support from a local society worker, including opening bank account
Savings and Loan Circles (SLC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enable saving • Sense of shared responsibility • Support network • Sense of belonging that is founded in saving
No-interest Loan Scheme (NLS)	No saving behaviour but view loans as savings in reverse, due to the ability to achieve another loan directly after one has been paid off

Table 5.1. Characteristics of Micro-Initiative Facilitate Savings

Galema et al. (2011) found that properties, including investments, may have a wide spectrum of beneficial effects on individuals (Bakhtiari, 2006), including a potential outlook and household security, amongst others (Mersland & Urgeghe, 2013). Although the beneficial results of wealth accumulation and savings patterns growth have been recorded, this study has not established clear flow-on results for the participants from saving benefits. Savings results were also explored in Australia (Cheston & Kuhn, 2002) as well as internationally (Christen et al., 2003; Park & Ren, 2001).

5.3. Financial Knowledge

The biggest benefit from both the economical and credit divisions of the AWP was greater financial awareness or abilities. Both AWP respondents claimed that training was comprehensive. It was partly attributed to the emphasis of the curriculum on financial literacy. While concentrating on business awareness, these abilities may be applied to family financial management.

Several interviewees spoke of an improvement in financial awareness with respect to the SLC. Each of them agreed that the community offered them a chance to speak concerning their financial position and to share their expertise and experience about methods of handling their finances. Interviewee S1, aged 53, and a mum of two boys said:

“There's discussions all the time in the network of SLC ... cash, and people still send each other tips on ‘don't do that to your mobile device’, or ‘do this’ ... You see, this very casual interaction occurs spontaneously because it doesn't seem like we're there with a community party or like we have these issues or

you see ... they are just a very quick, effective way to build relationships and help in communities.”

Another participant talked about the essence of the community that allowed transparent conversations regarding finances:

“And how should you manage it? And I agree that you should talk of this, you're there in a common transparent sense for finance reasons, however finances. And because it is fundamental to this community, the principles are transparent about this and we speak about people's loans and people come to offer a loan that I was not asked for... It is the sort of topic that other people do not speak of in their social platforms, I guess ... for me, I essentially do all my studying by chatting so I have found that, while I was in mentors because things, I can know a lot better that if people just thought to me when I was taught. No, I don't get much out of studying ... my key experience is to speak to strangers, so I think it's awesome because I would profit from chatting about money with others and I don't see that many ways to do so.”

Interviewee S2 clarified that since money is private, friends and family sometimes do not mention it. The findings in the study by Singh et al. (2006) suggested that, in Australia, wealth is often a very confidential part of people’s lives. For some situations, money can also be a challenging topic for spouses to consider (Singh & Cabraal 2006). It was noticed by S2 that the SLC’s emphasis was on finance, and this area was one in which wealth was addressed more freely than in other areas.

The table below illustrates the characteristics of the services that allowed participants to achieve greater financial awareness. This suggests that better financial literacy for the AWP members was due to the system’s financial analysis sessions and to the guidance of the service worker. In SLCs, improved financial literacy has been linked to greater rates of social contact and financial details and guidance exchanged by community leaders. The outcome was that leaders of the SLC reported that they passed down their improved financial knowledge and savings experience to their children, who then developed saving behaviours, and also stated that it opened up confidence and contact with other family members.

Micro-finance Initiatives	Characteristics
Ambitious Women Program (AWP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial information • Support by member of local society
Savings and Loan Circles (SLC)	Share useful financial information among participants

Table 5.2. Features of Microfinance Initiative enabled financial capability

5.4. Financial Stability

The microfinance initiatives have presented participants with a better sense of social stability by supplying them with incentives. This was primarily achieved by encouraging higher rates of financial inclusion. The concept of financial formation essentially says that since individuals have exposure to safe traditional financial products and services, they become economically active. That does not suggest they have to purchase the goods or services but rather they have the option or the ability to do so if and wherever they choose to or need to. This is an important difference as the financial inclusion of an entity is often calculated by the actual number and not the number of financial products a person has, or the forms they have exposure to. While such goods are historically not known to be 'mainstream' they are often deemed healthy and inexpensive.

Economic stability became a good reason to enter a microfinance scheme. When people felt they had access to a safe, accessible financial product or service, particularly access to interest-free loans and savings, they felt more secure in financial terms. Feelings of increased financial support were common to SLC and NLS leaders. Two key explanations for this feeling of financial stability have been given. In the background of the SLC, respondents pointed to the fact that they routinely save money and had exposure to it if appropriate. This sense of financial security was further reinforced by exposure to interest-free loans for SLC respondents as well as NLS attendees.

The SLC leaders saw the community throughout their life as an additional financial security. Even though not all members of the group entered because they thought as though they needed additional financial stability, the rest did. However, all but three participants reported that the ongoing financial calmness was one of the factors as to why they were drawn to the programs. In fact, all SLC participants involved in the study showed a greater financial protection standard, independent of whether they joined the SLC communities. That was because of changing conditions and the fact that they would tap in on their assets as necessary and also because they could have an interest-free loan if required.

Interviewee S3, a 55-year-old from the existing network of the SLC, the father of a boy, said that he really enjoyed the financial perspective of the microfinance initiative:

"I think, I prefer ... I hope, I want ... in numerical words ... That I should go anywhere if I have financial troubles. Like I have a feeling of peace ... It's a degree of protection that I just won't have somewhere else. It's an encouragement for me. I think they've given me a little security net in a realistic way that I usually wouldn't have. Although I'm in paying jobs, until a few years back, I'm employed in a field that is grossly underpaid to begin

with. I never won, I never made middle income, I was either a small income earner or a worker.”

He claimed he would not be able to get an NLS loan because he did not get federal compensation and the SLC gave her financial assistance. It is also not clear if he was residing in a location where an NLS was open. His statements indicate that her willingness to obtain funds while she was in a desperate need supported his with assurance and comfort and a stronger sense of financial stability.

Another participant, S2, around 50 years old, spoke from the existing circle of savings and loans of the relaxed spirit that she experienced financially with being a member of the SLC.

“I want to be prepared to take into consideration and plan for the unforeseen financial incidents and I feel confident I have a way to do so. I have a common contingency strategy so I sound like it's pretty easy to do.”

To S2, he had personal stability and emotional tranquillity as she had an outlet for his feelings whenever he encountered some unexpected financial difficulties. He thought she had a tool at her fingertips to support and manage his unpredictable financial circumstances. Another SLC interviewee even indicated of the budgetary stability situation that was offered by such a community. Further, S1, a customer of SLC, showed what she felt attracted her to the initiative.

“I believe that the main draw for citizens who were on small wages or fixed salaries is the financial stability that they would comfortably provide.”

She proceeded to clarify that the SLC provided the sufficient understanding of financial stability to participants.

“I assume if people know that the funds are available, after the original stuff has occurred, then ... the party is operating so I will get a mortgage if I need it, so it gives the peace of mind ... So, the thought of being able to only go to a network of people you meet, to apply for support if you really struggle is enticing, for those with fixed or small wages.”

Interviewee S1, a mother with two daughters, talked about the fact that the system offered her a better sense of financial stability because she realised that she would have access to loans if she wanted it.

“Yet, I suppose it's more for financial security. Only because I know that if anything occurs and I don't have the funds for it, I realise that I will collect it

without needing to run to the disaster response service or, worse, a money converter or whatever”

The final argument of S1 is significant. She points out that this form of accessibility provides citizens with peace of mind. She said she will not have to feel afraid to apply for a loan. Sometimes, people go to a bank for a loan regardless of the interest paid or just because they fear they will be denied. Getting exposure to credit outside the bank and not relying on payday lenders provided participants an added lesson of financial stability through savings and loans.

For those who did not enter the social stability savings and loan periods, all three were shocked to see certain unforeseeable incidents in their life, including personal health issues or family illnesses, which allowed them to enjoy the financial support and backing applied to the group’s participation. In the end, the increased feeling of financial stability that came from contributing to the association was a bonus for all members of the SLC.

Participant S6, a woman who had no dependants, entered the SLC as she appreciated the idea that the program provided for a developing society. She did not ever think that she may need a loan because she had a stable income. Nevertheless, her expectations shifted after she became seriously ill suddenly. She stated:

“Why ... It made me realise our lives could alter too quickly and ... A community like the savings and loan group gives you ready access to \$100 or anything.”

Unhappily sick, S6 discovered that irrespective of wealth, the life of an individual could shift without warning and that by becoming a part of a system of investments and borrowing could offer protection for the individual in periods of need.

Participant S4 had entered the initiative, aged 48 years, feeling she never had to obtain a loan as he had a stable monthly income from a paying career. However, after a member of the family got sick her economic position shifted drastically and she decided to abandon his responsibility to look after her, S1 identified with the situation of S4:

“About a year ago she should have been in quite a full-time position ... Yet she's sort of practically ... All right, then she said many times ... "I didn't need a loan, hopefully, but I would want to save my cash here." And her situation instead ... changed and had unhappy family members and gave up work to look after them ... Now several weeks earlier she had a deposit.”

The tale indicates that while people entered the SLC groups for purposes other than financial benefits, they still noticed and enjoyed with time the increased financial protection offered by the savings and loans group. It also indicated that there are

periods when additional financial support could be of great help, irrespective of salary. While participants in the savings and loan groups could have various cultural-economic backgrounds, the loans may benefit anyone economically, according to S4 and a part of the existing network.

“I think it was truly useful for people who are in SLC long-term on a very low income ... important things like the microwave, stove or car tyres, have to be repaired or patched, and they could very easily tap into the capital to just focus on it. You learn these intuitive interfaces every day. Although we had other leaders in the party, I think that we had more than basic income, had more affordable accommodation than the basic salary, yet at the same time we do have a roof above our heads so we don't care about getting funds to pay rent ... It's another degree of need, I know that. Yeah, we had money, but the income we didn't have... Paying an invoice.”

The SLC members gained many benefits regarding financial security from the introduction of the SLC, an initiative which had just been introduced and contributed to additional financial protection in participants' lifetimes. So, what about the SLC providing additional security? The SLC users said the financial stability applied was double. People knew the savings they had paid into the group would be theirs if and when they required it, so people knew they could use those savings whenever they truly lacked money (Schwittay, 2014; Garmaise & Natividad, 2013).

The other element of financial safety that was largely addressed by many of the participants was NLS. The participants understood that if and when NLS would be eligible, all representatives of the established community and the extended group would have taken out loans. Just one person from the new group in the savings and loan circles said that if one was added they would not use the credit facility, as they did not believe in having to borrow any capital. The other members of the new party did not talk about this and they were still in the process of establishing their rules and guidelines. They were also just at the start of their savings operation. Nonetheless, it was the money they looked forward to most.

Readily being able to access a non-interest credit facility was probably the greatest financial gain for NLS members since it culminated in improved financial stability. Some of the participants said they could not save. All the NLS participants interviewed claimed that the products they bought would not have been affordable without the NLS scheme, as banks would not have offered them a loan and certain companies such as payday loans would have charged them interest that they could not bear. In reality, leaders of the savings and loan groups often talked about common problems, namely that no other banking facilities were available and S8 indicated:

“Yeah, I was in a bank, but they won't recognise you, so they won't lend you money. They first ask you how much you make and then you inform them

that I'm with Centrelink so I operate only part-time, it's actually 100 US dollars. See you today. See you today. I was with investment traders and customers and a number of individuals seeking assistance and you realize they bill you \$100 for a tour. If the guy offers you free guidance and says come back next year to see if I can support you any more, you realize that you are in serious challenge.”

Both SLC respondents and NLS participants had a clear sense of which banks will not lend to them and that if they required access to a credit facility, they had restricted other opportunities, such as contacting a payday lender, which was not an appealing choice. Perhaps this was how the NLS provided significant support for participants of these programmes.

The AWP interviewees did not mention the willingness of banks and other service suppliers to obtain loans. The complexity of the system could only be due to one purpose. The AWP was indeed a business training plan and the loan was primarily to help establish a corporation. Therefore, leaving your job can also be daunting and requires some financial volatility. The AWP supported participants with no personal financial support except through education. As participants in the savings and loans circle were primarily responsible for their sense of financial stability owing to the connection of a loan and the retention of lengthy-term savings, the AWP did not encourage this kind of effect.

The NLS shared with the SLC a common aspect, namely the availability of non-interest financing, which is one of the key triggers of participant financial stability. The NLS participants sometimes secured a loan when they were still in danger, for instance when their fridge broke down and a new one was required. Furthermore, in addition to their wishes, both NLS respondents spoke about obtaining a loan for items they needed.

Although the basic structure of the NLS for the SLC remained close, the financial support for participants of the SLC remained improved. Everyone might take savings away if they wanted to quit but then the savings were deposited in a common bank account in order to lend money to all participants. This brought people a feeling of pride and obligation as they borrowed funds from relatives and co-workers. However, it offered greater power over people's financial situations as all SLC participants were accountable for the actions and choices taken by the group and introduced a degree of autonomy over their financial status to improve the standard of financial stability. In reality, it is this additional influence which eventually gave the SLC a stronger sense of financial stability.

Table 6.3 displays the system's features that allowed respondents to feel more financially secure. Interviewees felt improved financial stability because they had longer-term investments and when their exposure to an NLS was balanced with a stronger sense of obligation for the debts.

For both of the developed and extended SLC community respondents and NLS interviewees, the understanding that they could obtain credit as required was one of the most significant factors in a person’s sense of financial safety. This was further emphasised by the participants in the SLC as they had more freedom to access a loan. The awareness that SLC members were investing and could access their funds if necessary was another important aspect of financial stability.

Microfinance Initiatives	Characteristics
No-interest Loan Scheme (NLS)	Interest-free loan
Savings and Loan Circles (SLC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interest-free loan • Greater control and responsibility over money • Access to savings

Table 5.3. Features of Micro-initiative facilitate financial stability

5.5. Financial Difficulties

Not all the financial impacts listed were helpful. Six NLS participants spoke about challenges in handling their finances with rising loan expenses. They also said, however, that this was worth it for the advantages earned by receiving the loan.

An NLS member, N2, a 40-year-old and a single parent of three girls, said that borrowing made it challenging in handling the budget. She said she took extra money from her savings and always had to pay her bills to care for her three daughters.

“Another member of the NLS, and one child's mother, said that the \$20 loan repayment per quince-day indicated that she had less resources to spend on food. It's \$20 a fortnight so maybe I couldn't waste that on food. Yet then she replied, I have something more important to me. Hey. Hey. I got a machine. I will waste [nothing] on \$20... Good.”

She said the loan was a good thing for her. Two other NLS members repeated this, such as N1, who received a \$30 loan per quince and said that it was a lot of money for her, however she handled it, adding that she’d learnt to survive without \$30. *“You know, because you get money, it's amazing because you waste everything, so it isn't enough, you haven't got everything so it isn't enough, so that you should always work. We are strange animals, humans.”*

Once asked about the debt sum, another NLS participant stated that without reimbursement she would always have just \$5 in the bank account, the financial condition would remain the same. In reality, she claimed that the sum she consumed as a consequence of her loan was decreased as she could only manage a bottle of whisky for a fortnight instead of two bottles. She also claimed the loan implied that she had needed in her life certain little luxuries including wonderful soaps and candles. None of the other initiatives have recorded a rise in financial burdens or other hardships as a consequence of their involvement in their respective microfinance programmes.

5.6. Enhanced Business Participation

The production of income is a significant predictor of social participation, closely related to a person's willingness to access and participate financially (Barr, 2004; Mersland et al., 2011; Marr, 2012).

As a direct consequence of the microfinance schemes, sixteen participants indicated that their financial status had changed. Of these, the majority were of the AWP, fourteen of which reported that after finishing the AWP their financial condition had changed. The other two came from the fields of deposits and loans. Nobody from the NLS system announced a financial gain but the study did not determine to what degree the software stopped people from falling into more problems; as said by the NLS system staff, the influence of the NLS software was important.

About half of the participants questioned by the AWP claimed their financial condition had changed, with three claiming that when they had completed their studies, they had found jobs. Of the three women who had just finished the curriculum, two projected that they would boost their financial condition after their course and the third indicated that they might continue to expect a worse financial position, because they had initial outlays but anticipated it to change dramatically because their company had become more productive. Just one member, N2, aged 50, and the single parent of three daughters, said that after finishing the course, her financial condition became a little worse because she was taking out a loan. Four women said that their financial condition had not improved because they had not begun a company.

The rise in wages for two out of the fourteen members of the AWP who received more work as a consequence of the initiative, came from the investment generated in the markets. Such markets were sponsored by Women's Health Services, where participants could sell their products. One participant made \$300, while another said she made \$600.

Interviewee N3, who was in a partnership and a mother of five, said she wanted her company to avoid having assistance and to instead focus on her company for profits. Participant N4, aged 55, a couple of children, said his company was so good that his wife was going to leave her job and start partnering with him to help keep up with demand.

The financial influence on a respondent was really significant. The respondent, S8, spoke about the financial aspect of the SLC as a source for a drastic change in life towards a positive perspective, sharing the information of how bad it was when she divorced and how the SLC helped her transform her life.

“I did not have rental money and no food income ... So ... So ... I brought my children to another province because I don't know what to do ... And I met microfinance staff who was just a person interested in this project, and he spoke to me about the future, about my financial position After several meetings He said I may save \$10 a month, and said to me even if \$10 seems a great deal of money, essentially \$10 could be something that might help you in a serious crisis along the path, and since you know how things go away immediately, what are you doing? So, I saw the argument, so I took part in the community. And that was enormous because \$10 was a lot of money for me.”

Following joining the party, S8 described what had occurred for her.

“I came several times to save money then I wasn't able to keep the money a month ... Too many expenses were available ... Everything has been occurring. So, I can't come and stopped paying, and I was ashamed that I had unpaid bills and had this party, that I did not hold my share of them. The organizer of the cell kept calling me and I ... I wouldn't talk to her Then the car blown up one day, and it all went horribly wrong and I didn't care anymore ... I eventually took the phone in desperation and asked her Give me my at least back \$40, that's going to be enough to feed my kids for a few days. And she said, 'Oh no, I was actually making you payments. I saved money for you and you qualify for the loan, and I wondered if we could help you.”

This was the impetus to improve S8's life. After the program director promised her a support, she explained her thoughts.

“She lent me that, she paid for that money and at that time she lent me all around it [for me], so I went back and got my car and I began to join the group, and I became aware that those people care. When I thought that nobody else cared for them in this country.”

After S8 had received the loan, she went out and got a job within a week and said she had a double boost in her work quest. She needed the loan to be repaid and to prove to the SLC that she was trustworthy and, in turn, the loan gave her a stronger sense of self-confidence and faith. She said that she had stronger confidence in herself as others had

believed in her. In the case of S8, the rise was obviously due to the support and respect of other participants of the SLC.

Any rise in the amount of revenue was attributed to the performance of the AWP respondents. Although people were able to generate income in some cases in a market generated by community workers in a female community, this revenue generation could not support a larger income level in the longer term. Long-term income gains for AWP respondents were largely caused by the growth of small companies. The various businesses began with food and drink, schooling, transportation and clothing. The program elements had been difficult to isolate, enabling some women to start a business in comparison to others, particularly since all the attendees earned the same useful business information. However, what was necessary was the obstacles that women experienced at the early part of their company. This section will address the obstacles experienced by women in the AWP in starting their company.

Table 6.4 displays the system components that allowed learners to produce income. Business and management education that allowed people to create their own market outcomes as a consequence of the effective start-up of a company. Trust and encouragement from other participants in the system will also lead to improved self-esteem and produce more revenue.

Microfinance Initiatives	Features
Ambitious Women Program (AWP)	Education and support for helping business start-ups
Savings and Loan Circles (SLC)	Encouragement and support provided by other participants help to enhance confidence and inspiration

Table 5.4. Features of Microfinance Initiatives that support business

5.7 Summary

This section highlights the influences of the three microfinance initiatives for the participants of these initiatives, showing the positive relationship of enhanced business participation, saving behaviours and advancing the extent of financial stability and capability. However, these programs also deliver a sufficient amount of financial difficulties amongst NLS participants, although this is traded off by the benefits of the loans received from these initiatives.

Table 6.5 provides a summary of the findings regarding the implications of microfinance initiatives to their participants. Our findings indicate that the support network from all of the microfinance initiatives are crucial to fostering the saving behaviours amongst participants, hence, resulting to the wealth accumulation attitudes as well as reducing loans and debts of participants. Moreover, as indicated in the summary table, the primary financial implications resulted from not only the financial support of the initiatives but also the participants and staff of these microfinance initiatives. All of this support shaped opportunities and conveniences for customers of microfinance programs to enhance their financial situation to reach a higher extent of financial and social inclusion, especially regarding the capabilities of production and consumption. This chapter highlights findings regarding the financial influences of microfinance initiatives, in the following chapter, the social influences of these initiatives are provided.

Implications	Microfinance Initiatives	Features
Saving behaviours	AWP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial education • Support from local society worker, including developing bank account
	SLC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enable savings • Sense of shared responsibility • Support network • Sense of belonging that is founded in saving
	NLS	No saving behaviour, but view loans as savings in reverse, due to the ability to obtain a loan directly after one has been paid off
Financial capability	AWP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial information • Support by member of local society
	SLC	Share useful financial information among participants
Financial stability	NLS	Interest-free loan
	SLC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interest-free loan • Greater control and responsibility over money • Access to savings
Financial difficulties	NLS	Loan repayments
Enhance business participation	AWP	Education and support for helping business start-ups
	SLC	Encouragement and support provided by other participants to help to enhance confidence and inspiration

Table 5.5 Summary of financial implications of microfinance initiatives

Figure 5.1. NVivo Visual Map for financial implications of microfinance initiatives

CHAPTER 6. SOCIAL INFLUENCES

6.1. Introduction

In addition to the financial effects on the lives of the participants of microfinance initiatives in Vietnam, interviewees have discussed the social benefits of microfinance schemes. This chapter primarily discusses the social implications of these systems and ends with an overview of how certain aspects apply. The outcomes from these research findings were a real inspiration for encouraging broader social integration and enhanced social resources in participants' lives. Five major social factors were raised from the perceptions of participants including feeling safe and a sense of friendship, enhancing relationships, helpfulness, feeling assured and the essence of mutuality.

All of these fields are interconnected because, sometimes when interviewees mentioned about one aspect, they linked it to another. These implications are the outcomes of all microfinance programs, for example NLS, AWP and SLC. The results mentioned in this section are not explicit and there are no causal connections between them. Indeed, such impacts have occurred with each other and, sometimes, if one factor is improved, for example a higher degree of helpfulness, participants recorded effects in other fields, such as higher rates of assurance or enhancing relationships. This chapter initially explains the effects of the programs and afterwards provides descriptions and examples of the essence of the social aspects which have rendered such effects simpler.

6.2. Feeling Safe and A Sense of Friendship

Some of the main effects of the interventions on respondents was the feeling of connection and friendship amongst respondents and decreased isolation. The SLC and AWP members talked about a stronger sense of connectivity as a consequence of microfinance initiatives.

Interviewee A1, aged 52 and a single mum, mentioned about the advantages she experienced as an AWP member. She said it was so coordinated that the members behaved as though they were buddies, which helped her feel friendly and comfortable. She indicated that she received benefits from the system which was missing elsewhere in her world, such as connections and friendships:

“I believe that brought me further energy, strength and comfortable feelings ... You don't feel lonely anymore when you work with people, you speak to them.”

Interviewee S4, an SLC participant, said she saw the microfinance initiative as a place for participants to live and connect with each other.

“And I know ... microfinance initiatives are for me ... I think that's what it provides in term of both culture and financial supports in my home town - Binh Duong. It provides financial benefits and helps us, it also provides more and more than just that ... And I find it's a support in certain respects. I see its ability to create a society ... Well, it's just sort of a, I don't know why any people feel all right about joining. I mean certain people just want to contribute and feel linked and everything, so it's a straightforward opportunity for members to get together and engage in some respects.”

Participant S8, a single mum and an entrepreneur who is managing a shop, is one of the SLC members who clarified why cooperation and connection was so necessary.

“All of the members, who go to counselling, you remember. The distinction is not so much the counselling sort, it has someone to do with, so it makes a huge difference, it is the therapeutic relationship ... And that's the issue, neighbourhood organisations, that's the link. This applies to the party and needs to come each month to get familiar with these participants even though you just don't like them. You have to arrive and pay your bills, so you have to stay there for at least 10 minutes.”

Respondent S1 who contributed to the creation of the SLC in Binh Duong, as well as being a participant of the SLC, addressed the essence of the growth of the partnership and the indirect support received.

“I just look at them as a helpful device for putting people together, for making ... the chances to speak, and not only chat about finances, but chat in a friendly way about their children and their futures.”

Ultimately, the feeling of familiarity and friendship of any individual became an implication of community experiences. It was not simply a question of thinking they belonged to the community but also of knowing that they were related and a part of a friendly community and to others at the same stage who may have similar situations. The feeling of connection from people was very much tied to the communication and the formation of partnerships that developed social contact in microfinance initiatives.

6.3. Enhancing Relationships

Microfinance participants have spoken about making more friendships and having better interactions. The AWP program seemed to have been the biggest influence for Interviewee A3, aged 49. She claimed she had several issues with her life when she

entered the class. She decided to join since she *“felt it was more an escape path I didn't go for money, I wasn't involved in income, I only wanted to meet people, speak with each other.”* She mentioned that she has gained trust and developed new social strategies from listening to the speakers and how they communicated with others. She said that she met several new acquaintances through the curriculum and said *“I feel more comfortable in talking to strangers. Previously I appeared to retreat.”*

The AWP member, Interviewee A4, aged 55, said the initiative helped her *“recognise and navigate the environment”* by showing her how to be friendly in her region as the group was multi-cultural. She also claimed that she had made more contacts through the initiative. Upon leaving this microfinance initiative she also formed her own social female community, as she realised she had less energy with her peers. The support group meets once a week in a civic centre and she said she *“built great community bonds”* and was also friends with the people she encountered on the platform.

One SLC participant, Respondent S4, argued that she considered the advantages were associated with improving communication in the system, helping her with companions and that the connections supported her with other economical support.

“I just believe social opportunity is the advantage, I mean it is families, partnerships, citizens in periods of emergencies, including my mom, you know, because we have the moral financial assistance of local people, some of whom are in NLS and SLC communities I guess that's just one of the main drawbacks at the top. This is an approach of building a culture. Like microfinance, this is another way of building a society.”

When she was asked why developing a society was vital to them, she said:

“I believe creating a group, I mean, I've had some issues in my life since, you know, certainly 5 years, so without a group I feel I'd be another individual in spite of my capacity to cope with and my feelings of optimism for the future. I know, I might be supported with a certain amount of money from either place, but, without such positive partnerships, they are stuff that help you and maintain your life, through social groups via other associations and items.”

She then said that the underlying partnerships were SLC initiatives. She said it was because of perception and the feelings of participants that came with other financial or other support:

“Okay, I agree that it is one approach that members come in a sense of collaboration and function together, and by that I believe it can be done, certainly at a community level ... A job or by a certain type of shared

connection that binds citizens connected, you know this is it, I think, we can get an organisation in the local government to get a low interest loan to have a kind of narrow-term economic pressure relief. That may happen, but partnerships are not formed ... It may be with the individual in the department, but it's a ... Partnership based on operation, and all right, it sets an economic support ... Although ... but ... When I'm emotionally disconnected and economically poor and ... Rock [filtered] to a government institution to get an interest loan, all right, the interest loan satisfies my financial need, but it does not give me or encourage me to take part in civic events to develop connections with citizens. And ... and ... I think that is also the struggle of today, for to experience a sense of connection. I think it's another opportunity for acquaintances to feel like they are, to be part of things and to be associated with others."

Another participant of SLC, S2, who had been with the initiative since the beginning, talked about her experience regarding social aspects:

"We've seen the children of people grow and mature, events happen, marriages change, people get together. And if you go through any of this and there is a climate of tolerance and encouragement and dignity, then I think that these partnerships are possible. You remember, that's something different because it wasn't a community of savings and loans. I assume that you can have these kinds of connections as individuals move together through these interactions."

Another member, Respondent S1, perceived the SLC scheme as an incentive for friendship growth.

"I agree that savings and loan programs provide incentives for forming partnerships and creating societies, as well as resources for individuals to connect and maybe do a lot more."

There are a few indicators of what nearly all saving and loan members and businessmen have claimed, namely that as an outcome of getting to know people and networking there were more acquaintances and improved partnerships. The services have established ties of friendship and encouragement. As people talked about their partnerships and friendships, they often spoke about enhanced feelings of encouragement. Both are, in reality, quite intertwined. A rise in cooperation contributed to increased support while, at the same time, increased support encouraged the deepening of partnerships.

6.4. Helpfulness

Nearly all the people questioned commented about the microfinance programs, which offered unrestricted exposure to social networks and acquaintances. Many people claimed they did not have anyone to help them in their life before joining the initiatives. However, participants from all three programs talked about the impressions that the services were giving them.

When attendees spoke about helpfulness, this was also mirrored in the casual social support that shaped their fellowships and connections between the participants. However, half of the AWP people said they still had the more organised, interpersonal assistance of the group staff. Most people have stated that if they required some more details during or even before the session, the staff could provide them with answers or at least guide them in the proper way. S3 said that you travel about a little in business but it really supported you with every area of operating a business.

Another interviewee, A4, stated that she really enjoyed the program:

“People straight away give you assistance when you needed assistance. You never feel bad about having details. Without really knowing why, you inquire and get support. They allow you to get assistance when you need it. They're arranging what you desire. And if you don't contact them after period of time and need their support, they will be available for you.”

Respondent A5, a 55-year-old, talked of the respect for the existence of the AWP community.

“If you see people and what they are currently doing for their business, it is indeed, everyone pulls each other together and everyone is on the same plane. And you remember, you should do it. Yeah, the group's sisterhood with all the members. It was an amazing time.”

The plurality of AWP people said assistance and resources, such as travel and childcare, are really beneficial. Seven of the women interviewed required nursery and/or transportation assistance and stated that she would not have accessed the sessions had such services not been given. However, other people who did not use children's treatment or transport services claimed that they were really supportive.

Many people thought that they may like to rely on AWP service members to support them, perhaps years after their service is over. Even in this program, which had nearly come to a conclusion, one woman felt really sad while thinking about that support, particularly for new people, even when it was no longer possible. Overall, the AWP's

funding has become a significant element in encouraging women to begin their businesses.

The SLC leaders spoke of the incredible support they received in their communities from others. Participants formed partnerships and were mutually beneficial networks. Several of the participants of the SLC mentioned about turning to other members of the community if they wanted financial help, a loan, if they were emotional in situations when relatives were ill or where they actually offered each other guidance on various perspectives of the lives of members.

Participant S4, an SLC participant, said she always met those people in this microfinance initiative as she connected with people in networks surrounding her.

“I have been wondering in five years regarding the current conditions of my life so I don't care. I think you remember, people ask, man, how do you cope with this? And my reaction to that is that I was willing to live with it, because I felt helped.”

The relational essence of all microfinance programs has given major incentives to participants. Communication offered by participants as a forum to address their issues also felt better served by the relationships which formed during their time in the program's community.

6.5. Assurance

Assurance is a fundamental social aspect arising from observing and interviewing participants in study because it is crucial for the formation of partnerships and for the creation of respectful environments. Assurance is also important for social value cultivation.

Assurance was important for the sustainability of the microfinance initiatives, such as the NLS. How, then, has trust been classified as a system impact? It has an effect because even if it is also relevant for the NLS and SLC, there is an increase in confidence in individuals as a direct consequence of the SLC, for example, the effectiveness of a matched investment plan based on people's interest in saving. If they cannot save, the software would not be considered successful. Likewise, building trust amongst participants is key to the success of the savings and loan circles. Obviously, since two of the study circles were fresh or in service at least five years ago and because the researcher was only able to talk to them from a savings and loan circle that was no longer in existence, the findings could be incomplete. The member from the dissolved SLC nevertheless indicated that one of the explanations of why the SLC ended was that members already had a high level of trust and had already engaged in a different form of investment, as well as other sustainable initiatives.

Everyone has spoken of assurance. The explanation as to why the new party did not talk about assurance was not clear. It may be that they were very closed so confidence could be constructed or that the concept of loyalty was dissimilar from that of peers and community members. One potential is that the principle of assurance had not yet come into being as nobody in the group had utilised a loan yet. They were already creating their laws and procedures.

The trusting mechanism was specific with new members who had entered an already formed community compared with the moment someone approached the party from the beginning. For participation in an already formed community, participants needed to have faith both in the existing mechanism and in only one other individual in the network to realise how the method operated.

Assurance and feeling safe amongst participants enabled more versatility. This could be noticed in the later existence of the loans offered by the SLC, as they had become increasingly versatile in regard to the overall investment to the accounts, and even versatile with regard to contributions made into accounts. Even if this was not part of the laws of the game, if a person missed a meeting and could not save someone, the party should acknowledge that and support this one.

The improved versatility as a consequence of assurance was demonstrated by Respondent S5's account. For a while, before his son reached four years of age, he joined the SLC network and noticed that the meeting hours specifically coincided with his bedtime. This made it harder for him to join the meetings. He did not leave the party but he noticed that he could not join the meeting. He revealed his situation to the party who agreed unanimously to be part of the SLC and fund the community's saving account directly. This was only feasible since the leaders had complete belief and although S5 may not have joined the meeting very often, he wished to engage in the potential and, until then he remained linked by unplanned connections with other leaders of the party, markets and places.

Amongst some individuals questioned and studied in the SLC, only one talked about confidence issues. S7 spoke of a debt default because the fixed SLC was deemed an emergency fund. She said one participant defaulted and had to fight the participant for the cash. Interviewee A2 also tried to sue her. She claimed that other leaders of the community had so much confidence in the person who refused to pay the loan but she acknowledged the idea that a social worker needed to trust men, who stated that they had to do so. Participant A2 mentioned that the leader eventually quit the party but made ample money to offset the remainder of the loan repayments. Participant A2 also claimed she did not have enough faith in the group's newest leader to feel a willingness to offer her a loan unless she was a part of the company for about a year. She claims that the potential participant, Respondent S2, could only reimburse up to \$60, and she wouldn't be able to offer her a \$500 loan. Moreover, the shift in the meeting structure,

where the party only met once each year, indicated that the newest participant required more opportunities to communicate with other participants.

Generally speaking, S7 respected the other leaders of the SLC along with all other members of the group. The consequence was that SLC groups had a platform to address certain concerns, such as occupational or domestic problems. The optimism they had founded and developed allowed them to build a support structure to go beyond the SLC. This once again underlined the connection between community networking sites and demonstrated that improved mood would encourage great support.

The implication of the assurance built up and formed in the community was stated by two people, in specific in the enhanced SLC. Participant A5 mentioned about the enhanced influence of honesty and responsibility on her children and Interviewee S8 talked of the true impact on her existence in the community.

S5, an extended SLC partner and a mum of three girls, studied in a university and worked part-time in two separate jobs. She talked about how she had modified how the money was handled in her home as a consequence of the SLC. Participant A5 installed her home with a “*drawer*” system to support her and her children in saving or investing money. She said she had a cabinet at home in which she stored cash for taking care of her children, such as travel or food. She retained the money because her children wanted cash because she hadn’t had much with her in those circumstances like she’d had in the past. Participant A5 mentioned that her children called her immediately to inform her where, for what reason and how much, they took money from the cabinet. She said it had strengthened her typical household assurance and responsibility for income.

Respondent S8 is a mum of five children and manages a company. She said the plan helped her to develop trust, both in herself and in those around her. Respondent S8 faced challenges in her life and the encouragement and faith shown in her from other members of the SLC community contributed to drastic changes in her life. She said that she was willing to depend on herself and focus on her abilities to cover the loan because leaders of the SLC group had faith in her. Respondent S8 said she wanted other people to believe in her, firstly because she was so scared due to her previous period. Respondent S8 and A5’s stories highlight the crucial position faith plays in the SLC. Participant S1, when questioned about what was best in SLC groups for respondents, indicated that service members had to support individuals in order to realise what was good for them.

This indicated that the concept of confidence was integrated into the networks of the SLC from the outset and was introduced into the group’s philosophy and core values. While the trust shown by group members is an essential part of the group, they believe it should not be an unwise charitable foundation. Some situations necessitate a more cautious approach, for instance in the scenario of substance abuse. There was one case

of a man who for several years had been a part of the enhanced network of the SLC and became an alcoholic. On one occasion he demanded a supporting loan and the corporation decided to grant the loan on request that the payment was rendered to the business from which it bought the products. He was unhappy with it and, therefore, wanted to quit the party. He quit the community due to a serious lack of trust, but that reasonable lack of respect was purely because his past actions had shown that he was not able to receive the money directly.

6.6. Mutuality

Microfinance participants will be respected and they believe microfinance initiatives contribute to the well-being of all members. The SLC and AWP participants experience a feeling of mutuality or willingness to help other members. Neither of the NLS members mentioned this, however. This could be because leaders of the SLC groups and the AWP group had been in a close relationship with everyone in the group and had more chances to communicate and connect with one another and the service staff. For somebody to believe they should contribute to support others there needs to be a sense that they have everything to offer at first. Such emotions were triggered by both AWP and SLC participants.

In the networks of SLC, the idea of mutuality became introduced into community values. Participant S2, a member of the existing network of savings and loans, talked about the advantages that she had enjoyed as a part of this community and said:

“So, if I bring money into this collective bank account, then I realise that the account has been built, so everyone would be able to profit from taking the loan payments out of it.”

Another leader of the same group of SLC, interviewee S1, clarified the gains she found from mutuality, in particular for small-income individuals.

“Bad members are always ... not much is asked of them, you realise. You know. An error happened. An error happened. I cannot grasp what the mind of people think about you, but you're not treated as a helpful individual. While, if you are a part of an SLC initiative, it is assumed you can participate and invest and the fact that it is simple to donate will add to this.”

Participant S7 claimed that disadvantaged citizens were frequently depicted by the media as “dole-bludgers” and veterans as adding little to society. *“It is how many occasions they are presented, and this challenge is difficult. It means that you should make a difference and we give to each other and, yeah, it was seen as an incentive to support others finance, which they might not otherwise have had, for members of*

SLC networks, especially those with less financial opportunity than those in the communities.”

The notion of supporting others is associated with the principle of mutuality, that is, the notion of caring and offering help to each other. It is important to notice that although SLC participants used the mutual language, the AWP respondents used the terminology of ‘helping others’. In reality, after finishing the AWP, several members indicated they needed to assist others or that they still intended to serve others.

One member, said her own voluntary association had recently formed and sought to collect money for unfortunate children in other nations. He said he felt motivated when she saw others strive to help others, which encouraged her.

The AWP participants were often motivated by the information they had acquired. Four people in particular spoke about having to spread the experience and encouraged others to start new companies. Participant A7 said, “*I would like everyone to get their company going*”. She said she could not wait until she could start serving others. Ten of the SLC members stated that the relational elements of the community leadership were noticed. They claimed they could support other people and improve themselves, which brought them greater fulfilment. Some of these women may probably have been forced to offer financial support to other citizens. In addition, the principle of mutuality was introduced into the system framework. Whilst the business education curriculum was not formal, some learners thought they had advice to give to other people and decided to share their experience and skills.

6.7. Constraints of Social Interaction

Not everybody who talked about social engagement had mentioned positively about it. Nonetheless, four AWP members indicated that social contact among members did not fulfil their aspirations and that the initiatives did not support them and their friends to connect. One of the four participants found it impossible to communicate with the other people in the program. Participant A15 said the time allowed to socialise and make friends was not sufficient and A11 said they would be different in terms of community, employment and lifestyle from the other people in the initiative.

Ironically, all observers who agreed that social contact did not fulfil their goals had education rates and greater involvement in the larger Vietnamese culture. We believed that for motives that varied from their own, the other people of the community were there and did not respond to those parents. Participant A9, an SLC participant, said it was hard for her to match the time of meetings as meetings shifted every month. Participant A9 replied:

“Often, even as you catch up with mates, you always have to juggle schedules, so obviously the SLC party has also been like this, so now you know, we're nine so I guess we're all very relaxed meeting regularly, so it is better. This is better for me to say, because I want to be here when I see people later or whatever.”

All the other representatives of the SLC on the other side claimed they skipped the monthly sessions and offered reasons for preferring quarterly meetings.

With one person, Interviewee A2, an SLC candidate, the issue with the two monthly meetings was to find the saving sum for the three months and to spare it individually to the meetings. For example, if someone saved \$10 a month, they'd have to carry \$30 to the SLC meeting. In fact, whenever anyone had a loan, the compensation balance would be included. A2 said:

“I don't know for it, but I love it. You will have the money each month if the repayments were as \$10 to \$15 a month. But, per three months, you realise it is \$35 claim every three months, so you will have to bring in the money. I've placed in \$10 a month and it's \$60 that's about \$600. If something else arrives in that moment, you use it.”

Participant A2 proceeded to claim that she skipped the social aspect of the party—*“however, you don't see your mates every week, you know, get together.”*

Participant S3 often spoke about the lack of meetings and said the way the community interacted was via communication with other participants. He added, though, that there was frequent contact with numerous participants of the group and that in certain situations many of the participants had seen each other. He skipped the monthly sessions and said:

“I still do ... And I know that at least one other participant also missed them ... Since one of the secrets to the way these communities operate is to communicate with each other frequently. And the fact is, and it is fascinating, that certain leaders, and indeed all participants, see each other in certain ways throughout their lives. So, it's not like they're such a lonely bunch of people who meet once every 3 months and don't know each other, it's like people are always linked in other conducts ...”

A single mum, A10 thought it especially challenging to satisfy the meeting requirements because she mostly finished working on Saturdays and Sundays and the increase in meeting schedules rendered it all the more complicated for her to participate.

“Yes, it has been on for a while now and I’ve never been at a meeting session for years but that last one, because I was at some stage last year, so I was a kind of depressed feeling. Okay, it’s important to attend only because they realise you’re there and you’re out going to participate with the community. It’s just to demonstrate your thoughts, I guess I should do that and give it to and ask, would you bring it in and accept it, but this doesn’t sound very similar to me. I don’t believe it’s about related to wealth; we also live in a community.”

Another problem mentioned was that it was extremely challenging to remember the schedule of the meet, relative to regular meetings, when it was the first Saturday of the month, which was much more regular. One researcher even said that she often remembered what the sessions were on the Saturday night and that they had skipped several.

“I always remember, yeah, this is one couple of weeks, no it’s not, and the first Sunday of the week is the cycle of doing. Then when you’re out of this routine, you can come and go on Saturday and you immediately wonder, hey last Saturday there was a session, how much change did I have? That maybe, you know, I would have, but when you’re out of a pattern, you’re not in the routine, it’s a lot easier to get to the meeting.”

Such participants’ statements indicate that weekly meetings are an essential feature of the clubs, and meetings are necessary for communication and connections and also for the purpose of preserving, frequently as much as once a month. Nevertheless, the interests of all community participants in decision-making may be challenging to take into consideration. This is noteworthy is the absence of feedback on the number of meetings in the other two savings and lending circles. Sometimes, there will be nothing to tell about the topic while things are going well.

However, overall, microfinance initiatives brought significant social benefits to its participants. A senior member of an SLC sought to summarise social factors that helped individuals.

“I suppose that is that perhaps there is anything like a feeling of community you never get while you speak about face to face and interaction, so there are things inside a community that I feel is missing or separate from the real-life contact.”

6.8 Summary

Some of the key features discussed by the respondents when analysing the effects of the microfinance projects for participants and the contributing factors was the

significance of socialisation. The relational essence of all microfinance programs offered the beneficiaries tremendous advantages. The interaction offered a place for the individuals to speak about their issues and feel respected by the friendships which formed throughout their moment in the team environment.

All of the microfinance schemes delivered huge implications on feeling safe and having a sense of friendship, enhancing relationships, helpfulness, assurance and the essence of mutuality. Such partnerships have given rise to enhanced feelings of encouragement. The spectrum of social impacts are not discrete and they are all interrelated and mutually supportive, for one, people talked about stronger relationships, which contributed to more help. Growing support ultimately encouraged closer ties and partnerships. Trust had contributed to strengthened partnerships, which in turn led to greater confidence. These are just instances of how they work and the results on the social aspect.

These three microfinance programs of NLS, AWP and SLC have also helped participants to produce and cultivate higher rates of social capital. This is illustrated by respondents' enhanced assurance and mutuality. The form of confidence generated by participants of the SLC is known as 'powerful' or 'good' as it was local and contributed to the establishing of ties and better systems of help.

The interaction between these social elements is complicated but both are guided by services that enable citizens to communicate with each other. Help, intimacy, trust, mutuality and a feeling of being safe with friendship, as well as feeling less alone, all support each other and they are all components of the development of relationships and social capital which can be attributed in particular to the often-underestimated social interaction aspect of social inclusion. The impacts on social aspects and on the financial elements have proven to be a trigger for better outcomes for members, particularly in terms of individual factors in their lifetimes. Before synthesizing, discussing and concluding all empirical findings regarding the influences of microfinance, it is necessary to explore the influences of microfinance on participants' capabilities. This is also the focus of the next chapter.

Figure 6.1. NVivo Visual Map for social implications of microfinance initiatives

CHAPTER 7. THE INFLUENCES OF MICROFINANCE ON PARTICIPANT'S CAPABILITIES

7.1. Introduction

Besides the economic and social effects of the microfinance initiatives, the interviewees mentioned about several benefits associated with their view of themselves, the community and potentially as a consequence of the microfinancing initiatives. These aspects contributed specifically to the desire of the participants to accomplish what they expected or might want in their lifetime. The findings obtained from interviewing these participants showed that several of these were the economic and social influences already described in the preceding two chapters. The focuses in this chapter contribute mainly to shedding light on microfinance and participant's perceptions and experiences of their own competencies, including the ability of coordination. Participants said that they were more motivated and had more possibilities and capacities.

The capacity of any man or woman relates to the desire of an individual to accomplish what they want. This chapter indicates that members of the microfinance initiatives believed that they had improved capacities as a direct consequence of their involvement and a stronger sense of participating in all of the three microfinance initiatives—NLS, AWP and SLC. There are eight themes emerging from the findings associated to participant's capabilities: (i) independence, ability of self-control; (ii) improvement; (iii) increased confidence; (iv) pleasure and integrity; (v) a feeling of success; (vi) equality; (vii) additional abilities and improved education; (viii) and welfare.

7.2. Independence and the Ability of Self-Control

An interesting result from the microfinance schemes, especially the SLC and AWP, was the greater sense of independence, empowerment and the ability of self-control in participants' lives. All of these are closely linked to the principles of capacity, as they go about expanding the incentives that individuals will provide and to do things they want or desire in their lifetime. A respondent clarified that independence was admired.

Participant A12, an AWP participant, mentioned of the enhanced independence she had as a part of the microfinance project. She said it was a bigger measurement of her performance than earnings. She described this as follows:

"I guess I had more space ... Instead of how much more cash I need ... I calculate my performance by independence. I guess that though you own a lot of money, you're trapped because you have no independence. You may have billions in your accounts but if you work all day to earn your salary ..."

That's not cool, I don't think you choose life like this. And I agree that finding a living I want is an achievement. So, I can do anything and visit any place that I want."

She also mentioned that throughout her lifetime this independence offered her further options as she was happy about having the right to choose the life she desired. It wasn't the money in her savings account.

None of the NLS participants talked of the improvement in independence and the ability of self-control but the SLC members, particularly the AWP, did. The AWP has indicated that perhaps the microfinance system had expanded up the options they had, particularly with regard to their companies. The elements of the initiative were that most influenced members were business aware and the assistance offered by other entrepreneurs and the service worker. When asked whether the curriculum had any effect on the choices accessible, Participant A7, an AWP participant, said: *"It opened them up big"*. What allowed AWP participants to have an improved degree of options and independence was essentially the market knowledge presented. This included structured lectures and seminars, as well as informal interaction and interaction between participants. One member, Interviewee A13, participant of the AWP, also claimed that she had the option of not beginning her company with company preparation. She mentioned:

"I'm happy I could say that at that point I'm not willing to do the company. It didn't get angry since it was at a minimum an educated decision ... I may have gone out and you realise that in any company might be. Yet I'm really satisfied actually, I didn't know anything I didn't do ... It was not only an instinct but a conscious decision."

The microfinance initiative has, thus, provided people with more options in terms of how to organise and set up companies, as well as in the flexibility of information, and that, in some situations, it may be better to wait and find out what to expect before starting a business. The SLC gave participants the ability and incentive to administer the curriculum on the basis of collective consent as they desired. This indicated that people had greater flexibility over their life because this concept was integrated into their system's activities. Partners were able to voice their thoughts and both partners had the same influence in the way the curriculum worked. The SLC and AWP members had spoken of a stronger sense of responsibility over the wealth and power of their own lives.

One AWP client said that she felt calmer and that the system provided a great deal of influence over her feelings:

"And, in business you work with a variety of people and recognise multiple characteristics, so even though people are upset, yell or furious at me, I'm

very calm and collected, and that's really what people do when they're nervous. So, I have more ownership and duties over my own thoughts."

Another participant talked about her better sense of control over her finances.

"Command sound. Use sound. Sure, I like that I'm in better charge, so I'm better confident, and I realise there's a contingency plan for the budget. Relaxation, power and goodness certainly go hand in hand, I think."

An AWP founder, A14, realised that she had more influence over every part of her life.

"How to handle the time, too. How the building is run. Like, if I operate, what have I to do with my children? You know, how to spend time on them, the job, the home, the kids, you know."

Another AWP member, Interviewee A4, expressed her thought that:

"I can assure you that I feel better every day than I did before. I will add thank you because I've been so grateful ... If you are healthy, you can lose weight, you can manage your behaviour and I know that I am completely in charge of my life."

Participants believed that they had more influence over numerous aspects of their lives. One of the SLC participants did not have a chance to allow their children to take part in the SLC initiative—she considered they needed their savings practice to be started early. She felt it was important for people under eighteen to be allowed to enter the groups (although legal frameworks may have stopped this). She said it was to support low-income people create factors, saying that:

"You will wait until you're 20, because I think it's a shame, and in fact I think that undermines why it begins. I believe that for smaller socio-economic communities you will create certain structural improvements."

Participant A2 spoke about this as a weakness of the program:

"That's the drawback [in groups], they'll want them to become adolescents, where I want them to start saving habit arounds 7 or 9, probably around 13 where they understand about value, they don't know the worth, but yeah, that's the downside."

Participants also proposed forms of controlling this, suggesting that mother and father could be served by the children and parents should sign up for them and be responsible on behalf of the children for any management activities. This participant thought that she had no independence or power over the party in the way she desired. Therefore, irrespective of how much SLC groups try to involve stakeholders and allow people the freedom of preference in operating schemes, it is ultimately a democratic system so that all actions will always be made by a vote.

Microfinance systems have been shown to encourage greater independence and self-selection. Table 8.1 illustrates a description of the features of the services providing users with enhanced flexibility, self-control and power. Greater independence and opportunities were often encouraged for individuals by education, including formal training through business training and AWP seminars and more casual conversation. The open conversation was also about people thinking about a wide spectrum of things for each other, including inside the SLC networks and the AWP.

The support mechanisms and autonomy that enabled members to retain a degree of influence and independence over program activities have often added the enhanced level of option and independence. This is clearly just to the degree that the representative existence of the communities permits.

Microfinance initiative	Features
Ambitious Women Program (AWP)	- Education and training <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal training • Informal experiencing through networking and interaction - Support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community staffs • Other members
Saving and Loan circles (SLC)	- Flexible options in content of SLC - Informal support from participants through SLC network

Table 7.1 Features of microfinance initiatives that enabled independence and self-control

Figure 7.1. NVivo Visual Map for Independences and self-control

7.3. Improvement

The SLC and AWP members noticed that they were motivated by their engagement in the microfinance services. While people talked in various ways about this situation of improvement and equality, some talked explicitly about improvement.

Participant S7 considered the SLC’s strength primarily as the saving potential. She told about her group:

“It came at a moment when I and my children decided to improve the world so I started to adjust a bit. And [the group] is being introduced to me as a way to raise only a little sum of money, but I have a retirement strategy and a goal for the potential that is extremely inspiring. I ... I Many that were robbed of any alternative except to please Christ and to cope with my condition with humility and grace suddenly had that option of banking, so I wanted to do so. It was also a lesson for my son. No matter how small, save. No matter how big or small.”

Participant S7 had seen the SLC as a chance to improve her and her family’s life and to take advantage not only of her own interests, but also of her children. She stated she felt inspired specifically because of her proven saving capacity. It’s here so we can observe the flow-on effects that each of the participants will provide. She proceeded

also to state that she had the opportunity to obtain a debt that she did not need to payback:

“I really am an SLC support and assistant ... That is ... That is ... Just this ... Always using a debit card is really inspiring ... So, it's quite rewarding having to pay back the money, because I was there, because I got a mortgage out for my family.”

An AWP client, A4, said she considered the curriculum highly motivational.

“You may say, what we like to claim was your inspiration. It gives me a great deal of strength, helping women, particularly poor and old women. Again, and again, I can utter the term. They are extremely motivational ... I can assure you that they not only inspire people for the culture. We might be for women only, but for the society we still remain second.”

She discussed what she intended by improvement:

“Improvement is ... I'm ready for my company, I'm pleased with my parents and child, I'm satisfied with my society. They inspire [me] to believe like I can do something ... When you know [what] this term entails, then ... It's impossible to do it, because ... You've got the healthy and supportive mind, fitness. And that's what I achieve from the microfinance supporter. I'm a happy woman. I'm a better individual.”

The AWP allowed A4 to feel better of her own lifetime. It helped her to be happier with her lifetime and career.

S8, an AWP representative, expressed the thought that the microfinance program was so motivating compared to her experience of any other non-profit organisation. She was capable of articulating what was influenced and motivated by the curriculum for learners.

“At the later part of last year, I actually met my friends and at the early part of this year, we founded a [business-free] organisation. It's very rewarding to see participants work for others when it's not yourself, but it's other people where you feel more secure and safe and improvement and ... I guess you are...”

Participant A12 discussed what most other people had said in the same study. They found the chance of meeting other individuals who were influenced by what they were doing and helped to encourage participants to achieve their own objectives and goals.

S6, said she considered the AWP rather helpful in a couple’s relationship to her two children, too.

“It was really inspiring, she added. I assumed that much of the diverse professions working with small firms and enterprises were very masculine. As ladies, I think it might be humiliating if they don't know how to ask their bank teller, or whether you know the accountant, or anything like that. And I think it was good to master the lingo. It inspired me, though, because I didn't even think anything about that. I was never in the corporate field, I come from a sales industry that you meet at the other end of the continuum.”

In terms of A6, this was inspiring as she thought the industry was a male-dominated field and noticed that the awareness and experience offered by the initiative had broken down many of the language problems in the company. While this report does not discuss gender dimensions of microfinance, it definitely requires more analysis and is helpful for a potential review. Everything A6 said revealed why it was necessary.

Of course, they are merely examples of a broader community about individuals who feel inspired by their inclusion in the microfinance schemes, but here the goal was to reflect the key topics which people talked about. Table 8.2 provides a description of the core features of the services that have improved participants’ confidence. It shows that somehow the sharing of knowledge and the chance to see others and save money has led to higher participant enhancement.

Microfinance initiatives	Features
Saving and Loan circles (SLC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to save sufficient amounts of money • Can be offered a no-interest loan
Ambitious Women Program (AWP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience sharing • Chance to meet new people and receive encouragement

Table 7.2. Features of microfinance initiatives that enabled improvement

Figure 7.2. NVivo Visual Map for Improvement

7.4. Increased Confidence

The best documented advantage of programmes, specifically for participants of the SLC and the AWP, was the improved trust experienced by participants. As a consequence of the microfinance initiative, the plurality of respondents examined by the AWP reported was an improvement in their faith.

Among AWP's four participants who did not show an improved extent of confidence, two members stated that they were very positive before joining the system so their faith could not be improved. One respondent said that she could not comprehend anything about what was being discussed. Another respondent claimed it had little effect, if at all, on her sense of trust.

Respondent A1, an AWP member, said that she was encouraged by seeing and talking with other people in the group:

“My participation of microfinance initiatives gave me more energy and motivation, I guess. More strength ... You don't feel alone any more when you work with people, you speak to them ... It was good when you encounter people who are like you and we chat, laugh, speak and understand, you

know, in a humorous way ... And you feel like I'm powerful, I could do things, and particularly if you're stressed it's a nice feeling. I will balance on my knees. I will support my back. I will do stuff. I will do stuff."

Participant A8 talked about the information she had acquired that brought her more trust in herself. *"You get more confidence as you know more stuff"* and she claimed she underestimated her willingness to develop technical things until the AWP, but she gained programming knowledge from her children as an outcome of the software. Participant A5 said that the AWP participants mentioned that the fact that she should not doubt herself was one of the aspects that resonated with her, stating:

"Why shouldn't I do it? ... It was perfect for my self-esteem, so I believed you would. So, it was still uncomfortable with me ... Yet then ... Then ... I had really nice men surrounding me. I had amazing friends."

Participant A13 stated that she was not comfortable about her linguistic skills until joining the AWP as she was from a refugee group, but she began to feel that she could do so when she was in the initiative, encountering other migrant females and listening to stories about how they operated their company successfully; at the time of the interview she had recently launched her own company.

Once asked what the initiative system implied to her, A7 replied, *"Trust and the main thing is confidence"*. Participant A13 said that her confidence regarding the system was one of the key elements that allowed her to seek a workplace and that *"The speakers are alert ... Had you been confident you might succeed, trusting in yourself ... So, because she can manage that, I will ... The fact that I was even more relaxed helped me find jobs. I guess"*. Collectively, the AWP participants said that the microfinance service significantly strengthened their confidence. This can be seen from the aforementioned cases; trust was built in different facets of their careers and was not restricted to a company. The SLC participants have spoken of improved trust, even though the form of trust given by the system differed for these participants. In certain people, confidence had been related to the enhanced confidence arising from the growth of business skills. Another member who had served with an SLC since its creation talked about faith and factors for participants' improved interest. Participant S1 replied:

"I think that you're just concerned with one thing and that you believe that you can manage it and be careful about resources. Many of the different things that people have made me is about managing something involving money for years ... Who would imagine we'd ever be interested in anything like this, or I might have, but capital is all that experts are doing. And I guess certain people have a feeling of more confidence, so a desire to pick up a bit more and maybe get a part-time job, research or something like that."

She clarified that the unified aspect of the microfinance scheme, and the manner in which all the participants were at some stage accountable for the position of the banks and secretaries, gave people more hope and would also have an effect on others' lives, giving them more trust in their ability. Other representatives from the SLC felt assured that they had improved financial stability and benefits as well as the potential to access and utilise NLS programs if appropriate.

Table 8.3 summarises the different features of microfinance services that have contributed to improving participant confidence. This included market skills and resources for AWP participants and the ability to meet and support other people with a similarly disempowered context, such as other migrants and meeting speakers that motivated and empowered participants.

The rise in confidence for SLC participants was triggered by the increased financial safety and the ability to be accountable for the management of funds, including financial abilities from other individuals and knowing financial planning details.

Microfinance initiative	Features
Ambitious Women Program (AWP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Useful experiences and knowledge to operate business - Communication and interaction with other business men and women - Motivating female entrepreneurs
Saving and Loan Circles (SLC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial stability - Chances to manage financial plan effectively

Table 7.3 Features of microfinance initiatives that enabled the increase of confidence

Figure 7.3. NVivo Visual Map for Increase confidence

7.5. Pleasure and Integrity

Self-control and improved confidence was followed by a sense of satisfaction and integrity for members, particularly the respondents in the NLS scheme. They spoke about their newly bought household goods with a sense of satisfaction and were happy that they could afford something different. Participant N1, and mother of one child, purchased a microwave with their first borrowing and talked about the heightened feeling of pride:

“It’s my microwave. Today I please my kids. Since I never had a second-hand microwave or anything like that all my life with grandfather, then father and friend. You see, someone else’s microwave. Today it’s mine, and I’m very happy.”

Those that were questioned at their homes were eager to display the things they ordered with their borrowings. It was the first time several of these people had been willing to buy anything different and there was a feeling of accomplishment. Another NLS member, N5, spoke about the joy of having something different.

“They own something and they have different things ... [That's] a little integrity and confidence that you recognise. I don't often have the good new products and everything.”

The SLC representatives often talked of a feeling of pride that came with their participation in such a community as they did not need to ‘offer’ a loan to the banks. We spoke of integrity as they were willing to obtain an amount of money from the SLC rather than head to a private company or bank where they expected refusal. They used the circle as a way to obtain a dignified loan; they may go to their friends for a loan but here they were not non-acceptant as they realised the capital was open to them, as is the view of N5:

“I just realised I was curious because I was able to get it, I didn't have to feel guilty about it, or did you say it? There has been no chaos and I realised there would be capital.”

Table 8.4 summarises the attributes of the services that may improve members’ pleasure and integrity. The NLS members had the ability to buy a new product that they deemed their own. In the spheres of savings and loans, there was a certain sense of pride involved in the ability to obtain a loan without needing a charitable association or bank that others worried might not grant them a loan.

Microfinanceinitiative	Features
No Interest Loan Scheme (NLS)	Can purchase necessary household equipment and furniture
Saving and Loan Circles (SLC)	Can borrow from friends and relatives

Table 7.4 Features of microfinance initiatives that enabled pleasure and integrity

Figure 7.4. NVivo Visual Map for Pleasure and integrity

7.6. Feelings of Success

Eight interviewees mentioned about their success through the microfinance schemes, four of them were from the NLS, two were from the SLC and two members were from the AWP. Research findings proved that there were numerous reasons why members of microfinance initiatives perceived a feeling of success.

The members of the NLS mentioned about a feeling of satisfaction because of the chance to buy a piece of furniture. As seen above, N1 gave opinions about her growing sense of satisfaction in buying a brand-new microwave, which indicated that she had a sense of success, saying it was a challenge for her family to buy new items as the money earned was only authorised for food and bills. She said she was not good at managing when it could have been avoided. The NLS software gave her a chance to buy a new piece of equipment. The feeling of success was extracted from the feeling of entitlement of a new home inventory for this person. What made it easier for her to buy this was an interest-free loan that she could pay back. Thus, the NLS scheme offered the agency a greater feeling of success for the members.

Interviewee A5, a member in the current AWP, thought that after she completed a business proposal for her company at the conclusion of the awareness sessions, there was a real feeling of accomplishment. She replied:

“I recall that when we went [to the worker in the community] to give us the business proposal of someone else, I was thinking oh my goodness, what are we supposed to do? And at the end, you go when you see the stuff in your mouth, oh my goodness you remember.”

Participant A3, an AWP member, said market experience gave her a feeling of accomplishment. She said:

“I go there then ... And at the top, like I said ... I've accomplished a lot. Like I suppose I'm really working to get stronger ... I'm also wanting to figure out more about the industry until I let my partner do it.”

These two learners had a feeling of accomplishment as they realised how much they had advanced before the curriculum started. The impetus for supplying the organisation to these members was the company management programme.

Participant S8, an SLC member, felt success when she got a job as a necessary consequence of her participation in the SLC scheme. In particular, the support and beliefs of the other members of the group led her to qualify for this job.

Table 8.5 outlines the aspects of services which have improved members' feelings of satisfaction. The feeling of accomplishment within the NLS members was strongest as the system offered them the chance to acquire something fresh and that was something all of the participants encountered in their life at the same time. The AWP has created a feeling of success by delivering business and management knowledge for members. The encouragement and confidence of other team leaders is helped in achieving the SLC participants.

Microfinanceinitiative	Features
No Interest Loan Scheme (NLS)	Can buy new products for their house
Ambitious women program (AWP)	Receive education and training for managing businesses
Saving and Loan Circles (SLC)	Receive support and encouragement from other members in group

Table 7.5 Features of microfinance initiatives that enabled pleasure and integrity

Figure 7.5. NVivo Visual Map for feeling of success

7.7. Equality

The fundamental challenge that people perceived in society was that they had not treated each other equally. The microfinance systems' participants mentioned about equity, but it was noted in multiple different ways in each of the microfinance schemes. This is important because it means that individuals feel injustice in various ways and reveals that there are various ways of fostering a perception of equality between many participants of microfinance programs.

Discussions among researchers and microfinance initiative members showed a strong feeling that they saw and considered people with low wages negatively as lower-class people. This was also addressed when there were discussions about getting close to bank accounts and bank loans, as well as in more broad terms while referring to the broader society. As a consequence, some respondents still did not participate with the broader community and some participants often said they were either unable or could not bring friends to their homes.

For the migrant women from the AWP, discrimination was more pronounced as they experienced a separate degree of disadvantage based on social and religious differences. These three services, though, have provided respondents a better feeling of equality. Another AWP member mentioned about equality in their microfinance program's community since most of the participants did not come from a single place, they were from several areas in Vietnam. The key idea was 'When you can, then I will' so you can connect with all the other members without any doubt.

The NLS women claimed that one of the factors they preferred in the NLS system was that they were handled in the same way. That is in comparison to what is frequently stated by low-income people regarding their background in banks or just their impression about how the bank system should handle them. One respondent said when questioned for money from a deposit, "*you ought to go to the bottom to demand to you*

realise, be treated like trash". Participant N5, an NLS member with no children, said she enjoyed the NLS system because it handled you fairly.

"They do not put too many concerns and give you a fair opportunity to get a loan you know while you have all the documents, bills and stuff you know. You know."

An NLS respondent, N1, talked about her enhanced desire for equality because she could possess the items she thought that people had on higher incomes. N1 said the loan made it possible for her to get things that other people had.

"It's because you go to locations to see people doing that because they're going back to your place because you don't, you don't have that so you feel a bit, you know, behind you. You know. Because only if you do that, only you sound like other men ... This allows me just like anyone. You know, they say many, you're on welfare, oh you poor thing. In reality, it's since you can't afford much."

Participant N1 was more egalitarian of culture because she was able to buy products and because she believed that she had some advantages that the majority of the population lacked. The purchase of commodities allowed her to be more egalitarian of community and made her feel more like all the others. Here we see that N1's sense of equality represents the dominant social exclusion paradigm, in which economic engagement is perceived as a form of participation.

People involved in the SLC addressed the equity and effect of inclusion among the members in the group. Participant S8 spoke about her improved sense of equality.

"It's just personal conditions that pushed me in the opposite direction, my ambition to be around more influential people and prominent individuals was there, because it was an outlet for this because not everyone had been destroyed yet, like you said. All of these individuals was in this community and they needed support because it was realised that everybody had to be on fair terms because even those that didn't require a loan or take a loan because they had been paid back for twelve stressful months every ten or so dollars every two weeks because it got damaged, so they had to know how irritating it was. You will actually come and do it, you know, which was a very precious thing."

With respect to how the party performed, S8 said:

"Yeah, that's the big thing. There is no one in the majority who is better than anyone in the community. We're just the same because I'm the leader"

because they chose me and I get to be the supervisor, so I'm not more important than anyone else."

In terms of S8, the idea that everybody in the company had fair access to an NLS and could repay the same loan, irrespective of their degree of earnings or rank, was equity and also that everybody had to pay the same total sum of savings.

The following statement reflects the significance of how an individual is perceived as well as viewed in other people's minds. Participant S8 spoke about how her partner abandoned her and she did not feel like a member of the "high community" but associated with "*the trash*". She said she thought that other people weren't bothered with her or, if they were, they would just support her or feel sorry for her. She said that her system of SLC was perfect and she could rely on it.

"I came to know that profoundly at some point, because when you're single, you unexpectedly find everyone else in need of that, that's your universe. You go from being with high quality, recognising the individuals in distress to being stuck with the dregs of community as it is because they're the type of citizens who you instantly associate with. Whether you want it or not, but many people do not want to meet you, they want to meet you and they feel bad for you since they want to support you. So, no one would consider you as their rivals, because you were their equivalent when you had a high rank, so instantly you were their PR, you were their boss, you were their kindness, so it was nice, so you especially remember when you were refused. Unlike divorce, it's a terrible situation, because sometimes after violence has taken place and all of that is certainly an immense release, so you have the same identity problem."

One SLC leader, S7, said she felt highly respected because she was in the community and stated that she felt as though she was poor to other people since entering the party. The perception of dignity arising from contributing to the collective has had a significant effect on its own thinking.

She said, "*This always strengthens the harmony and understanding of where I am at in my life today*". All participants were viewed as equal in the SLC. The SLC is, thus, the first step in integrating people into the community and creating and maintaining belief in themselves and those around them. I often advocate a sense of dignity independent of specific financial situations. From these SLCs, citizens were willing to shift to social inclusion without becoming disadvantaged in 'mainstream' culture.

Overall, these three initiatives led to the strengthening of their members' sense of dignity. This desire for equality helped improve people's trust and helped them to feel happier and more motivated as people in society. As seen in Table 8.6, equality has been promoted for a variety of purposes in that the service staff did not speak to the clients

and viewed them as partners for NLS members. The feeling of equity arose among AWP members as the curriculum was targeted towards people of history. It ensured that members had the privilege of communicating and engaging in a friendly and encouraging context with people who experienced common obstacles. There is a feeling of respect within the SLC, as all participants of the community were viewed fairly and had fair resources and fair control.

Microfinance initiative	Features
No Interest Loan Scheme (NLS)	Treated equally by society members
Ambitious women program (AWP)	Receive chance to meet women in supportive ways
Saving and Loan Circles (SLC)	All participants gained equal participation to the program

Table 7.6 Features of microfinance initiatives that enabled equality

Figure 7.6. NVivo Visual Map for Equality

7.8. Additional Abilities and Training

The two capabilities frequently spoken about from the participants were about improved literacy and enhanced financial planning capabilities. The first was more prevalent amongst members in entrepreneurship, while the latter amongst SLC respondents was more popular, despite the shared responsibilities involved with

program running. The AWP members have mentioned about gaining extra credentials in order to promote their companies as a direct or indirect product of the initiative.

The AWP business and financial training courses were completed by several members, supplemented by an Education Incentive Program (BIP) that offered further industry skills and instruction. They claimed that the AWP was a step in the way of BIP, and some members said they only heard and knew of BIP via the AWP. Respondent A4 claimed that, although she had taken the AWP course, she did not think she could finish and learn more knowledge from the BIP course. The members spoke about the variations between BIP and the AWP. The four women agreed that the BIP course in market education was even more detailed, but they also earned other advantages from the AWP, such as improved funding and motivation.

Interviewee A15, who did not qualify for the BIP, was really thankful for the AWP system because otherwise she would not have had access to this material. Of course, other financial abilities, such as greater financial literacy, were learned by microfinance schemes.

Figure 7.7. NVivo Visual Map for education and training

7.9. Welfare

Members of all microfinance initiatives gave feedback that through the services of these groups they lived safer and happier and, indeed, healthier lives in some situations. The microfinance services affected aspects including perspective and reduced anxiety rates and less complexity. People felt their needs were satisfied and were more content and appreciated by the microfinance services in their lives.

Only one member of the NLS mentioned that obtaining the loan and buying a new washing machine decreased the tension in her existence. The others who talked about stress reduction come from the AWP. Half of the participants who were examined in the AWP reported a reduction in their anxiety levels and a rise in their extent of happiness and welfare. Although the SLC leaders had not discussed decreased tension, they had spoken about improved financial stability, which means that they were less concerned or threatened regarding their fortune.

Regarding stress management, many of the AWP members reported that it had a substantial constructive implication on businesses gaining expertise or at least figuring out where to seek more details while beginning a company, and that it helped to minimise stress levels. One member, Respondent A8, and the only parent of the two children said this by saying *“It has alleviated my tension, I have a lot of small business experience, where to call, how to do it, how to continue it”*. For another person, it helped ease depression to just get out and meet other people and have conversations with many other members. *“Get out of my building ... A couple of different people they spoke to in the system and my head was interested with those stuff. It's tension relief. On the other side, company awareness minimised tension. I think stuff, I certainly believe that my lack of awareness was an obstacle and I think part of it showed in my anxiety levels. And I definitely eased some of that after the test.”* Another member from SLC stated that the improved financial stability of their lives brings citizens a better sense of welfare with A9 stating that:

“It was really fantastic support for some men. When I recall people actually walking, maybe not performing, as though they were walking on the street today, but so grateful they were joining, because that brought them financial protection and so on. And so, it opened several people's gates, and I think ... Much because the sense of wellbeing was higher or stronger because they owned financial stability stuff going in their lives, it was like a bit of stress reduction.”

The NLS plan often presented clients with a feeling of huge amounts of welfare. In reality, three participants in the NLS spoke specifically of a higher degree of wellbeing. The unhealthy behaviours of two individuals was that, for one, she had quit smoking because she could not afford to smoke. *“Two years ago, I was using a pack and a half and I didn't smoke cigarettes at all”*. She found this to be a good impact on her career. The NLS loan implied that another person could not manage to purchase as many cans of beer for a quarter as they had used to and she cut down on her alcohol consumption.

Participant S2, another participant of the microfinance scheme, SLC, also stated that after becoming a participant of the scheme, her wellbeing would change, since in the old days she could not afford to attend a dentist. She talked about how she could not get a lending amount to see a doctor because she was in the system. She also said that she had funds available to help the situation with her teeth— *“I didn't actually go to the doctor for five years, so I'll be willing to do this now, so obviously I didn't worry what would occur if I got the bill. Nonetheless, I actually made a dentist meeting and I will be home early”*. She kept talking about the sufficient time she could have been working had she not been an SLC member.

“So, I'm not concerned about that. So, I had no toothache or that sort of stuff, but yeah, I haven't been going over too long as I couldn't afford it because while I was in Centrelink, I is on the waitlist so I think I have been hold around 3 or 4 years until you have a check-up.”

Perhaps the biggest impact of the services on a person's mental health was a decline in depression. People who spoke of decreased depression all came from the AWP and said it was because of contact with other females. Respondent A8, who had facial anxiety for over a decade, said her stress levels and sadness were significantly reduced for the length of her AWP. Participant A8 said that when she knew about the difficulties facing certain other people, she didn't dwell too hard on her own case because her attention had been busy with the workshops. Participant A4 claimed her wellbeing after the plan became improved since she was less depressed and gained ten kilograms. Participant A4 claimed that it was because the curriculum made her satisfied that this move encouraged her. *"If you're healthy, you can lose weight, you can manage your health, and I think I'm completely in charge of my life"*. Participant A3 already had depression before the plan and claimed the plan had such positive implications on her that her amount of treatment had declined and she had gained weight during the start of the program.

Interviewee A1 explained how her wellness was changed by the AWP.

"We spoke and chuckled and you joke, and at the same moment you know, in a nice way and feeling that I am strong I can do stuff, and it's a wonderful feeling to do, particularly if you're sad, Yeah I can stay at two feet of my own, I can do stuff."

At least several other AWP respondents mirrored A1's reflections, with A1 explaining that her sense of welfare had improved greatly.

"I don't think I took it strictly to get the chance to speak to other people. I've dealt through illness and sadness. I always moved life backward for a bit. So, they got me here by chance after seeing them. And without really understanding them. I don't believe they know it influenced me."

Another user of microfinance scheme, A8, who was still suffering from depression, said that after taking part in the AWP business sessions she felt better. She related this advantage to the interactive nature of the event and said that because of the meeting she felt better and that they spoke together. *"We enjoy, we eat, we drink, we speak to each other about these challenges"*. She explained why, when she joined the AWP, she had decreased levels of anxiety.

"First of all, I don't know about other people before that study, but I got rid of my stress when I completed the class. In the first instance she spoke to [the Community's staffs] and she asked me a lot about my stress, and if I decided to continue, she offered me moral support. She said you can do that, and when I went to her, I met a person and we spoke and at that point I never felt when I was alone at home, and I was wondering and I was more sad. I

was a little happier than before when I spoke to them. First, for other people I don't know because they might have some benefits for me, but my gain was that my depression was alleviated and my vocabulary wasn't so good."

An SLC member, Interviewee S7, also spoke about the impact that the curriculum had on her wellbeing and her health because of the comfort she experienced thanks to savings.

"My health especially my wellbeing has been significantly enhanced as it was one of the items for which I had absolute interest. I am not too stressed or anxious about this problem and my emotional wellbeing is improved as I had a savings account."

Another member, S8, talked about the effect the SLC had on her because of its sponsorship.

"I have been trying to walk ahead and it's like I found my legs again. And that group was the crucial point when I was ready to quit, and I'm not in retirement, but I felt like I had nothing left to do and I was just being beaten over what I could hack and this band changed it and they showed me one or two times when no one was able to offer me a chance or even caring."

Participant A3, an AWP client, said her life had strengthened when she took part in the initiative. She said, *"All has been successful since I began. I don't know if that's all, or whether I don't realise my approach about things, but since then it has it changed"*. In addition to life improvements, people have mentioned a feeling of performance.

As already shown, these three microfinance schemes, including the influences on stress management and wellbeing and a higher degree of user satisfaction, have important effects on members and their welfare. Table 8.7 provides a description of the features of the recipient microfinance schemes. For the NLS members it was primarily attributed to the availability of loans and a consequent decrease in tension or the effect of an unwillingness (owing to pay-outs) to buy products detrimental to the welfare of an individual. A greater understanding of wellbeing was fostered for the AWP members by business training and, specifically, through the engagement of participants. As part of the mutual contact between participants and exposure to an interest-free loan, higher rates of support arose among leaders of the SLC.

Microfinance initiative	Features
No Interest Loan Scheme (NLS)	- Able to access to preferential loan

Ambitious women program (AWP)	- Business and financial training - Opportunity for interaction and communication
Saving and Loan Circles (SLC)	- Chance for improving social interaction and communication - Able to access to appropriate loan

Table 7.7 Features of microfinance initiatives that enabled welfare

Figure 7.1. NVivo Visual Map for welfare

7.10 Summary

This chapter has identified the implications of microfinance initiatives on members’ capabilities. Members of all three microfinance services experienced an improved sense of pleasure, integrity, independence and self-control as well as confident enhancement in their lives. Participants also felt a sense of success and a deeper sense of belonging, integrity and self-confidence. In addition, microfinance participants had better welfare and thoughts of inclusion in their community.

However, microfinance schemes are often liable for removing remote areas lacking resources or connections to markets, areas with a scattered community or populations that rely on a single economic operation (Joseph & Kibera 2019). The most pitiful indictment against microfinance is that it needs the disadvantaged to be entrepreneurial. It is painfully evident, also in our own world, that most citizens are not

entrepreneurial. It would be unrealistic to believe that the weak are different. Microfinance supporters prefer to encourage the notion that all disadvantaged citizens are dynamic, talented businessmen and women only waiting for an opportunity to shine if they just have access to credit (Huybrechs et al., 2019). Critics contend that microfinance is exclusive and that most disadvantaged people are badly trained, oppressed by culture, and unlikely to have the entrepreneurial drive required to start up a company. Critics emphasize the need for a more universal solution to poverty alleviation.

While it is clear that not all disadvantaged people can profit completely from microfinance, they can benefit indirectly. For example, if a woman has the expertise and creative nature to start a company, her whole family will gain from her success. Microfinance should not exempt young people, the aged, the sick and the disabled, since they are also friends of the household (Milana & Ashta, 2020). Especially in poor rural areas where everyone is connected to everyone else, where one family member participates in a microfinance program and is effective, the benefits can be applied to all members of the family, even those who are unable to participate. In response to the charge that microfinance excludes rural areas lacking infrastructure, while these areas have more difficulties adopting microfinance schemes, several MFIs have effectively penetrated the rural community (Churchill, 2020). As stated earlier, farmers, MFIs and other organizations can purchase a community vehicle or work together to come up with other solutions to the difficulties at hand (Hossain et al., 2020).

This study has found that there are three specific attributes of microfinance initiatives, including the implications of financial resources, the exchange of knowledge and social implications. The financial implications from microfinance schemes provide support such as an interest-free loans and the possibility of investing, which rendered participants more motivation, more encouragement, more confidence and more success. It also encouraged higher rates of wellbeing. The exchange of knowledge took place through formal and informal methods. Members listed this as a primary factor for enhancing independence, preference and influence and a stronger sense of improvement. The increase in awareness has tended to promote confidence and feelings of success as well as welfare. It also facilitated personal development and additional training for some participants. Multiple factors such as social communication and interaction, encouragement and trust from all of participants contributed to an enhancement of the members' capabilities. These findings are significant as many of Vietnam's new microfinance projects highlight some of the greatest implications for them which delivers positive impacts for local communities in Vietnam.

Table 7.8 offers a description of the effect on participants' capacities and the features of the systems that we have perceived from them. One significant feature is that by allowing individuals to satisfy their expectation, the NLS system has strengthened participants' sense of pleasure, integrity and confidence, as well as their sense of accomplishment. However, the SLC and AWP have fostered much of the impact on participant capacity, as demonstrated in the earlier chapters, with social engagement providing a number of beneficial impacts for microfinance members. Such beneficial

effects, as well as the social engagement mechanism itself, have culminated in increased participant skills. The capacities of participants in microfinance were further strengthened as opportunities were given for this social engagement, including market preparation and exposure to interest-free loans, along with the availability of financial support. Having discussed how microfinance schemes influence the participants' capabilities, the final section of this paper addresses the discussion and conclusion of research outcomes with the relevant literature to highlight the contributions, implications of this work as well as providing further discussion on limitation and future research directions on microfinance and human capabilities.

Implications	Microfinance Initiatives	Features
Independence and self-control	Ambitious Women Program (AWP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Education and training <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal training • Informal experience through networking and interaction - Support <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community staff • Other members
	Saving and Loan circles (SLC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Flexible options in content of SLC - Informal support from participants through SLC network
Improvement	Saving and Loan circles (SLC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to save sufficient amount of funds • Can be offered a no-interest loan
	Ambitious Women Program (AWP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience sharing • Chance to meet new people and receive encouragement
Increase confidence	Ambitious Women Program (AWP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Useful experience and knowledge to operate business - Communication and interaction with other business men and women - Motivating female entrepreneurs
	Saving and Loan circles (SLC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial stability - Chances to manage financial plan effectively

Pleasure and integrity	NoInterestLoan Scheme(NLS)	Can purchase necessary household equipment and furniture
	SavingandLoan circles(SLC)	Can borrow from friends and relatives
Feeling of success	NoInterestLoan Scheme(NLS)	Can buy new products for their house
	Ambitious women program (AWP)	Receive education and training for managing business
	SavingandLoan circles(SLC)	Receive support and encouragement from other members in group
Equality	NoInterestLoan Scheme(NLS)	Treat equally by society members
	Ambitious women program (AWP)	Receive chance to meet women in supportive ways
	SavingandLoan circles(SLC)	All participants gain equal participation to the program
Education and training	Ambitious women program (AWP)	Business and financial training and education
Welfare	NoInterestLoan Scheme(NLS)	- Able to access to preferential loan
	Ambitious women program (AWP)	- Business and financial training - Opportunity for interaction and communication
	SavingandLoan circles(SLC)	- Chance for improving social interaction and communication - Able to access to appropriate loan

Table 7.8. Summary of implications of microfinance initiatives on capabilities of participants

CHAPTER 8. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

8.1. Introduction

In recent years, Vietnam's microfinance area has exploded with many new projects and increased government support. Partnerships still occur between non-profit organisations (NGOs) and the financial industry. What was missing in the microfinance field in Vietnam was research that examined the implications of such microfinance projects. This study examined the effect of three microfinance schemes on participants in Vietnam.

The main question for this study was: How do microfinance initiatives affect the Vietnamese participants' capabilities?

Based on the main research questions, two more sub-questions were addressed:

1. What is the influence(s) of microfinance programmes on their Vietnamese participants?
2. How are microfinance initiatives encouraging these impacts?

These research questions were reviewed within the adoption of qualitative methodology and the grounded theory approach. The study and data analysis approach also drew on concepts of frameworks of social exclusion, financial exclusion and capability approach. The qualitative methodology was used to explain how the microfinance initiatives played a positive role in their participants' lives. In light of the philosophical structures, the collection of data was based on data triangulation, including semi-structured interviews, documents and participant observations.

8.2. Three Impacts of Microfinance

Three distinct categories are highlighted to emphasise the effects of microfinance initiatives on their participants, including financial aspects, social factors and the capabilities of participants. This section provides the response for the first research question:

RQ1: What is the influence(s) of microfinance programmes on their Vietnamese participants?

8.2.1. Financial Influences

All microfinance initiatives have been developed around a financial aspect as all participants addressed the major beneficial effect of the microfinance schemes on their finances. Regarding the implication of microfinance schemes, respondents claimed that they believed they had a greater sense of saving behaviours, financial knowledge,

financial stability, financial difficulties and enhanced business participation. Respondents who talked about financially related opportunities listed just one sector where there was no exposure to financial resources and exposure to a bank's inexpensive loan. Nevertheless, two microfinance schemes, the NLS and the SLC, were able to offer the participants these resources to allow them to obtain access to effective loans.

This study did not identify the long-term impact of microfinance initiatives, such as the AWP, which offered higher income rates for female entrepreneurs. It is still unclear if the companies founded by women will produce earnings from them in the longer period. In addition, although female participants showed higher financial management abilities, behaviour improvements were not assessed, although some people spoke about improving the pattern of saving and spending. Furthermore, all of the financial effects were not optimistic, with a majority of participants showing higher financial tension related to non-interest loans, but these participants believed the burden was improved when accounting for the advantages of the loan.

8.2.2. Social Influences

Microfinance initiatives are able to contribute to improve greater social communication as well as interaction amongst Vietnamese members of two main microfinance programs, the AWP and SLC. These interactions and communications have nurtured the feelings of being safe and having a sense of friendship as well as a stronger sense of being affined not only for themselves but also for their family and other members of microfinancing around them.

Microfinance participants have talked about making more friendships and better interactions as well as feelings of reciprocity, which means microfinance members are willing to contribute back to society after receiving support from these initiatives. This finding corroborates the ideas of Hudon et al (2020) and Beisland et al., (2020) who suggested that members of microfinancing schemes believed it to be more about establishing support and friendship, which offered unrestricted exposure to social networks and acquaintances, as a result of the interaction of microfinance communities. Participants also mentioned about the sense of assurance, equality, and wellbeing for all members, which is crucial for the formation of partnerships and for the creation of respectful environments. Although not all implications of Vietnam microfinance initiatives were positive for its members, the negative effects were minimal as most of the participants understood that their lives were significantly influenced by the social aspects of the microfinance services as well as their related community as reported by Huybrechs et al (2019).

8.2.3. Influences of Microfinance Schemes on Participant's Capabilities

This study proved that if microfinance schemes can help to enhance standards, coupled with enhanced financial stability and social interaction and communication, microfinance participants would have improved capability and practices. They relate to: the sense of self of a person, such as independence and the ability of self-control; a sense of improvement; an increase in confidence, pleasure and integrity; a feeling of success; a feeling of equality; skills development; and a sense of welfare. Ultimately, there was a positive implication on the capabilities of Vietnamese participants of microfinance.

8.3. Summary of Financial and Social Perspectives of the Microfinance Programs

This section responds to the second research question RQ2: How are microfinance initiatives encouraging these impacts?

The microfinance projects had two major components that enabled the scale of the participants' experiences. Those were financial influences and a place for microfinance participants to connect and interact with each other in society. The availability of financial resources contributed to an enhancement of financial effects and social engagement activities which led to broader social advantages for participants, such as partnership improvement and a better sense of confidence, inclusion, the desire to support others and more financial planning abilities. These findings further support the idea of Nogueira et al., (2020) and Guerin (2020). The availability of social networking experiences has often driven individuals to become more positive and willing to help others as well as to create and encourage greater standards of social capital.

The synthesis of these two factors has made participants feel more motivated and more confident. One representative from a group of SLC clarified it clearly by indicating:

“I believe, from my understanding now, the financial perspective is more relevant and the social component should become more essential with time [..]”

Table 8.1 provides a summary of the features of microfinance initiatives that led to the enhanced capabilities of participants. The table is divided into two sections. The first column lists the financial features and the second column reports the social features of microfinance in Vietnam which impacted participants' lives. The financial aspects of microfinance that were supported to a greater social inclusion amongst microfinance participants were: (i) financial training; (ii) the possibility to save money; and (iii) interest-free lending, which have been mentioned in the studies of Rehman et al (2020) and Joseph & Kibera (2019). Meanwhile, the social parts which enabled greater social inclusion included: (i) assistance from microfinance staff and communities; (ii) support and trust from other participants of microfinance programs; (iii) greater abilities to manage and plan savings accounts; (iv) an enhancement of the shared responsibility; (v) a feeling of belonging and arranging financial plans; (vi) the capability of social

interaction; and (vii) equality and respect; those results agree with the findings of other studies of Milana & Ashta (2020) and Churchill (2020).

Financial Perspectives	Social Aspects
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Financial training 2. The possibility to save money 3. Interest-free lending 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assistance from microfinance staff and communities 2. Support and trust from other participants of microfinance programs 3. Greater abilities to manage and plan savings accounts 4. Enhancement of the shared responsibility 5. Feeling of belonging and arrange financial plans 6. Capability of social interaction 7. Equality and Respect

Table 8.1. Summary of financial and social perspectives of the microfinance programs

8.4. Contributions and Implications of the Thesis

This study has proved that the microfinance systems have delivered the possibility of maximising the capability of the respondents. The social dimensions have been shown as of equal importance as the financial factors bring meaningful improvements to participants of microfinance and help them pursue better and happier lives. Social inclusion policies have also been tied to the belief that if anyone is financially involved in society, they are socially integrated. Furthermore, the findings of this study indicate that a more balanced and pragmatic way can be used to leverage the implications of microfinance. One of the useful ways that can be drawn from this study is the utilisation of loans. These findings further support the idea of Atahau et al., (2020) and Sinha et al (2019), showed that it has the ability to connect a loan that empowers participants' capabilities instead of simply using it.

The introduction of microfinance initiatives has helped people to have more selection in their lives. This option was the trigger for supporting participants in a variety of fields. Some features of the initiatives have helped participants to become more balanced in terms of both communication, connectivity and economics, and these have contributed to enhanced participants' capabilities. The programs served as proxies to increase the options and possibilities of the participants, such as to enhance their capacity and social

inclusion, and this was a turning point for their greater social integration. These results match those observed in earlier studies of Bateman (2020) and Omomowo (2020).

Bringing microfinance participants together in a place and promoting greater people-to-people relations is a unique capability of microfinancing in Vietnam. Microfinance members talked more about relationships and social growth than about inclusion in the traditional, consumerist culture. This was especially true in terms of the SLC and the AWP.

Figure 8.1 Summary of the research

Figure 8.1 illustrates the main findings of this thesis. The first part illustrates the three microfinance initiatives that this study has collected data from, including the Ambitious Women Program (AWP), the Saving and Loan Circle (SLC), and the No-interest Loan Scheme (NLS). The thesis then presents dimensions of financial and social implications. The final section on the right-hand side shows the increased capabilities of participants and highlights that only when a microfinance initiative addresses both the social part as well as financial aspects is there a significant influence on the capabilities of participants.

The microfinance initiatives include an outlet for social networking as well as financial resources in order to expand its capability. This finding supports previous research (e.g. Green, 2019; Nair & Njolomole, 2020; Morshed et al., 2020) into this area by link microfinance with participant capabilities. If a microfinance system is able to promote both a sense of financial stability and social engagement, it can contribute to a higher degree of personal success and improved participant capabilities. The AWP and the SLC

offered both financial resources and incentives for social interaction; nevertheless, the NLS system presented only financial facets. While the NLS initiative was able to offer members a sense of pride and confidence, the capacity of the NLS members was not improved to the same extent as the capacity of the participants of the other initiatives. This implies that, in order to achieve a higher degree of social inclusion and expand the ability of participants in microfinance schemes, a balanced solution is required to tackle both social and financial aspects. The findings observed in this study mirror those of the previous studies that have examined the effect of microfinance on social inclusion and financial status (Bernards, 2019; Correa & Girón, 2019; Bateman, 2019; Zhao & Han 2020).

The present findings seem to be consistent with other research which found in current literature of Hossain et al (2020); Milana & Ashta (2020); and Anglin et al., (2020) which demonstrated the need for a balanced way of solving the problems raised by low-income people as well as the interconnection of financial and social concerns. A compromise needs to be achieved between the availability of financial services and the creation of opportunities for social interaction. As all are involved, we continue to see drastic shifts in participant's lives.

The advantages of expanded financial abilities as well as greater social participation and capacity development are the direct outcomes of a comprehensive way to promote microfinance development in a developing country like Vietnam. This implies that if the microfinance initiatives are to improve the potential of the members and encourage a higher degree of social involvement, provision will be made of all financial resources and incentives for human and social interaction. That is the key suggestion of this study.

8.5. Future Research Avenues

Regarding potential future research avenues, one possible field for further investigation would be the role of gender in microfinance programs. Further studies could be carried out to understand the results and consequences of microfinance schemes, which can be achieved by including fairer numbers of men and women in the study. This would better be managed to achieve by considering the social essence of gender inequality in different contexts of microfinance.

In addition, there are far more in-depth qualitative and quantitative studies in the field of microfinance, especially in developed countries such as the US, the EU, and especially exploratory studies and field studies regarding the influence of programs based on participants' needs and functions. This would provide an interesting and useful foreign contrast within the scope of this thesis, and practical information on the influences of microfinance programs in a wide range of different regions.

Another field that is worthy of discussion, notably for sustainable development, would be to understand why participants would not go directly to commercial banks and use financial service such as loans but instead join the microfinance schemes. While existing literature and previous research has demonstrated that participants often mentioned that they feel they would surely be ignored for a loan from any bank, some say that they feel uneasy or ashamed to go to a bank, given their credit history. It is, therefore, beneficial to discover some of the subjective barriers faced by microfinance participants and how some of them might be resolved.

Whilst it could be questioned as to whether the schemes are effective or failing to help participants out of poverty, this thesis indicates that poverty is multidimensional, especially in the context of Vietnam, and that poverty may require more than solely economic engagement. Considering poverty should involve giving people more freedom, social interaction and capabilities to accomplish what they desire in their lifetimes.

There is also no single type of microfinance system that is able to meet the desires of all participants. In Vietnam, microfinance projects will stay flexible and adapt to satisfy participants' requirements, but still be holistically oriented on delivering both financial resources and the means of social perspectives. This development will ideally occur along with effective evaluations to enable an appreciation of program participants' roles and capabilities. Microfinance projects must not only be solely community-oriented, but also their quality needs more attention from policymakers and society consideration.

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Appendix 1. Participant Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Dear [participant name]

You are invited to participate in a research project being conducted by University of The West of Scotland. This information sheet describes the project for potential participation in the research project. Please read this sheet carefully and be confident that you understand its contents before deciding whether to participate. If you have any questions about the project, please ask one of the investigators.

This research is looking at the social and financial impacts of microfinance programs. This study will help us to understand if these programs bring greater social and financial benefits to participants. If so, what aspects of the programs contribute to these benefits?

Who is involved in this research project? Why is it being conducted?

This research is being conducted by Minh Bui, as part of his PhD project. All students are required to have an academic staff member as a supervisor. His primary supervisor is Dr Mizan Rahman, from University of The West of Scotland. The research project has been approved by the Ethics Committee before it being conducted.

What is the project about? What are the questions being addressed?

This project focuses on people who have participated in microfinance programs. The aim is to discover the financial and social impacts of the program on the participant, as well as the program's benefits.

If I agree to participate, what will I be required to do?

In the interview you will be asked about your experience with the program, from a clients' perspective, and about your overall impressions of the program. This includes feedback on the benefits it provides clients, as well as any perceived limitations. The

interview will last for approximately an hour and a half and will take place in a location convenient to you. The interviews will be either recorded or noted for analysis.

What are the risks or disadvantages associated with participation?

If you are unduly concerned about your responses to any of the questions or if you find participation in the project distressing, you should contact Mr Minh Bui or Dr Mizan Rahman. They will discuss your concerns with you confidentially and suggest appropriate follow-up, if necessary. You also have the option of contacting the Ethics Committee of University of The West of Scotland.

What are the benefits associated with participation?

Participation in this research will allow you to evaluate the program for yourself and perhaps build on its positive aspects. Your contribution will also help provide a better understanding of the program, and perhaps contribute to program development and improvement. This will help to ensure that it meets the needs of future clients.

What will happen to the information I provide?

All information collected throughout this study will be kept securely in a locked cupboard, where only the principal researcher will have access to it. This will be destroyed after five years. All participants will be identified by code so that their names will not be associated with either the tape of our interview or the transcript. Only the principal researcher will have access to that code. Identifying details will also be masked. All information will remain confidential, and you will remain anonymous.

The results of the research will appear in academic papers for publication or for a conference, and a thesis. Only pseudonyms will be used, and all identifiable information will be masked.

What are my rights as a participant?

Your participation in this program is completely voluntary. You have the right to access any information that we collect from you. Please note that you can withdraw from the project at any time. If you do choose to withdraw, all unprocessed information obtained from you will not be used.

Whom should I contact if I have any questions?

If you have any questions, please contact Mr Minh Bui via

Personal details withheld.

Yours

sincerely Minh

Bui

DBA Candidate

University of The West of Scotland

Appendix 2. Participant Consent Form

Participant Consent Form

Name of participant (option):

Project title: The Influence of Microfinance Initiatives to Capabilities of Vietnamese Participants – A Qualitative Study

Name of investigator: Minh Le Bui

Personal details withheld.

I have received a statement explaining the interview/questionnaire involved in this project. I consent to participate in the above project, the particulars of which - including details of the interviews or questionnaires - have been explained to me.

I authorise the investigator or his or her assistant to interview me or administer a questionnaire. I give my permission to be audio taped: **Yes/ No**
I give my permission for my name or identity to be used: **Yes / No**

I acknowledge that:

1. Having read the Participant Information Consent Form, I agree to the general purpose, methods and demands of the study.
2. I have been informed that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time and to withdraw any unprocessed data previously supplied.
3. The project is for the purpose of research and/or teaching. It may not be of direct benefit to me.
4. The privacy of the information I provide will be safeguarded. However, should information of a private nature need to be disclosed for moral, clinical or legal reasons, I will be given an opportunity to negotiate the terms of this disclosure. If I participate in a focus group I understand that whilst all participants will be asked to keep the conversation confidential, the researcher cannot guarantee that other participants will do this.
5. The security of the research data is assured during and after completion of the study. The data collected during the study may be published, and a report of the project outcomes will be provided to University of The West of Scotland, and I can

request a summary of the research findings. Any information which may be used to identify me will not be used unless I have given my permission.

Participant's Consent:

Name Date:.....

Signature

Investigator's Information

Name Date:.....

Signature

Participants should be given a photocopy of this consent form after it has been signed.

Appendix 3. Interview Guide

Interview Guide

1) Introduction

1. Tell me about the micro-finance that you are involving? Including

- How it did begin
- Decision process
- How did they get involved
- How they heard about the organisation
- Why did you choose this?

2. What has being part of this group meant to you?

- Personally
- For the family
- In relation to the knowledge gained
- Level of confidence
- Any changes in community involvement?
- Any financial or personal sacrifices?
- Any other impact or cost/benefit?

3. Tell me about your experience with the group?

- Positive moments?
- Negative moments?
- What made you stay with it?
- What do you like and dislike?

4. Has being a part of this program affected the choices you feel you have now, as opposed to before?

- What types of opportunities and choices?
- What about for their family?

- Have they been positive or negative?
- What particular aspects of the process contributed to this?

II) Finances

5. Tell me about any changes in your financial situation as a result of this microfinance initiative?

- Employment situation
- What changed in your income level?
- Changes in use of financial products (mortgage, savings...)?

6. What sort of changes have there been in your budget?

- Stress on budget
- How do you budget?
- Sense of control over finances

7. Do you feel you have enough money to look after your family's health, to buy medicines and so on?

8. Is your family, or your own health a concern for you?

- Has there been an increase in consumption
- Changes in unhealthy habits (smoking/drinking)

III. Social networks

9. How did your family respond to you joining the group?

- Did it change the future outlook for you or your family?
- Why some family members and not others
- Was there a family discussion
- Whose decision was it to join, and how did you decide WHO was going to join? Was more than one family member able to attend the sessions?
- Who did you have encouragement/discouragement from? Why?
- Any changes in the relationship since the program?

10. Can you tell me how the loan process may have affected your outlook on life?

- Outlook before
- After
- What about process generated the difference

11. In what ways did the process influence or affect your sense of control over your life?

- Financial control
- Control over situations
- Life in general
- What would help to generate more control

12. Who would you turn to for assistance now?

13. Do you feel you are part of a community? If so, can you describe that community for me? Is there any community that you feel you do not belong to, but would like to? Do you feel left out, different, or excluded from any groups?

- Type of community
- Sense of engagement
- What they mean by community
- Level of connectedness
- Hobbies
- Time involved in community activities • What prevents more time

14. Have you always felt this way?

15. Where do you see yourself / and your family in 12 months? 5 years?

16. Are there any comments about the process that we haven't covered and you would like to add?

17. Any other comments of your overall experience.